

**Work-life balance of working women in Pakistan- A
case study of China Mobile Contact Centre in
Islamabad**

Dedication

I dedicate my dissertation to my late parents for their endless love and encouragement. My father Mohammad Muneer Malik did not only nurture and raised me but also taxed himself dearly for my education & dreams. My mother, Mahfooz Muneer Malik, was and always will be my greatest strength and source of motivation. Unfortunately both passed away during the course of this doctorate.

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Abstract

This study provides an insight into lived experience of working women employed in contact center industry of Pakistan on their work-life balance. Pakistan represents a conservative society with patriarchal roots, when women are discouraged to seek paid employment, and remain involved in unpaid household work. Even women working on paid jobs are also expected to discharge household responsibilities. Considering the tough nature of contact center job, maintaining a work-life balance could become quite difficult for the working women in a patriarchal society like Pakistan. Previous research studying work-life balance of working women employed in contact center is mostly confined to the developed countries or India (Belt, 2002; Domingo-Cabarrubias, 2012; Rashmi & Kataria, 2021; Tara & Ilavarasan, 2009, 2011). This leaves a gap in the literature, which justifies this study. This study provides an insight into the work and life domains of the women working in contact center industry of Pakistan, highlights the factor that influence their work life balance, and contributes towards theory and practice of work life balance of working women in a patriarchal society i.e. Pakistan.

This research adopted a phenomenological research strategy to relate to lived experience of the working women on their work-life balance situation. The study used in-depth interviews to collect the data, which was analyzed through a systematic coding approach to understand work and life domains of the working women. The study used theoretical lens of work-life conflict theory to enrich the findings and propose an extended version of work-life conflict model suitable for patriarchal societies like Pakistan.

Findings of this study noted that women working in the contact center industry actually have two work domains i.e. work and family, and their life domain is a distant from their family-work domain. Considering the work domain, work routines of working

women were caricaturized by high work load, long working hours, lack of flexibility, and meager managerial or organizational support. As a result, the working women experiencing negative behavioral, psychological, and physical consequences. There was also some indication of discrimination, lower motivation and lower satisfaction from the work. The family domain of the working women was dominated by household management and care giving responsibilities, while the life domain was neglected and was represented by leisure time with family, self, and social circle. Findings of the study highlighted existence of a conflict between these three domains, making it work-family-life conflict, where the nature of the conflict was temporal, roles based, and strain based in nature. The study noted that social role expectations from the women force them to juggle between work and household responsibilities, documenting the influence of socially enforced roles on work-family conflict. It was also noted that work and family domain responsibilities leave no personal, free, or leisure time at disposal of the working women. This study recommends that bringing more flexibility in the work routines and provision of managerial or organizational support could improve work-family-life balance situation of the working women. This study contributes to the theory and practice on work-life debate by highlighting notions of a work-family-life conflict, and recognizing the influence of social role of women on the conflict.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

First chapter of the study provides an introduction of the study. It relates to the notions of work-life balance and specifies its conceptualization that has been adopted in this study. Subsequently, this chapter relates to the background of the study to highlight work-life balance situation of women in Pakistan and then explains the work-life balance dynamics of the contact centre industry. After that, this chapter explains research problem and specifies research questions, which is followed by a description of study aim and its research objectives. Lastly, significance of the research is highlighted, and structure of the dissertation is elaborated at the end of this chapter.

1.1 Introduction

Work-life balance has emerged as an important issue of modern times, and has received much academic as well as public attention (Kelliher et al., 2019; Lee & Sirgy, 2018; Sirgy & Lee, 2018). Empirical studies have indicated that better work-life balance leads towards positive work related outcomes (Beauregard & Henry, 2009; Brough et al., 2020; Haar et al., 2014; Yadav & Dabhade, 2014; Sirgy & Lee, 2018) as well as general quality of life and psychological wellbeing (Greenhaus et al., 2003; Haar et al., 2014; Moore, 2006; Mumuni, 2020; Sirgy & Lee, 2016; Smith et al., 2011; Zheng et al., 2015). Despite theoretical and practical importance of the concept, it is considered to have an elusive conceptualization (Kalliath & Brough, 2008; Wood et al., 2020). It has been argued that work-life balance refers to the degree of satisfaction from both work and family lives (Clark, 2000). It has been noted that many researchers have confined the conceptualization of work-life balance with a situation of no conflict between work and family life of individuals (Au et al., 2019; Byron, 2005;

Eby et al., 2005; Robertson et al., 2019; Whiston & Cinamon, 2015), while other argue that the conflict goes beyond the scope of the family life to include social life of individuals (Keeney et al., 2013; Sturges & Guest, 2004). In this regard, Roberts (2007) has argued that the interest on work-life issues sparked after women started to seek paid work outside their home, highlighting issues pertaining to work-family conflict, and ignoring other aspect of social life of individual employees.

Recent scholarship on the work-life balance has favored broadening of the conceptualization of the concept to include variety of social roles, that an individual may assume both inside and outside of the workplace (Keeney et al., 2013; Kelliher et al., 2019; Stock et al., 2014). In this context, a plethora of definitions and approaches is available to relate to work-life balance (Casper et al., 2018; Sirgy & Lee, 2018). In this regard, Sirgy and Lee (2018) categorized these definitions in two main domains: first, connoting to the role engagement of individuals in work and non-work life; and second, to the extent of conflict between work and non-work life roles. The first domain of definitions had four further different conceptualizations. First, referring to attentive engagement in multiple roles; second, stressing on equal involvement and time engagement with multiple roles; third suggests a balanced satisfaction pertaining to different life domains; and fourth, relating to balance in all aspects i.e. involvement, time engagement, and satisfaction across different life domains. Likewise, the second domain was further classified into three different conceptualizations: first, focusing on minimization of conflict between work and family roles; second, arguing for a state of role enrichment with no role conflict; and last, pertains to management of resources to minimize role conflicts. Sirgy and Lee (2018) combined these two domains to define work life balance 'a high level of engagement in work life as well as non-work life with minimal conflict between social roles in work and non-work life'. Considering the

variety of conceptualizations of work-life balance, Lewis and Beauregard (2018) argued that the term has subjective connotations, and may have different meanings for different individuals. In general connotations, it relates to the notions of attaining a balance between work and non-work life of employees (Rashmi & Kataria, 2021), where non-work life relates to their family life, social life, leisure time activities, and other self-time activities (Casper et al., 2018; Keeney et al., 2013; Kelliher et al., 2018; Stock et al., 2014). Keeney et al. (2013) also stressed to incorporate activities relating to attaining education, maintenance of health and fitness, and community involvement into non-work activities.

Apart from the broadening of non-work domain, the notions of balance in the equation of work-life balance have also raised some issues (Casper et al., 2018; Voydanoff, 2005), where some have attributed it to equal distribution of energy, time, and commitment to work and non-work roles (Greenhaus et al., 2003; Kirchmeyer, 2000); while others have relied on a situational approach, where the balance is contingent on the circumstances and subjective perspective and perceptions of the individual (Kalliath & Brough, 2008; Riter, 2007). The later version makes work-life balance a subjective concept, which is open to the subjective interpretations, but also provides an individualistic lens to relate to work-life issues of an individual. This study also adopts a subjective conceptualization of the work-life balance, where employees from different contexts, gender, and occupations may face different issues pertaining to work-life balance. As noted by Roberts (2007), one-size-fit-all solution is unlikely in situations involving work-life balance issues. Thus, it is important to understand work-life balance issues of distant workforce groups working in particular context to find context and group specific solutions and advance our understanding on context specific work-life balance issues.

Considering the subjective approach towards the conceptualization of work-life balance, the study relates to simple working definitions of the concept. Haar et al. (2014, p.362) defined work-life balance in terms of “individual’s perceptions of how well his or her life roles are balanced”. A more detailed version of the definition was provided by Casper et al. (2018, p.197), who related it to ‘employees’ evaluation of the favorability of their combination of work and non-work roles, arising from the degree to which their affective experiences and their perceived involvement and effectiveness in work and non-work roles are commensurate with the value they attach to these roles, where non-work roles represent everything that takes place outside of formal work settings (Bello & Tanko, 2020; Brough et al., 2014; Haar et al., 2018; Keeney et al., 2013). Both of these definitions support a subjective stance on the conceptualization of work-life balance. Such conceptualization prioritizes perceptual version of individual to relate to the relationship or balance between work and life considerations. Kelliher et al. (2018) supported adoption of a subjective conceptualization of the concept to relate to a more dynamic and encompassing understanding of work and life aspects of individuals, where focus of such understanding remain in experiential perceptions of individuals.

1.2 Background

Roberts (2007) explained that women started to take part in formal work after the Second World War, giving rise to the consideration as to how married women balance dual roles of work and household management. In this regard, Kapur (1970) and Sherwani (1984) noted that working women experience conflicts and tensions due to their dual roles, where managing family life is also deemed a priority along with keeping up with the work life. Such pressure also exists in contemporary societies, where women still struggle to cope with their dual responsibilities, and are

disadvantaged compared to men (Favero & Heath, 2012). Doble and Supriya (2010) also noted that pressure of work makes it difficult for women to effectively take care of their children. Vasumathi (2018) also explained that having a spouse and children does not hinder the advancement of men, but could play a negative role for working women. In this regard, Cesaroni et al. (2018) argued that work-family issues are relevant to both men and women, but women tend to be more affected by these issues due to their increased involvement in activities pertaining to management of their family. Rodríguez-Rivero et al. (2020) argued that women assume a different position in the household, requiring them to invest more time and effort to manage household chores and take care of children (Meraviglia & Dudka, 2021; Power, 2020). Thus, women may face more conflicts pertaining to work life balance compared to men, and the situation may be more intense in countries with patriarchal orientation.

Pakistan is a country with traditionalist culture, where the cultural structure of the country has a clear patriarchal orientation. Weiss (1990) noted that Women in the country are not deemed equal to men, and this discrimination becomes more prominent in their economic participation (Weiss, 1999). Bhattacharya (2014) argued that the patriarchal structure of society is influenced by Indian ideology, which deems women are subjugated to their male counterparts. Furthermore, Tabassum (2016) also noted that Islamic religion of the country, although gives equal rights to women, but charges them with the responsibility of managing household, while men assume the responsibility of earning for their family. Thus, women are discriminated with in Pakistani society, resulting in a limited access to education, financial resources, and employment opportunities.

Apart from the patriarchal orientation, Itrat et al. (2007) noted that people in Pakistan have a strong family orientation and like to live in a combined family system.

Tabassum (2016) noted that under a combined family system, women are labelled as 'home makers' and they have to stay at home to perform household chores (Grünenfelder, 2013; Kamal, 1997). In this regard, Kamal (1997) noted that working women, doing a paid job, are more likely to face disapproval in Pakistani society. Subsequently, Roomi and Parrot (2008) highlighted that practice of veil and notions on honour limit the freedom of women to move freely in the society, limiting their ability to search and take a formal job. Roomi and Harrison (2010) explained that women are protected in Pakistani society and as a result are discouraged to go outside and do things on their own. More recently, Rehman and Roomi (2012) noted that situation in Pakistan is changing with time and women now are taking formal jobs and contributing towards livelihood of their families. Despite this improved scenario, where they enjoy more financial autonomy and greater participation in economic activities, women in Pakistan are entrusted with dual responsibilities to manage their job and household at the same time (Sadiq & Ali, 2014; Noorani & Shakir, 2021). Previously, Umar and Rehman (2013) documented that such dual roles of women results in a negative spillover effect from work to home and also the vice versa. Likewise, Arif et al. (2017) also highlighted that working women not only contribute towards the financial wellbeing of the family, but also perform household chores. Thus, women cannot escape household obligations, even if they are doing a job and providing financial support to their family. Noorani and Shakir (2021) highlighted that juggling with the both, job and family responsibilities, women in Pakistan face immense pressure, work and time conflicts, and imbalance in their lives. Such imbalance may be higher for some industries requiring higher mental and physical attentiveness. This study is conducted in the context of contact centre industry, which is considered one of the most demanding industries in service segment (Latha & Panchanatham, 2010).

Following section provides a description of contact centre industry, its scope of activities, and related work life issues with specific reference to the developing economy of Pakistan.

1.3 Context of the Study: Contact Centre Industry

A contact centre or call centre represents a voice-over model of customer service, where customers are contacted digitally to deliver services to local or international clients (Ghazi, 2006). Parul (2014) noted that the work routine of contact centres is characterized by odd and long working hours, higher workload and pressure, pressing deadlines, and demanding clients. Latha and Panchanatham (2010) also highlighted these issues and added that night shifts and work pressure causes biological imbalances among contact centre employees, and ultimately contribute to employee stress. In this regard, Singh and Pandey (2018) found that more than 85% of the employees at call centre in India reported health related issues, while 90% of the women employee responded that they might leave the job at call centre after their marriage. The industry also had bad contextualization due to its work conditions. In this regard, Taylor and Bain (1999) contextualized a call center as an 'assembly line in the head' to relate to its intense work routine and mechanistic processes. Peaucelle (2000) related it to 'Taylorian workshop', where workers are expected to work to the maximum, with high level of stress, and a limited scope of break from work. Belt (2002) equated call center with a 'female ghetto', due to higher employment of females, while Woodcock (2016) styled call centers with the phrase: 'factories of our time'. Zielińska (2019) also notes that call center jobs are contextualized with bad quality or inferior jobs in public discourse.

Considering women in the contact centre industry, Pandu et al. (2013) noted that women employees in Information Technology (IT) and IT enabled services industry

are exposed to poor work-life situation. Singh and Pandey (2005) also related to the hectic and mechanistic nature of call centre job to highlight health related issues and other addictions caused by this job. They also concluded that the job restricts their ability to maintain a work life balance. Earlier, Belt (2002) also supported a stagnant work routine of call centres, where most of the employees were females, and had lower probability of career growth. The growth was further deemed difficult, as many working women in the call centres worked on part time basis and had dependent children. It was highlighted that career progression at call centres required long hours of working, unwavering commitment to the tedious work and organization, and geographical mobility; making it difficult for most women to progress their careers in the industry. Russell (2008) also agreed to these notions and highlighted the gendered nature of work at call centres, with tight managerial controls and high target orientation, and few career progression opportunities. Scholarios and Taylor (2011) also argued that domestic responsibilities obstruct women to reach managerial positions in the call centers. Overall, it could be concluded that work at call centers is tedious, stressful, and provide little growth opportunities for its workers, who are mostly females (Hunt & Rasmussen, 2010; King, 2020).

The 21st century has witnessed a revolution of information technology and telecommunication industry in Pakistan (Ahmad, 2022), giving rise to contact centre industry. Sangji (2022) noted that there are more than 2000 registered IT companies and call centres in the county, and the number is growing steadily over the time. ET (2010) deemed call centres 'a part of everyday life', and noted that employees in call centres of Pakistan were facing issues related to angry customers, high workload, and high stress. It was also noted that women customer service agent faced more stern behaviour from customers, causing them to hurt emotionally, and sometimes leave

their jobs. Khalid et al. (2013) noted that employees, including females, in the contact centres experience higher levels of stress. They also noted that female employees were not working in the night shift, which could be attributed to the cultural restraints or family related responsibilities. Ahmad and Javed (2015) also highlighted the situation of work overload for call centre employees in Pakistani contact centre industry, and noted that cultural and domestic barriers hinder the ability of women to seek employment in the contact centre industry. Akhtar (2019) explained plight of call centre employees in Pakistan by highlighting extreme work situation, stress, and health related issues. It was noted that work stress caused frustrations and anger among the employees, which also spilled over to their family and social life.

This study is conducted on Zong Mobile company, which is a subsidiary of China Mobile Company. Zong was established in Pakistan in 2008, and currently have a subscriber base of 44.8 million customers, having a market share of about 23% (PTA, n.d.). The company established its first English language call centre in 2012 (Azam, 2012). Considering the large customer base of the company, employees at contact centre of Zong face same stern job credentials, that are embedded in contact centre industry. In this regard, this study specifically considers females working in the contact centre of Zong to understand their work-life balance issues and provide implications.

1.4 Problem Statement

Pakistan is a developing country, with lower representation of women in labor force (only 23.31% in 2022) (Redealli & Rahman, 2021). Xu et al. (2021) noted that female labor force participation in the country is lowest in South Asian region, where underlying reasons for the lower participation were domestic responsibilities, social norms, and lower access to safe transportation. Asian Development Bank noted that only 25% women with a university degree contribute to the economic activities (ADB, 2016). In this regard, Farooq (2022) also

explained that women only account for about 21% of the total employed workforce, and most are employed at entry level jobs, seldom reach at managerial level, and actively discharge their domestic responsibilities.

It has been argued that contact center job provide necessary flexibility to women to accommodate their domestic responsibilities and work timing (Belt, 2002), implying that women having greater household responsibilities could opt for low responsibility contact center job (Scholarios & Taylor, 2011). On the other hand, contact center jobs are intense, stressful, and may require a night shift (Hunt & Rasmussen, 2010; King, 2020); making it difficult for women to manage their domestic responsibilities. It has been noted that women represent a minority in employed workforce in technology sector, including the business process outsourcing (BPO) segment, or call centers (Malik, 2019). Survey conducted by Pakistan Software Association revealed that BPO or call center was among the lowest favored segment for women, and was labelled as least women friendly (P@SHA, 2012). Interestingly, Ahmed and Javed (2015) highlighted a shortage of women in call center jobs in Pakistan, presumably due to the odd working hours of night shifts, in which Pakistani women are reluctant to work due to cultural and domestic constraints. Tanwir and Khemka (2018) noted the same for whole information technology (IT) sector, where women occupy almost 14% of the employment space, and that too in lower level ICT job, not making up to the managerial or professional level. They noted that this was in contrast to the trend in other Asian countries including Malaysia and Philippines. In the call center industry as well, the proportion of female employees is found to be higher in other countries (Belt, 2002; King, 2020; Russel, 2008), which is not the case in Pakistan (Ahmed & Javed, 2015). Considering the presumed suitability of women for contact center jobs, it is important to understand factors that discourage women to seek employment in contact center industry of Pakistan.

In this regard, research in the contact center industry have only highlighted work-family issues, where work is presumed to be tedious, and women are also bound to take domestic responsibilities (Belt, 2002; King, 2020; Scholarios & Taylor, 2011). However, women may have a social or non-work and non-family life for themselves, as modern conceptualization of work-life balance takes into account all non-work aspects including a social side, leisure time activities, and any other important activities as presumed by working women (Casper et al., 2018; Keeney et al., 2013; Kelliher et al., 2018). Therefore, it is also important to understand a true manifestation of work-life balance for women working in contact center industry to understand their view on work, family, and life and the balance between to encourage them to seek and maintain employment in contact center industry of Pakistan as Tanwir and Kemka (2018) proposed that factors like flexibility in working hours, provision of day care centers, working from home, and paternity leave could facilitate women participation in employment landscape of IT related industries.

Apart from that, much of the work on work-life balance is concentrated in the developed countries (Change et al., 2010; Rashmi & Kataria, 2021), while work on women working in call centers is concentrated in either developed countries or in India (Belt, 2002; Domingo-Cabarrubias, 2012; Ng & Mitter, 2005; Norman et al., 2004; Singh & Pandey, 2005; Tara & Ilavarasan, 2009, 2011). Very few studies have considered dynamics of work-life balance for Pakistan, a country with different social and cultural structure. Few studies available for Pakistan only note work-family dynamics of women working in contact center industry (Ahmed & Javed, 2015; Khalid et al., 2013). This study considers work-life balance in its subjective connotations, and tries to understand work-life balance dynamics of women working in contact center industry of Pakistan to provide implications.

1.5 Research Questions

Considering the research problem, following are the questions that this study seeks to answer:

- How women working in contact centre industry of Pakistan describe their work-life balance experience?
- Which factors restrict or support attainment of work-life balance in contact centre industry of Pakistan?
- How contact centre industry could support their women employee in attainment of work-life balance in Pakistan?

1.6 Research aim and objectives

The aim of this research is to understand dynamics of work-life balance of female employees of contact centre industry of Pakistan. In this regard, following research objectives are attained by this study:

- Understanding subjective meaning and contextualization of work-life balance for women working in contact centre industry of Pakistan.
- Assessment of the level of work-life balance being experienced by women working in contact centre industry of Pakistan.
- Identification of the factors hindering the ability of women to attain work-life balance in contact centre industry of Pakistan.
- Provide implications and suggest policies to improve the work-life balance of women working in contact centre industry of Pakistan.

1.7 Significance of research

It has been noted that women are underrepresented in employed workforce of contact centre industry of Pakistan. Further, available scholarship encourages to conceptualize and understand notions of work-life balance with its subjective and

contextual manifestations. Considering these two aspects, this study has both practical and theoretical significance. On practical context, this study enables the managers and policy makers to understand meanings of work-life balance from a view point of women actually working in contact centre industry of Pakistan. This enables them to use this understanding to devise appropriate policies to support women in attainment of work-life balance. Thus, managers in contact centre industry could not only improve productivity and job satisfaction of their female employees, but also encourage women to seek employment in contact centre industry, ensuring better recruitment and selection outcomes. Thus, findings of this study could help contact centre industry in a meaningful and practical manner.

Considering the theoretical side, this study contributes to the emerging body of literature by providing conceptualization of work-life balance of women employees in a particular context i.e. contact centre industry of Pakistan. Thus, this study encourages to adopt an open approach to understand and conceptualize work-life balance by adopting a subjective and context bound approach. Further, much of the available scholarship on work-life balance is related to the developed world and there is a need to study the phenomenon for less developed countries (Rashmi & Kataria, 2021) like Pakistan. Moreover, work on contact centre industry has two shortcomings in this regard. Firstly, it only considers to balance out work-family considerations, whereas the current debate argues balancing of work-life considerations. This study considers broader conceptualization of work-life balance to consider all non-work aspects of individual's life. Secondly, available scholarship on contact centre industry have considered contact centres in developed world. Apart from that, India received considerable attention due to its prominence in BPO and call centre services. Meagre evidence was available in the literature for other developing countries like Pakistan.

Thus, this study contributes to the body of literature by highlighting the subjective and contextual conceptualization of work-life balance. Further, it also provides evidence on the credentials of work-life balance of women working in the developing economy Pakistan in its full scope and conceptualization, which received limited attention in available scholarship.

1.8 Structure of the dissertation

This dissertation is divided into seven parts. First part, introduction chapter provides background and context of the study, elaborates research problem, states research questions, and highlights significance of the research. Second part, literature review provides overview of the previous research on work-life balance by relating to its evolution, relate to its conceptualization, describe work life balance for working women in developing economies, and in Pakistan. Third part, theoretical framework provides an overview of theories on work-life balance. Fourth part, research methodology provides details on the research plan by relating to adoption of research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, sampling strategy, data collection method, and data analysis procedure. Fifth part, findings and interpretations discusses results inferred from the collected data and relates to lived experience of the women concerning domains of work, and life; and also discusses the findings in the light of existing theories. Sixth part, conclusion concludes the study by relating to main findings of study, acknowledging limitations, highlighting contributions, providing implications for practice and policy, and recommending avenues for future research.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

Chapter two of the dissertation provides review of the available literature on work-life balance. The chapter starts with the evaluation of debate on the work life balance and its shaping with time in practical as well as theoretical context. After a detailed elaboration of work life balance and its evolution over time, the chapter discusses conceptualization of work life balance by considering its elements i.e. the work, the life, and the balance. In this part, all three aspects are related to the call centre industry to relate to the nature of work in the industry, visible life aspects of call centre workers, and work-life balance situation of call centre employees. Subsequently, matters pertaining to the work life balance of women is taken up to relate to their work and life aspects.

2.1 Evolution of work-life balance

Although academic focus on the work life balance emerged in 1970's, after women started to opt for the formal employment (Frame & Hartog, 2003; Kelliher et al., 2019). The issues had been prevalent since the beginning of communal living and organized working. Naithani (2010) related to the historical aspects of work-life balance, where the evolution was segregated into different phases. The first phase relates to early life of communal living, where people started to work outside home, mostly at farms near home. At this phase, all family members used to work together and focus of the work remained on food security (Mmbengwa et al., 2015). After that came the pre-industrialization phase, where trade and craft business started to take hold of economic landscape, causing division of work and family life. Lambert (1981) related to the early shift from agriculture to organized Guild work, and noted that guild work

had implications for the social life of people. Likewise, trade in the ancient times was a risky venture, requiring long travels, and other risks (Howard, 2014). Both of these work required long working hours and sacrifice of family and social life. Afterwards, industrial revolution brought more formalization into work setting, where factories and industrial areas were established, often away from home (Naithani, 2010). Baker (2017) related to the life of a baker, who got carried away with the merchandising opportunities during the growth phase of industrial revolution. It was noted that although his wealth was increasing, he was increasingly struggling with his new social and family life. Ultimately, he got bankrupt, and iterated that bankruptcy proved blessing as he felt happy with his small business, family, and friends. Further, Voydanoff (2014) explained that during this time, men started to dominate factory workforce, and women were charged with the responsibilities of managing household, further causing segregation of work roles, where men were to go out and women were to remain at home. Snooks (2002) argued that industry remained labor intensive and relied heavily on the physical strength, giving men advantage compared to women at the workplace, reinforcing the role of men as earning hand, and women as homemaker. Thus, during this whole period, most men were working outside, and there no discussion of work-life balance, expect concerns for long working hours and unfavorable working conditions. Such unfair treatment of workers gave rise to establishment of labor unions and calls for reduction in working hours (Skidelsky, 2019). Apart from that, there seem to be no explicit account of work-life balance during this time.

After industrial revolution, technological advancements reduced the need of physical strength in the workplace, resulting in greater women participation of in the formal workforce (Snooks, 2002). Roberts (2007) noted that greater participation of women in

workforce started roughly after the World War II. Such increased participation of women did not subdue their primary responsibility as home-maker, and women had to take care of their children and household, in addition to their work responsibilities (Gatrell et al., 2013). Lockwood (2003) also noticed an increasing rate of women participation in formal work during 1980s and 1990s, and as result, organization started to offer various support programs to facilitate women workers, particularly mothers. At the same time, academic interest on the work-life balance shifted towards dual career couples (Gilbert et al., 1987; Hochschild, 1997; Rapoport & Rapoport, 1977), with primary focus on women and their ability to negotiate a balance between work and child care (Kelliher, 2018). During this phase, a concern on work-life balance emerged, but this concern was largely limited to 'women issues' or 'social issues'. During this time, HR practitioners also started to stress on work-life balance issues to argue that it was not only good for the individual employees, but also for the whole of organization (Frame & Hartog, 2003). Work-life balance issues were also much highlighted by The Women's Liberation Movement in the industrial countries. The movement called for more facilitation to women including maternity leave, flexible work schedule, and related accommodations (Raja & Stein, 2014). Further, legal developments by the end of 20th century further strengthened the case of work-life balance (Frame & Hartog, 2003), whereas the idea of work-life balance also expanded to men with argument that people want to maintain a balance between their personal and professional lives and require flexibility to manage their work schedules, which contributes towards their work and life satisfaction (Raja & Stein, 2014). Thus, work-life balance became a general, less gender specific issue in the early years of 21st century (Lockwood, 2003; Raja & Stein, 2014). Naithani and Jha (2009) categorized the factors, causing an increased focus on the work-life balance during

second half of 20th century and noted three categories of these factors i.e. family and personal life related factors highlighting a greater work participation of women, child bearing women, dual career couples, and single parent stressing the considerations related to child and elderly care, and related health and wellbeing issues; work related factors, indicating the changing dynamics of the nature of work with characteristics like long working hours, unpaid overtime, demands for shorter work hours, working part time, work stress, intense nature of work, and changing timing of work; and other factors including ageing population, rise of service sector, technological complexities, skill gaps, lack of social support networks, demographic shifts, and globalization. Previously, Frame and Hartog (2003) also highlighted changing nature of work, shift towards service oriented economy, long working hours, and legislative developments as supporting factors, facilitating evolution of work-life balance in the practice. The notions on work-life balance further strengthened after advent of 21st century and the domain evolved as a multidisciplinary field of enquiry and conceptualization. The focus of enquiry started shifting from the manufacturing to the service sector roles, like client focus and work intensification in professions like consulting, finance, education, and law (Sommerlad, 2016). Further, explosion of information and communication technology have further provoked the issue by blurring the boundaries between work and life (Des Horts et al., 2011; Kelliher et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019). The latest focus of the debate and enquiry on work-life balance has been diverted to the implications of COVID-19 for work-life balance (Hjálmsdóttir & Bjarnadóttir, 2021; Vyas, 2022).

Apart from the evolution of work-life balance in practical context, where organizations and practitioners started to levy increased attention to work life balance considerations, academics also started to provide theoretical models to understand

the sources and implications of work-life balance. The review of literature provides five models of work-life balance (Guest, 2002; Khateeb, 2021; Zedeck & Mosier, 1990). These theoretical models explain the relationship between work and life of individuals. First of these models is segmentation model, which segregates work from the non-work life, and assumes that there is no connection between these two domains (Guest, 2002). The model argues that individuals can function in a successful manner in one sphere without any influence of the other (Evans & Bartolomé, 1984; Payton-Miyazaki & Brayfield, 1976; Zedeck & Mosier, 1990). Thus, the separation of time, spaces, and activities allow individuals to function in a segmented manner, where work segment is a competitive, impersonal, and instrumental sphere, while non-work segment is considered a sphere of expression, intimacy, affection, and relationships (Piotrkowski, 1979; Zedeck & Mosier, 1990). Naithani (2010) believed that segmentation of the work was caused by the movement of workforce from rural to urban areas, whereas Guest (2002) noted that the model lacks empirical support from the literature. Subsequently, spillover model argues that there is no strict segregation of work and non-work life (Dén-Nagy, 2014). Although both of these are separated by time and space, spillover of values, skills, attitudes, emotions, or behavior could happen between these two domains, blurring the boundaries and influencing people (Staines, 1980). Thus, it is argued that satisfaction and happiness from the work spills over to the non-work life of individuals (Zedeck & Mosier, 1990). Kando and Summers (1971) argued that attitudes related the work become an ingrained aspect of the personality and are translated into home life. Likewise, Mortimer et al. (1986) noted that such ingrained attitudes influence orientation of an individual towards children, others, and also self. Thus, the behavioral boundaries between work and non-work life get blurred (Zedeck & Mosier, 1990). In this regard, Pleck (1995) noted that the

direction of spillover may be different between two gender cohorts, where women may experience it from family to work, and men vice versa. Guest (2002) indicates towards the empirical plausibility of the theory, but objected on the generic nature of proposition. It could be argued that the proposition is too open for the interpretation and fails to account for variability in the situations and experiences. Despite its generic nature, spillover model established inter-relationship of both work and home domains, leading towards further development of theoretical models.

In this regard, Staines (1980) proposed a compensation model propagating an inverse relationship between work and family life, making these two antithetical in nature. Therefore, individuals make up in one sphere of their life, in terms of satisfaction or demands, for lacking in the other. Guest (2002) exemplified that, someone with routine and undemanding work may compensate it by playing an active and major role in local community related activities outside work settings. Thus, worker tries to compensate for the deficit in one sphere of life (work or family), by extending more resources (time and effort) in the other sphere (Khateeb, 2021). Kando and Summers (1971) identified two components of the compensation theory: first, supplemental compensation relates to the situation where lack of psychological states, behaviors, or experiences in the workplace are compensated by an increased involvement in the family activities; and second, reactive compensation relates to the situation, where individual seeks to make up for his work related deprivations through non-work related activities, such like involvement in leisure activities. Scholarios and Marks (2004) noted that compensation theory seemed to meant for typical male worker, working in an industrial setting. Subsequently, instrumental model argues that actions in on sphere of life are instrumental to success in the other sphere (Guest, 2002). The model presumes that one environment, particularly work is a mean to achieve better

ends in the other environment (Zedeck & Mosier, 1990). In this regard, Evans and Bartolomé (1980) argued that work and good career support building and maintaining a successful and satisfying family and leisure life, and vice versa. Guest (2002) also exemplified this by highlighting the efforts of a worker, seeking extra work of long hours and routine job to maximize earnings, that are required to buy a car or home for his/her family. Thus, work outcomes may be instrumental to achieve family related ends, and vice versa.

The last theoretical model describing the interrelationship between work and non-work life is conflict model, which has sparked academic interest in recent times (Guest, 2002). The model was proposed by Greenhaus and Beutell (1985), who explicitly noted existence of work-family conflict in situations where time is to be allocated between work and family, making it difficult to meet requirements of both life spheres; stress from participation of one role makes it difficult to effectively participate in the other; and specific behaviours required in one sphere make it difficult to meet requirements of the other. Thus, a three pronged source of conflict was proposed, where conflict could arise from time allocation, role strain, and behavioural requirements. Thus, satisfaction or progress in one sphere may require sacrifice in the other, as both of these spheres have different expectations, requirements, and norms (Guest, 2002; Zedeck & Mosier, 1990). These theoretical models are descriptive models, relating to work and family life and their possible interrelations. Guest (2002) highlighted that, individually these models have limited practical value, while embedding these models with the causes and consequences could yield better value. These models serve as starting point of modern thinking on the work life balance as they shed light on the interaction of work with family, and also account for other non-work aspects of life like leisure activities. Subsequent section of literature review

relates to the conceptualization of elements of work-life balance.

2.2 Work-life Balance

Work-life balance connotes the relationship between work aspect and non-work aspect of life of working individuals, where modern conceptualization stresses on achievement of satisfactory balance between these two. Such balance is to be attained by restricting one side, normally work, to spare time and energy for the other i.e. non-work life including family and other leisure activities (Kelliher et al., 2018). Initial notions on the work-life or rather work-family balance deem these two aspects as mutually incompatible (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985), giving rise to the notions of conflict, having negative consequences for employees, organizations, and families (Allen et al., 2000; Eby et al., 2005). Subsequent work has evoked notions of work-family enrichment, where experiences in one sphere of life could improve quality of life in the other (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006), contributing towards individual, organizational, and family related outcomes (McNall et al., 2010; Shockley & Singla, 2011; Zhang et al., 2018). Casper et al. (2018) highlighted that the domains of work and life are well established, while connotations of the balance are often contested. It would be useful to understand connotations relating to these three aspects i.e. the work, the life, and the balance. Description of these three aspects in isolation would provide functional ease, where a comprehensive conceptualization of work-life balance might be elusive, but understanding these three aspects in isolation would clarify functionality and usability of these terminology.

2.2.1 The work

Since the advent of industrial revolution, the nature of work is in a process of evolution and change. Modern day work dynamics are characterized by automation and use of information technology (Abraham, 2008; Webster & Ivanov, 2020). Vorhauser-Smith

and Cariss (2017) also noted emergence of contemporary forms of employment contracts along with a rise of self-employment options and gig economy jobs. They argued that these trends were consistent across many countries and these developments were expected to continue in the future to change landscape of employment arrangements and nature of work. Much of the focus on the work-life balance studies has focused on standard work arrangements, characterized by permanent-full time work, during standard working hours, with single employer (Deloitte, 2018). Recent scholarship on the issue has considered flexibility as part of work environment and routine (Chung & Van der Lippe, 2020; Prowse & Prowse, 2015; Timms et al., 2015). The embedded flexibility into modern form of work like annual hour contracts, zero hours' contracts, and variable working schedule results in complicated work related routines and outcomes (Kelliher et al., 2018). Cannon (2017) noted that such working arrangements result in intense work activity during some periods, and lighter or no work during others. Rubery et al. (2016) raised concerns on the stability and predictability of the earnings of such workers. O'Sullivan et al. (2015) also related to the non-standard working hours of such workers, and their tendency to overwork due to unpredictability on availability of the work. Therefore, contemporary work arrangements are reshaping to accommodate technological trends, and many work arrangements try to incorporate flexibility in the work schemes. However, such flexibility may cause more strain for the workers, creating uncertainty and contributing to their share of work related strain.

Contact centre industry is one of the fast growing industry in various countries, where work arrangements and routines are different from traditional work model. Sawyerr et al. (2009) noted higher employee turnover rates for the industry, which they attributed to the nature of work and related pressures. Deery et al. (2010) found that contact

centre employees face higher levels of job strain, where such strain increases after introduction or special offers and dispatch of invoices, as contact centre workers have to deal with high call volumes during that activity. They also noted that product range, services, pricing, and discounts rapidly change at contact centre industry, where employees have to read, absorb, revise, and update information constantly to remain updated and ensure consistent customer services. Such work setting requires extreme monitoring, creating pressure on the workers (Taylor & Bain, 2005). In this regard, Pico (2006) also argued that excessive monitoring along with a pressure to achieve performance target provokes stress and feelings of dissatisfaction among contact centre workers. Apart from these issues, there are issues pertaining to dealing of aggressive and abusive clients in the call centres (Maos, 2014; Poddar & Madupalli, 2012). It has also been noted that work in call centres is highly monotonous in nature with low prospects of growth and skill development (Belt et al., 2002; Domingo-Cabarrubias, 2012), making the work tedious and boring. The communication in the contact centre is also one way, from top to bottom, and through formal means like e-mail, intranet, bulletin board, memos, and team meetings (Bool-Sale & Sale, 2010). Such communication is devoid of consultative process, hindering empowerment prospects of employees, and scope of their job autonomy. Pico (2006) also highlighted that contact centre industry requires its workers to work at night and in variable shifts, making it difficult for them to have social interactions outside of their work environment. Highly monotonous work nature of call centres could be equated to assembly line production (Taylor & Bain, 1999), where jobs are highly standardized requiring the clients to have a dyadic communicative interaction with individual clients, where such interaction is guided by a formal script, invoking a feeling of lower job autonomy and control among the workers (Varca, 2001).

Thus, it could be argued that nature of work arrangements is changing over time, where employers are increasingly offering flexible working arrangements for their employees. Such arrangements might give rise to certain issues, requiring employees to overwork or remain strained due to work related uncertainties. Further, call centre work, although is deemed contemporary form of employment, bring various work related challenges for the employees. These challenges could be related to work load, monotonous and dull nature of work, or due to variable and night shifts. Thus, call centre work may deprive people of their social and family life, and could cause stress spill over from work environment to the family environment.

2.2.2 The life

Initial contextualization of the life domain had been confined to personal life context, only considering family life of the employees and ignoring other aspects of non-work life (Bellavia & Frone, 2005; Keeny et al., 2013). Pichler (2009) also related to this and argued that contextualizing life domain as family only delimits the scope of life domain as there could be much more to the life apart from only family. Thus, a contextualization of life by incorporating domains of family life, social life, leisure life, community life, financial or material life could be more realistic in recent times. Keeny et al. (2013) also recognized that while addressing work-family issues is a major concern of modern times, the debate must incorporate other spares of non-work life to recognize diversity of workers' interests outside of work. Thus, they argued that conceptualization of life domain should be drawn from quality of life literature (Cambell et al., 1976; Felce & Perry, 1995; Wen et al., 2012) and multiple identity perspective (Burke & Stets, 2009; Coulmas, 2019; Thoits, 1983). Considering the evolution of the work-life balance, the focus on the family aspect of life domain arise from initial focus of academicians and practitioners on the challenges faced by parents, particularly

mother, dual career couples with children. Thus, most of initial evidence focused more on the family domain of life, and ignored other aspects, leading Özbilgin et al. (2011) to assert that most of knowledge we have on work-life balance is mostly based on mothers, or the parents at best. In this regard, Keeney et al. (2013) noted that other members of work force, except mothers and parents are ignored in available scholarship and even care given by other members of family like siblings, other relatives, and grandparents. Likewise, care of elderly, ill, and handicapped is also ignored even in the literature relating to family domain. Some studies also have raised concern on ignoring the cohort of workers, having no child care or family related responsibilities (De Janasz et al., 2013; Kelliher et al., 2018; Özbilgin et al., 2011). Considering this debate, it could be argued that most of available enquiring on work-life balance considers some aspect of family domain as sole aspect of the life domain, which could be misleading.

Recent debate on the work life balance has started to accommodate wide variety of on-work life including hobbies, education, cultural responsibilities, social activities, and leisure activities (Casper et al., 2018; Keeney et al., 2013; Kelliher et al., 2018). In this regard, Kelliher et al. (2018) argued that family and related caring responsibilities are essential duties. These duties could be treated like a form of non-paid work, while some life activities could be opted by choice or because such activities are good to have like Wilkin et al. (2016) indicated that adopting and caring for the pet might not be essential or required activity, but it is an optional choice that require time and energy to deal with. In this regard, Veal (2018) chalked out day to day activities of people considering their leisure activities. Part from the work, sleep, and body care activities, other activities highlighted were domestic work and care, community, and leisure activities. The leisure activities were further related to four aspects i.e. recuperation

and rest, family, entertainment, and others. The leisure had always been considered an important aspect of life domain (Veal, 2020), like Small and Riley (1990) deemed this aspect important along with other aspects of life including marriage, home management, and parenting. More recently, Premeaux et al. (2007) noted similar aspects of life domains including leisure activities, home care, elder care, parents, and spouse. Drawing from the quality of life literature, Cummins (2005) noted that there could be about 170 domains of life, where the major domains being the work, leisure, neighborhood and dwelling, friendships, financial resources, social participation, family, and health. Raja and Stein (2014) argued that life domain represents everything else, excluding the work. It should include physical activities and needs like sleep, health, nutrition, and exercise; spiritual and emotional aspects and related activities; social interactions and obligations related to family, relatives, friends, community, and religion; and also daily life activities like paying bills, doing household chores, and laundry. Casper et al. (2018) explained that people may be involved in the domains other than work and family, and such involvement may vary from person to person in accordance with their perceptual importance for that domain. It was also argued that not all the life domains may be important for any particular individual all the time, and importance of different domains may vary in accordance with the evolving interests of the individuals and their experiences or circumstances.

Considering the contact centre industry, employee at the industry are expected to learn not only a particular language but also understand a foreign culture and develop a foreign mind-set (Aneesh, 2012). Hechanova (2013) noted that majority of call centre employees in Asian countries are young graduates, who are quite attached to their family. Further, working in night shift has also consequences for social, family, and health life of call centre workers (Hechanova, 2013; Pico, 2006). Muecke (2005)

explained that variable nature of work routine and working in night shifts causes serious disruptions not only to the family life, but also restrict time for social interactions with family, friends, and relatives. Mirchandani (2004) also explained that call centre workers get detached with their social life, particularly the events that occur during the daytime. Hechanova (2013) also highlighted that most call centres follow work and holiday routine of their host country, rather than their home country. As a result, most employees are unable to attend their family and friends for their home festivities, creating a social divide and feeling of unease. Bakker et al (2003) related to the call centre job as having emotional and physical exhaustion, which again has negative implications for the quality of life (Deery et al., 2002; O'Brady & Doellgast, 2021). Likewise, Zito et al. (2018) also argued that emotional dissonance of call centre employees leads towards negative job and life outcomes. Simons and Buitendach (2013) also related that call centre workers are exposed to higher work pressures, intense workloads, and mental and physical exhaustion. Such environment makes it difficult for the worker to maintain a healthy work and social life.

Overall, it could be noted that most of the previous work has focused on the family aspect of the life domain and ignored other important aspects of social and personal life of workers. Further, more must of the previous work as only considered women and parents with children for work-life balance considerations, while relatively young and single individuals have received little attention. Considering the contact centre industry, most of the workers working in the industry are young and single. Further different and intense nature of call centre work have potential to shape the life of employees differently, who might be sacrificing their personal, family, or social life for their job; or work stress and emotional distress may be spilled over from their work domain to the life domain.

2.2.3 The balance

The notions of balance in work-life balance denotes to the relationship between work and life domains of one's life (Kelliher et al., 2018). There has been a debate in the literature on the possible use of terminology, where some authors prefer to use interface instead of balance (Anderson & Kelliher, 2020; Grawitch et al., 2010; Kelliher, 2016, Le et al., 2020), while other have debated on the notions of conflict or enrichment with regard to the relationship between work and life (Casper et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020; Vieira et al., 2018). It also has been argued that the notions of 'balance' between work and life are confusing (Voydanoff, 2005), have subjective interpretations (Kelliher et al., 2018), and therefore little consensus on its conceptualization exists (Casper et al., 2018). Kalliath and Brough (2008) noted that work-life balance has been contextualized in six ways: first, relating it to multiple roles of working individuals; second, as having equity between these roles; third, as satisfaction between multiple roles; fourth, in terms of fulfilment of role salience between different roles; fifth, as the relationship between role conflicts and facilitation; and last, in terms of perceived control between different roles. It is pertinent to note that historically, work and life domains were perceived to be mutually incompatible, where a sacrifice of one domain was required to meet the demands of the other (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985), and much of the debate focused on the interrelationship of each other, and on the ways to create a balance between these two. In a general and objective manner, the notions on the balance are related to equal distribution of energy, time and commitment to work and non-work roles (Greenhaus et al., 2003). However, such objective approach would be quite rigid to accommodate situation and context specific trade-offs, giving rise to adoption of a situation specific and subjective approach (Kelliher et al., 2018; Reiter, 2007). Thus, work life balance under this

approach is related to subjective perceptions of the individuals as to what extent they are satisfied with work and non-work domains of their life in a given situation or context.

The debate on the balance started after Marks and MacDermid (1996) highlighted the notions of role balance relating to the full engagement in all life roles. During early 2000's, the balance was contextualized as a situation of no work-family conflict or low conflict and high enrichment state (Duxbury & Higgins, 2001; Frone, 2003). These conceptualizations gave rise to the notions of an objective quality between both domains, where work-family balance was seen as equal engagement in or equal satisfaction with both work and family roles (Greenhaus et al., 2003). In this regard, Halpern and Murphy (2013) denoted the work-family balance to a beam, where work and family roles were hanging on each side, and a strict balance was to be maintained between the both to remain afloat. Such strict contextualization was contested by Voydanoff (2005), who proposed to embed environmental contextualization of the concept and argued that balance could be achieved by seeking demand-resource fit, where work and family demands are to be met through the resources available in both domains. This contextualization of work-family or work-life balance adopts a subjective approach, seeking to maintain a balance through the available resources. Subsequently, Valcour (2007) explained it in terms of psychological approach, where work-family balance was actually related to the satisfaction of an individual with both domains. Thus, the balance here was a psychological construct representing level of individual's satisfaction to the extent he or she has met his or her role demands in both domains. Grzywacz and Carlson (2007) related it to the social environment of the individuals by highlighting balance as a relational construct, where role expectations are negotiated and shared between the individual and his or her partners in both work

and family domains. Subsequent conceptualizations of the balance dropped the idea of a perfect equality between work and non-work domain. A more elaborative explanation was provided by Greenhaus and Allen (2011), who argued that balance could be achieved at the point where role effectiveness and role satisfaction, both are consistent with the priorities of life, making it a value driven construct, allowing for person to person and context to context variability in meaning of the balance. A more recent conceptualization of the 'balance' is provided by Casper et al. (2018), who related it to the appraisal of individuals as to how well they are able to combine their work and non-work roles. More specifically, they stated that work-life balance relates to "the extent to which employees hold a favourable evaluation regarding their combination of work and non-work roles, arising from the belief that their emotional experiences, involvement, and effectiveness in work and non-work roles are commensurate (compatible) with the value they attach to the roles" (p. 199). Thus, conceptualization of work-life balance has become more open over the time, where individual's own perceptual assessment in relation to his/her values are considered to relate to his/her work-life balance experience.

Considering the monotonous and stressful work routine of call centres, and difficulty of call centre workers to manage their non-work life, work-life balance has become an important consideration in the industry (Agarwal, 2014). Contact centre industry is characterized by night shifts, excessive monitoring, angry clients, excessive work load, and long working hours (Agarwal, 2014; Kavitha, 2017). Such characteristics of the nature of job make contact centre job a difficult work, whereas maintaining work-life balance in the industry seems difficult. Rao et al. (2007) called for improvement in work-life balance policies of call centres in developing economy context to improve employee retention and satisfaction. Asuncion (2008) noted that married women were

less likely to continue at call centres, due to high demands from both work as well as family domains. Domingo-Cabarrubias (2012) also found that women employees at call centres complained on the conflicts between work and other non-work domains like family, domestic, and social responsibilities. Sharma (2015) noted that employees of call centre complained on the difficult and stressful nature of the job, which caused health and social issues for its employees. It was also noted that the industry provided good compensation and perks to its employees, enabling to the maintain a good lifestyle. Joseph (2015) found that employees at call centre industry experience lower levels of work-life related satisfaction, which induces their turnover intention to become high. The study also noted that work-life related satisfaction was different for different age and gender cohorts, highlighting that the satisfaction or balance could be subjective and context or person specific. Menaria (2016) explained that stressful job at call centres make it very difficult for the employees to deal with family issues. Moreover, demands from the family and personal life could also cause extra pressure on the workers. The study found that business process outsourcing industry exhibit higher levels of work-life issues, which could not be resolved by the workers as such workers have limited time for their personal and family life. Recently, Cabello (2022) have also favoured implementation of work-life balance initiatives in business process outsourcing industry. The study noted that the industry had lower flexibility, particularly with regard to choosing work time or shift; lower educational opportunities to facilitate education of employees; and issues pertaining to payment of overtime and night differentials. Thus, it could be argued that call centre industry has higher work demands, and as potential to distort work-life balance perceptions of the workers, as workers are less likely to bear stress and work overload both from work as well as from non-work domains.

2.3 Work-life balance for working women

Anne-Marie Slaughter ignited controversy when she argued that work–life balance is not possible for women, who cannot “have it all” (Slaughter, 2012). Studies have shown that managing their work and family responsibilities is one of the most crucial challenges faced by female employees (Abdulrahman & Ali, 2016). Female employees trend to prefer flexible time and schedule in between work and families rather than other material work benefits (Eaton 2003). Compared to men, balancing work and life is more difficult for women as the burden of responsibilities is disproportionate (Mazerolle & Barrett, 2018; Bird, 2006). Women have to look after their children and at the same time, fulfil their domestic responsibilities, it often creates a barrier for their career advancement (Sharma & Parmar, 2016; Cross & Linehan, 2006). Balancing both workplace and family is difficult for women since giving time to kids, spouse and office are their expected social behaviour (Semlali, & Hassi, 2016). A study conducted by Goyal (2014) showed that 75% of the female employees reported that they have less time for their children while 44% of had given preferences to household work indicating that the importance of household work cannot be underestimated, even in the case of working women. A study showed that gender disparity and coping up with obstacles like-retention of employment, workplace security especially in rural areas are major challenges faced by female employees (Hossain, et al., 2019).

Apart from the household responsibilities, social stereotypical gender roles also cause provocation of work-life issues; for example, male as breadwinners and female as home makers orientation have made it more difficult for females to manage work and family together (Agarwal, et al., 2015). Female employees in the services sector experience burnout and fatigue due to having high workload (Rich, et al., 2016).

Therefore, they struggle to give sufficient time to their family (Adisa, et al., 2014). Case studies from developing economy of Nigeria depicted that as women have to carry out multiple roles, it often creates difficulty for female employees to have a decent work life balance (Pandey, 2016). Research suggests that women who did not have children show significant higher job commitment compared to women who had children (Mazerolle & Barrett, 2018). According to the study carried out by Pradhan (2016) depicted that while males are able to balance both of their family and work role; for women; there is a trade-off of one role for another. Female doctors face problems when they try to manage their career and life together which eventually, results in poor health, stress, absenteeism, lack of motivation (Goyal, 2014) and depression as well as exhaustion (Welford, 2008). As a consequence, female employees often end up by changing or shifting their career for their family life (AlGhamdi, 2014). It is reported that for the purpose of children's upbringing, female employees give up their career (Arima, 2016). In addition to that, long working hours could engender not only physical but also mental health of female employees which, as a result; causes a decline in the employee performance (Arima, 2016). Due to the long working hours, female employees' satisfaction regarding the work life balance gets reduced (Keeton et al. 2007). Therefore, the attempt of making a balance between their work and personal life at the same time creates an adverse effect on the career path of female doctors (Arima, 2016). The high workload of female doctors leads to stress and also creates conflict between their work and home. Therefore, due to having less flexibility, it adversely impacts their lives, leaving them lethargic and exhausted (McIntosh, et al., 2015). According to Yamazaki et al. (2017), although the number hours spent by females is commensurate with men, the family interference for females is higher than men. However, women having young children faced the highest interference. Prakash

(2018) demonstrated that gender difference exists when it comes to work-family conflict. Higgins et al., (1994) in their study depicted that women experience greater amount of role overload compared to men. Talreja (2017) reported that women experience more work family conflict than men.

Considering the difference in the attitude and role of the women, women experience different type of work life balance issues. As women are expected to behave in a particular manner and also are charged with domestic responsibilities, they are more likely to face work-life issues. This requires that women should be studies separately in order to find related practical implications.

2.4 Work-life balance for working women in developing economies

Last two centuries have witnessed a gradual improvement in the status and economic power of women. This is particularly true for developed countries, and not so true for developing ones (Cohen, 2006). Huis et al. (2017) noted that women are deprived in all major spheres of their life including personal aspect, societal aspect, and relational aspect; where personal aspect is related to the psychological aspect of wellbeing, societal aspect considers social roles and relates expectations from women, and relational aspect is associated with the relationship of women with their family, friends, and networks in the close proximity. Pratto et al. (2011) explained that males are more powerful in their social endeavours, while women are less resourceful, uphold limited social obligations, and are conservative in their cultural orientation. Clark and Clark (2004) highlighted that developing nations have a patriarchal culture, where opportunities and roles of women are limited in their scope. Women assume traditional, household roles, and receive lower support from their family and social networks. For employment as well, they remain confined to lower paying, unstable, and unskilled jobs; limiting their bargaining power to leverage some margin to

maintain work-life balance. This was indicated in the findings of Khan and Majid (2004), who found a reservation wage gap of 22.6% between men and women, indicating that women were willing to opt for a much lower job than men in developing countries. Cohen (2006) also noted that exploitation and abuse of women seems acceptable in developing countries, where they carry an inferior social status. The findings of Clark and Clark (2004) also indicated that the status of women in developing countries was directly related to their quality of life.

Jayachandran (2021) explained that social norms in most developing countries restrict women to go out or work, and confine them to their home. A long-standing norm entrenched in the societies of developing countries is enforcing responsibility of child care and house work on women (Sayer, 2005), even in the case of formal employment outside of home (Bittman et al., 2003). This requires these women to opt for few formal paid working hours, need flexibility in time, and limit their travel distance and time (Jayachandran et al., 2021). The interesting fact in this regard is that in any case women in developing countries are caught between job and family-related responsibilities and work. This leaves them with little self, leisure, and socialization time. A scholarship of research also indicates that facilitating women in child care or household chores leads them to commit more time to their formal paid job (Bharati et al., 2020; Dinkelman, 2011; Martínez & Perticará, 2017; Talamas, 2020). Thus, it could be argued that women in developing countries remain busy in their family-home roles, even if they are formally employed in paid jobs. Even in that scenario, women tend to sacrifice their paid work for unpaid household work. This highlights the dilemma of women in developing countries, who struggle for work-work balance, and may not have the luxury of work-life balance. Thus, the issues of work-life balance for women in the developing country context may originate from the societal norms and social

role of women, who work outside of home in formal paid jobs, and also work inside their homes in unpaid tasks related to caring of children and management of household (Broadbridge, 2008).

Akanji et al. (2020) also argued that division of work and related responsibilities in the developing countries are normatively defined, where women are deemed subjugated to men because of their normative social role of care giver, and men assume a superior role of bread winner for entire household (Abubakar, 2018; Cohen, 2006). Such care giving role responsibility coupled with the formal work requirements causes the women in developing countries to experience work overload and mental strain, rendering a work-life balance issue (Mushfiqur et al., 2018). Likewise, Akanji et al. (2020) explained that dealing with demand of both works, inside and outside home, for longer periods of time leads women doctors in Nigeria to fall prey to stress, where the time squeeze fuels a negative work-home interference. Nwagbara (2020) investigated the role of institutional patriarchy in provoking work life balance issues of female doctors in Nigeria, and found that patriarchal orientation is deep rooted in family and institutional structure of Nigeria, that promotes women exploitation, and intensify work-life issues in the country, which include inflexibility of work routines, excessive workload, and suppression of female participation and voice. Likewise, Adisa et al. (2017) also noted that female doctors in Nigeria are burdened with domestic responsibilities that include caring for children, elderly, and other relatives in the family. They further highlighted work issues like lack of managerial and organizational support, long work shifts, and requirement of physical presence in medical sector of Nigeria. Thus, both work and home domain require a lot of time and effort from female doctors of Nigeria, exacerbating work life balance issues. In this regard, Mushfiqur et al. (2018) noted that work-life balance issues relating to work pressure, lack of support

from relationships, challenging or hostile work environment, work pressure, high socio-cultural demands, and cultural expectations were important aspects of work life balance, leading towards social sustainability of female doctors in Nigeria. Likewise, Subramaniam et al. (2015) conducted a survey of women working in service sector of Malaysia to explain that flexibility in working arrangements was a central premise of work life balance of these women, and it was deemed more important by educated women, earning good salary. Thus, provision of flexible work could enable working women to attain reasonable level of work-life balance.

Many studies have considered work life balance issues of Middle Eastern and Arab countries, where many of these countries have orthodox religious orientation, with special status of women. Abubaker and Bagley (2016) noted that females employed in telecommunication sector of Palestine were given due attention to embed flexibility in their work requirements, and argued that such policies are based on Islamic ideologies, where women are considered a protected segment, both in work and also in family settings. They also argued that Arab culture have cultural values on protection of women, giving them more ease and flexibility in work settings. Lekchiri and Eversole (2021) provided the evidence on work-life balance of Moroccan professional women to indicate that burden of family related responsibilities and excessive work responsibilities make it difficult to achieve a viable work-life balance for working women of Morocco. It was highlighted that despite their job, women were expected to retain full responsibility of the management of household, and full time jobs made it difficult for them to take care of household responsibilities. Most of the respondents indicates that organizations in Morocco do not have formal work life balance support program for women, and only their parents were supporting them to meet the demands of work and family. Same findings are also put forward in context of

other Arab countries like Foster et al. (2013) also indicates that working women in UAE are expected to run the household and care for children. In above to that, these women were deprived of any organizational support to manage their work –life balance issues, making them stressed, demotivates, and less satisfied with their lives. Such women also lose work drive and impede their professional growth and prospects of professional success. Farahat (2009) found that Egyptian female physicians thought that maintaining a balance between work and life was difficult, and they tried to opt for small family, obtaining support from housekeeper or babysitter, and sharing in the family income to manage their household side. Female physicians felt stressed and tend to avoid taking full maternity leaves to ensure career progression and avoid loss of income. Most reported that balancing career and family goals, taking care of children, and managing housekeeping were difficult to handle simultaneously. They also complained about lower support of their husband in this regard. Women in Saudan were also found to sacrifice their career growth to take cate of their children, leading them to remain at lower tyre of managerial position (Kargwell, 2008). Most of these women also used family support to maintain work-life balance, whereas limited support was available from their employers in this regard. Mehdizadeh (2011) provided evidence for Iran to note meagre organizational support for women, caught in family and work responsibilities. It was recommended to improve child care support, leave policies, and flexible work schedules to support women at work. Likewise, Metcalf (2007) also recommended to improve support and maternity related policies of Middle Eastern countries to support women workers. In this regard, Karam et al (2013) explained that working women perceive work-life balance as a web of multiple roles and conflicting responsibilities, where they have to navigate between and across the web to maintain a balance. The authors also argued that the representation of

work-life balance as a complex web was mostly related to the developing countries with collectivist culture, and may not be true for developed countries with individualistic culture. Belwal and Belwal (2017) also provided an interesting evidence, where employers were found satisfied with performance of female workers, but the same workers were facing work-life balance issues. Employers also mentioned that no formal complaint on work life issues was lodged by female employees, and these issues were discussed informally in the organization. As a result, some employers offered flexible and shift work to their female employees. Al-Asfour et al. (2017) studied barriers and challenges to career progression of Saudi working women to note that work life balance was deemed a major issue of the women. These women had strife routine, and excessive workload, raising role conflicts, and burnout. Getting pregnant was deemed a major issue, where women were expected to leave their job after being pregnant. It was also noted that home and family was deemed a primary responsibility by these women, impacting negatively to their career prospects. Likewise, working women in Bahrain were likely to quit their job as a result of higher role conflict and dual responsibilities of work and home (Al-Alwai, 2016). It was also noted that job stress was directly related to the seniority in the organization, whereas limited organizational support was available in Bahrain for women to manage their work-life balance issues. Only Tlaiss and Kauser (2011) provided evidence for Middle Eastern country of Lebanon, highlighting that women managers did not feel work life balance as a viable issues affecting their professional career progression. They explained that domestic help and supportive partner were key factors to support work life balance of these women.

Lewis et al. (2007) and Abubaker and Bagley (2016) argued that the standard western approaches to reduce work hours or flexibility of working policies could be ineffective

in developing country context, as these policies ignore gender roles, gendered nature of work in developing countries, gender related constraints, and other cultural factors that define work settings of female employees. Asian countries like India, Bangladesh, and Philippine also have a particular social structure. Many studies have highlighted work-life issues of female workers in these countries. Lewis et al. (2007) highlighted this issue in relation to modern work trends in India, which are characterized by hard and intense work routines, making workers sacrifice their personal lives. Delina and Raya (2013) also noted that women are deemed inferior segment of Indian society, who stay at home for house chores, work on relatively primal jobs, and face time squeeze due to multiple home related and job related responsibilities. Chawla and Sondhi (2011) tries to explain work life balance of women workers of school education sector and business process outsourcing industries in India to find that job autonomy and organizational commitment explained work life balance of female teachers, while only work overload had a negative impact on work life balance in business process outsourcing segment. Previously, Rajadhyaksha (2012) explained the work life policies of Indian firms that focused on the gender equality, work flexibility, child care, health awareness, and stress reduction. These policies enable women to develop their career alongside men, seek counselling to mitigate stress and improve health, and facilitate child care. Chandra (2012) also noted that work of the husband is prioritized in Asian household, while wife is expected to sacrifice her work for the sake of family and children. Devi and Kiran (2014) provided evidence from the work life balance aspect of women employed in the labour segment of construction industry. They highlighted that although construction sector in India has witnessed some improvements, and some level of automation and mechanical support has been incorporated, labour job is still difficult due to its static nature and physical work

involvement. Further, dust, noise, environmental, and climatic impacts could make this job more difficult and hazardous. They found that women working in labour avoid childbirth as bearing a child results in lower earnings and loss of the job. Further, working long hours and working extra to earn overtime put considerable strain on the health and life of women construction workers in India. With specific reference to the IT sector of India, Mohanty and Jena (2016) explained that excessive work hours and odd timings force women IT professionals to quite the job. Previously, Palanivel and Sinthuja (2012) also noted that work-life balance programs in IT sector of India were not appropriate for women employees, compelling the women to work under sub-optimal situations, or negotiating some out of standard flexibility arrangement with their employer. A need to improve the situation to provide more support to women workers and chalk out standard policies for women employees was recommended by the study. With specific reference to the call centre work, Muñoz et al. (2013) noted societal and cultural discontent for women doing this job. They explained that women doing call centre jobs in India are not considered respectable, and the job involve night shifts and they have to work with young men for long hours, and even at night. This highlights societal pressure that women worker of call centre have to face in conservative countries like India, further working in odd shifts also hinder ability of women to balance their social and home life.

Hossain and Rokis (2014) highlighted the work-care balance context of Bangladesh to note that highlight educated women working in one of the largest university on Bangladesh prioritize their family over work, where work and schedule flexibility enables them to maintain a balance between family roles and work requirements. On the other hand, Uddin et al. (2020) found that women working in banking industry of Bangladesh required instrumental and emotional support of supervisor, work place

and co-worker support, and family support to maintain work life balance, implying that attainment of work life balance could be relatively more challenging for women working in the banking sector of a developing economy. Subsequently, Uddin (2021) related to the challenges of Bangladeshi working women during COVID-19, which not only affected earning ability of women but also induced more work-family pressure on them. It was found that certain work-life balance considerations improved for women like improved flexibility of work routines and working from home, greater spouse support, and some organizational support; while other aspects deteriorated like greater work pressure of work at home and home related chores, non-cooperative of family members, issues relating to joint family system, and increased stress. It is interesting to note that although women are expected to prioritize family over work, and during ordinary time, work pressure may interfere the family domain. However, during COVID-19 excessive work at home in child care and household chores seemed to interfere with the work domain, indicating that women are expected to work at work, and also at home, all the time – with no time for themselves or any leisure and social activities.

In Philippine as well, women are expected to adopt a conservative role, that require them to do family work (Caparas, 2010). Such expectations are deep rooted in the social norms of Philippines society, and women opting to do paid work still need to perform household chores. In this regard, Kim and Ryu (2017) highlighted that female employees required paid sick leaves, health insurance benefits, childcare policy and compensatory time off; and these aspects of work benefits were positively related to the organizational commitment. Work-life issue in the Asian developing countries are generally related to gender issues, connoting to struggle of females to survive and get some space in a male dominated world (Chandra, 2012). In this regard, Lewis and

Beauregard (2018) noted that work life balance could be deemed a luxury in the developing world context, where social norms may also have a more direct influence on the work and life aspects of individuals. It is also interesting to note that work-life balance of women in developing countries is always connoted to work-family balance, where women have to balance work at work and work at home. Majority of studies did not highlight any social or leisure life aspect of women. It could also be noted that role of women in the developing countries are culturally defined, where women are obligated to perform family role of care giver, whereas role of working for paid job is considered something extra. Women are expected to sacrifice their work domain to ensure that all family needs are met, while males assume role of a primary bread winner. Moreover, religious aspect was also dominant in Arab countries, where women are required to observe modesty and remain at home. Thus, work life issues of women in the developing countries should be considered in specific social and cultural contexts, which may be different even for different developing countries.

2.5 Work-life balance for working women in Pakistan

Like the other developing countries, Pakistan also has a patriarchal society with strong culture of male dominance. Nasir et al. (2019) explained that social norms and religion plays an important role to support patriarchal stereotypes in Pakistan. This leads women to remain at home and take up family related responsibilities, while men go to paid work and assume the role of breadwinner for the whole family (Jejeebhoy & Sathar, 2001). Such scarification of work from female side is a prominent aspect of Pakistani society, where female doctors, after completing their medical degree get married and do not pursue a career in medicine (Moazam & Shekhani, 2018). This element of sacrifice is a prominent aspect of working aspect of women in Pakistan, where women have to meet their family related obligations, and may sacrifice paid

work partially or fully to prioritize their caregiving role in the household. Roomi and Harrison (2010) explained that religious and cultural orientation require women to wear veil and restrict her movement outside home, where such situation is more intense in the rural areas of Pakistan, while both men and women work in urban areas of Pakistan. Jalal-ud-Din and Khan (2008) related to socio-economic and cultural constraints of women in rural areas of Pakistan to note that women in rural areas of Pakistan face discriminated treatment from their childhood, and are deprived of their rights and are confined to home to take care of children only. They also noted that women are unable to participate in household decision making, even about their life; and carry a deprived socio-economic status. According to Hakim and Aziz (1998), basic functional unit of society in Pakistan is extended family, which includes male in a dominant position, his wife or wives, his children, his brothers and their wives, his married sons and their wives, his nephews, nieces, and many other relatives. Males are considered superior to females, who are expected to wear veil, and remain separated from males and their work. Naqvi et al. (2002) also found that women have lower employment prospects in Pakistan, where size of the family was inversely related to their decision to opt for a paid job. Apart from the extended family, Khan (2007) restrictions like full body veil or 'purdah', which restrain women to get exposed to men, outside the family. This reinforces their role within the household, or require them to avoid working full time. The requirements of 'Purdah' arise from their societal place, which symbolizes them as 'honor', where being exposed to men or going outside could violate the honor of the family (Irfan, 2009). Such honor symbolization also restricts mobility of women in the society (Mumtaz & Salway, 2005), forcing women to stay private and assume the role of homemaker (Jejeebhoy & Sathar, 2001). Therefore, societal norms pertaining to roles of particular gender group enforce

their ways of functioning, including their travel, work, and meaning in life (Adeel et al., 2014). Thus, it has been argued that sociocultural environment of the country forces women to take up a household role (Adeel & Yeh, 2018) and this family role holds, even if women chooses to be engaged in the paid work, outside their home.

Literature provide evidence that women in Pakistan may leave formal jobs (Noor & Maad, 2008) and start pursuing entrepreneurship in spite of formal jobs, due to a possibility of flexible work and better prospects of having a good work-life balance (Ahmed et al., 2019; Rehman & Roomi, 2012). Samih (2009) interviewed working women of Pakistan to find that women have strong feelings for their household, and feel guilty on missing or avoiding home related work. Working women also through that living in a large or extended family was more difficult compared to living in a small or nuclear family. Likewise, Saulat et al. (2019) found that married working women in Pakistan are more likely to leave their jobs, after becoming mother. They also noted that married women provided facilities such like children day care, work from home occasionally, and also have in-laws support have better work-life balance and also are more productive. On the other hand, Hassan and Azam (2014) explained that many women in Pakistan prefer home based paid work, and women involved in such work are wrongly conceptualized as part time workers. Such women worker face discrimination, unhealthy working conditions, and difficulty to manage work and household responsibility at the same time. Moreover, Waqar et al. (2021) pointed out that working women having same job and experience credentials as men are less likely to pursue promotion and seek more responsibility. Considering the work life balance aspects of formal jobs in Pakistan, Fatima and Sahibzada (2012) noted that female university teachers in Pakistan reported lower work-life balance compared to their male counterparts. They further indicated factors like lower spouse support,

childcare issues, elder care responsibilities, and lower peer support in this connection. Malik et al. (2010) assessed work life balance and its implications for job satisfaction for medical doctors in Pakistan. They found that both male and female doctors in Pakistan had lower work-life balance due to intensive work requiring long duty hours. It was also noted that work life balance was associated with higher job satisfaction and lower turnover intentions among doctors in Pakistan. Noor and Maad (2008) found that work life conflict and stress were significant predictors of turnover intention of women marketing executives in Pakistan. Using a high representation of female employees in the sample, Ahmad et al. (2013) noted that flexibility in the working hours was main aspect of work-life balance, and it also had a apposite relationship with employee motivation. Pervez et al. (2015) provided a detailed description of the problems of working women in Pakistan, where at home sphere, they are unable to manage house, visit and meet relatives, and give time to family; while in work sphere, they face issues pertaining to transportation and travel, and harassment. Naz et al. (2017) also studied work life balance issues of the women academics in Pakistan to highlight that working women find it difficult to maintain a balance between work and family life. They found that women employee complained on lack of support in both work and home spheres of their lives. However, it was noted that women were imparting both their work and family related responsibilities by effective scheduling and obtaining support from other family members. They also highlight that women academics were not able to devote much time for their leisure activities, and activities related to physical and mental wellbeing. Shahin et al. (2021) provided evidence on the impact of personality traits on work-life balance of academics working in Pakistan. They found that personality traits of extraversion, agreeableness, and imagination were significant predictors of work life balance, whereas significant differences were

also noted for work life balance levels of single vs married categories, and living in nuclear vs joint family. Bano and Wajidi (2021) found that stress and employee behavior were significant predictors of work life balance of female teachers in higher education sector of Pakistan. Shaikh et al. (2019) studied that factors relating to the work-life balance of females working in NGO sector of Pakistan and found that personality, employee engagement, and perceived organizational support were significant predictors of work-life balance of females working in NGO sector of Pakistan. Rafique et al. (2018) noted that work-family conflict was a significant predictor of psychological well-being of women employees in Pakistan. Likewise, Murtaza and Khan (2017) found that better work life balance was found to be a significant predictor of job satisfaction of female faculty members of a business school in Pakistan. They also noted that flexibility of working hours, daily workload, and provision of organizational facilities helped female faculty to maintain better work life balance.

Khursheed et al. (2019) considered the case of married female professionals in Pakistan to explain that working hours and spousal support were key factors determining work life balance of female professionals in Pakistan. Their study also noted presence of long working hours, high work demands, lower spousal support, and personal issues in Pakistan, causing work-life issues for married professional women in the country. Likewise, Akram et al. (2008) also studied work life balance of working couples in Pakistan to find that work overload, stress, career progression, and life quality were important predictors of work-life balance for working women of Pakistan. Bashir et al. (2019) narrated experience of working women in one of the largest cities of Pakistan and explained that working women in Pakistan face dual pressure, both from work and home. Women provided that they were facing an

unbalanced life, and are not offered any flexibility in their work schedule. Apart from that, they complained of being harassed, oppressed, and helpless. They also complained on trust issues of their partners. Syed et al. (2019) studied working women of universities of a Pakistani city and argued that women plays multiple roles including being mother, wife, sister, daughter, and also working employee; which makes it difficult for her to maintain a work-life balance. They found that higher workload and lack of paid leaves cause women to face difficulty in managing work-life spheres, and recommended to provide facility of day care for children, relaxation of office timing, and job sharing. Jabeen et al. (2019) studied women in government and health jobs to note that working women in these sectors enjoy good family support and facilitation from their employers, making the work-life balance possible. Recently, Atif and Zubairi (2020) deemed depression and anxiety important predictor of work life balance for women working in banking sector of Pakistan. Kibriya et al. (2021) explained that working women in Pakistan perceived work life balance to relate to management of both work and family related affair, where women used various coping mechanisms to maintain work life balance. These mechanisms include focusing on their trust and faith on God, time and stress management, using support systems, task crafting, and prioritizing work. The study recommended to implement flexible working hours, and provide children day care facility to women employees to better manage their work and family life.

Recently, Fazal et al. (2022) published a systematic review on the work-life balance issues in Pakistan and noted that women in developing countries like Pakistan faced increased pressure of home responsibilities during the pandemic of COVID-19, adding to their work-life balance challenges. In this regard, Kalsoom (2022) noted that work pressure on women teachers amplified during COVID-19 as they had to do extra

wok in both professional and household domains. In work domain, they were required to prepare material and deliver lectures in online mode, requiring learning new set of skills; while in household domain, they had to work extra to care for the whole family, staying at home during pandemic. This lead to work-life imbalance for the female teachers in Pakistan, and the situation was further aggravated for the female teachers, having dependents, children, handicapped, or elder to care for. Likewise, Ali and Ullah (2021) also shared lived experience of academic women in Pakistan during the pandemic and highlighted that women academic remained overwhelmed during COVID-19 due to higher work load and lower support. They tried hard to balance their family and work responsibilities, and remained stressed most of the time. It was noted that they remained occupied with children, family, and online teaching, and could not devote much time for research and academic writing. The situation led them to remain frustrated, exhausted, burned out, and in desperate need of leisure and personal time. Sahbaz et al. (2021) also explored emotional, psychosocial, and professional challenges faced by women working in health care segment during COVID-19 in Pakistan. They noted that female working in health care faced excessive workload during the pandemic, and they remained under fear of safety of their family and their own self. They felt lonely during quarantine and were emotionally depressed. On professional side, they battled with the uncertainty and changing treatments and procedures, and provided excessive counselling to patients and their family, making their job more time consuming and difficult. Females particularly faced challenges related to transportation, management of house chores, children care, home schooling, and other related tasks. It was noted that female health workers faced greater challenges both at home and at work during the time of pandemic.

It could be noted that women face work-life issues in Pakistan, like any other developing economy with male dominant culture. It is also interesting to note that most evidence in Pakistan comes from education or health sector, the two sector that are preferred for female employment due to their perceived suitability for the female employment. Fazal et al. (2022) also indicated that women in Pakistan chose teaching or medical profession due to social norms that deem these professions fit for women. Further, these professions also require lower work time commitment in many cases, enabling females to perform household chores. Limited evidence is available on other segments of industry in this regard, although few studies are also available on banking and other services sectors. Moreover, here as well work-life balance is considered as a juggle between work and family related responsibilities, giving lower attention to other spares of women lives like leisure, self, fitness, and like.

Chapter 3

Theoretical Framework

Chapter 3 of the dissertation provides a description of the available theories that seek to explain interaction of work and life domains of workers. The theories described in this chapter provide a holistic and context free discussion on the work life balance of workers. This chapter also relates to the theoretical explanations. On the work-life balance of women, particularly with reference to those living and working in a conservative patriarchic society.

3.1 Introduction

The debate on the work-life balance has its roots in the industrial revolution and related developments, where workers of 18th century campaigned against the practice of long working hours (Khateeb, 2021). Most of the early notions on the work life balance remained confined to the reduction and standardization of working hours (Sullivan, 2014). The domain of work-life balance flourished after 1960's, where women started to enter in formal workforce and various studies were conducted to understand work-life issues of dual earner families and working mothers (Lewis et al., 2007). Notable contributions in theocritical development of work-life domain started after Rapoport and Rapoport (1976) developed segmentation model, arguing no relationship between work and life domain of workers. Subsequently, Staines (1980) explained the notions on the work-family interactions through compensation theory, highlighting the tendency of individual to compensate the deficit of one domain by investing more resources in the other. In the meantime, Greenhouse and Beutell

(1985) proposed their conflict theory, highlighting a conflict between work and life domains. Another perspective was highlighted by Pleck (1995), who argued that issues of work domain could spill over to the life domain, and vice versa. In subsequent year, Nippert-Eng (1996) explained work-life balance with the lens of a boundary theory. All of these theories explain the work-life balance aspects from a western perspective (Le et al., 2020). This study uses a phenomenological research design to explore the work-life balance reality of women working in contact center industry of Pakistan. This chapter reviews the some important theories in this regard, whereas these theories would be used to relate to the work-life balance phenomenon for women in the contact center industry of Pakistan.

3.2 Early theoretical models – Segmentation and compensation

The segmentation theory of work-life balance suggests that individuals should keep their work life and personal life completely separate from each other in order to achieve a balance between the two. According to this theory, work and personal life are two distinct spheres, and individuals should not allow the demands and stresses of one to spill over into the other (Edwards & Rothband, 2000; Staines, 1980). Thus, the both work and life domains are deemed separable from each other and individuals are able to live both in a distant manner with no interrelation between the both (Guest, 2002). The theory was criticized for its impracticability, as it was found that both work and family domains were closely related to each other (Bello & Tanko, 2020; Bruke & Greenglass, 1987). Further, it has also been argued that recent developments in information and communication technology have blurred the distinction line between work and life domains (Cousins & Robey, 2015; Nam, 2014).

Subsequently, compensation theory of work life balance suggests that individuals may experience imbalance in their work and personal lives, but they may compensate for

this by seeking out positive experiences in other areas of their lives (Edwards & Rothbard, 2000). This theory acknowledges that individuals have multiple roles in their lives, such as being an employee, a parent, a spouse, a friend, and a community member, and that they may experience conflict between these roles. In this regard, Edward and Rothbard (2000) identified two forms of compensation. First is supplemental compensation where the subject does not receive a reward in one domain and tries to compensate this by seeking a supplementary reward in other domain. Example include the situation when some individual does not receive praise from people in the work domain, and compensates it by seeking praise from people in the personal life (Prdhan, 2016). Second is reactive compensation, where the subject tries to compensate negative experiences of one domain through seeking positive experience in the other domain (Edward & Rothbard, 2000). Example include a mother seeking a happy and quality time with her children after a bad workday (Pardhan, 2016). Overall, the compensation theory of work-life balance suggests that individuals strive to balance the demands of their multiple roles, and they may compensate for imbalance in one area of their life by seeking out positive experiences in other areas. Despite its usability, one should be wary of possibility of overcompensating and related issues like burnout at work or social problems in personal sphere of life (Trzebiatowski & Triana, 2020).

3.3 Enrichment and facilitation theories

Unlike segmentation model, both enrichment and facilitation models do not consider work and life as distant domains. In this regard, enrichment theory of work-life balance suggests that work and personal life are not separate domains, but rather can enhance and enrich each other (Pardhan, 2016). The theory is opposite to the notions of the conflict in work and life domains and argued that experiences and skills

acquired in one domain could improve quality of life in the other domain (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006). Pardhan (2016) explained that enrichment theory focuses on the acquisition of skills or resources, which are beneficial for the subjects, who might be experiencing a challenging life. Thus, resources and skills acquired in one domain of life could enrich the other. Greenhaus and Powell (2006) highlighted two pathways in relation to the enrichment. Affective path enables the subject to transfer positive emotions and behavior between work and family, whereas instrumental path enables the subject to use skills and behaviors obtained in one domain to improve the outcomes in the other domain. Overall, this theory argues that experiences obtained from domain like skills, abilities, and values i.e. instrumental sources; or moods and satisfaction i.e. affective sources have ability to enrich the experience of other domain (Morris & Madsen, 2005).

Another related theory arguing no distinction between work and life domain is facilitation theory, which argues that work and personal life are not separate entities, but rather interconnected parts of a person's overall life experience. The theory explains that resources, skills, and roles in one domain facilitate management of the roles in the other domain (Khateeb, 2021). Wayne et al. (2004) deemed facilitation as a form of synergy, where resources such like skills, abilities, and values from one domain make it easier to perform roles in the other domain. It is different from the enrichment experience, where experiences from domain improve quality of experience in the other domain, whereas in facilitation context, experiences in one domain help or facilitate the role execution in the other domain (Pardhan, 2016). Wayne et al. (2007) explained that facilitation has three components i.e. engagement, gains, and enhanced functioning; where engagement refers to the degree an individual invests in the relative domain; gain could be developmental – related to

skills and knowledge acquisition; affective – behaviors or moods, capital – related to money, social status, or health; and efficiency related. Lastly, enhanced functioning refers to improvement in role execution and performance in one domain.

Overall, both of the theories explain a spillover of positive aspects of one domain on the other and highlight the ability of the subjects to manage their work-life balance at their personal and professional roles by means of enrichment or facilitation.

3.4 Spillover and crossover theory

The spillover theory of work-life balance suggests that the experiences, emotions, and behaviors of an individual in one domain of life can influence and spill over into other domains of life. Zedeck (1992) explained that most of the work done in last two decades of previous century has focused on spillover, which could be positive or negative (Guest, 2002). Edwards and Rothbard (2000) explained spillover as a process through which work and family domains could affect each other, generating similarities between both domains. The spillover could be both instrumental or affective, where instrumental spillover relates to the spillover of skills and behavior, while affective spillover relates to the spill over of moods or attitudes from one domain to another (Edward & Rothbard, 2000; Ilies et al., 2009). Pardhan (2016) argued that spillover could take place in both directions, from work to life domain, and vice versa. Greenhaus and Powell (2006) explained that positive spillover is also denoted to as the enrichment theory. Xu (2009) also argued that feelings of accomplishment and contempt in one domain of life could generate a likewise feeling in the other domain. Bello and Tanko (2020) explained that both work and family domains are considered an integrated entity in the spillover theory, where happenings at work have a tendency to influence the happenings at home, and vice versa (Young & Kleiner, 1992). Thus, subjects have a tendency to transfer behaviors, attitudes, moods, emotions, and skills

from the work settings to the home settings (Kelly & Voydanoff, 1985). There is ample research on the spillover theory, but theory is specified in a generic manner and have little value in practical settings (Guest, 2002). Therefore, more detailed study on the causes and consequences of the spillover could be more revealing and useful.

A related concept of cross-over could also be traced in the literature. Westman (2001) defined crossover in terms of job stress being transmitted from a subject to his/her partners. Thus, job stress or related feelings could be transmitted from work domain to the life domain and vice versa, and such feelings could influence the people, with whom subject have a regular interaction. Subsequently, Westman et al. (2009) explained that crossover is a bi-directional transmission of both negative and positive dispositions, moods, and emotions from the subject to the connected people such like work team members, spouse, or family members. Pardhan (2016) explained three aspects, through which crossover could happen. First is the empathetic reaction of the partner on the stressful feelings of the subject, contributing to the stress level of the partner as well (Westman, 2001). The second aspect is decline in leisure time of the subject, which could affect social and personal relations of the subject by promoting a negative feeling about the subject and contributing to the stress and anxiety levels of the partners (Demerouti et al., 2005). The last aspect happens due to the social undermining process, where stress and time pressure of lead the subject to engage in negative behaviors such like anger or criticism towards the partners, thereby contributing to the dissatisfaction and stress of the partners (Bakker et al., 2018).

Overall, spillover is related to personal satisfaction or dissatisfaction of the subject, where positive or negative aspects of one domain may spillover to the other domain; whereas crossover is related to the satisfaction or dissatisfaction of partners of the subjects, where positive or negative experiences of the subject in one domain could

crossover to the partner(s) of the subject in the other domain. Considering the telework as in call center, Zhang et al. (2020) explained that such work have a higher probability of positive and negative spillover, compared to conventional office work jobs.

3.5 Boundary and border theory

The boundary theory of work-life balance suggests that there is a clear distinction between work and non-work domains, and that individuals need to establish and maintain boundaries between these domains in order to achieve balance and avoid conflicts (Pardhan, 2016). Boundary theory segregates blocks of time and space in a simple form, where these blocks could be attributed to the different roles of the subject and his/her life environment (Zerubavel, 1993). The theory highlights the manner through which subjects create, maintain, and alter boundaries to classify the world, in which they operate (Ashforth et al., 2000). The theory was designed within the sociological paradigm, and notes the manner by which subjects assign meaning to their life spheres and relative ease of transfer from one sphere to another (Nippert-Eng, 1996). In this regard, Allen et al. (2014) noted that there boundaries between work and non-work domains could be behavioral, physical, and psychological, where these boundaries make work and non-work domains distant from each other. Thus, in order to maintain a balance, individuals must effectively manage the boundaries between these roles and domains, so that they can meet the demands of each without causing conflicts or stress.

Clark (2000) extended the theory and provided a border theory in this regard. The theory explains that people negotiate and manage work and non-work domains to ensure minimal level of conflict. The theory identifies work and non-work domains as distant domains, but also acknowledge that both domains have ability to affect each

other (Khateeb, 2021). The theory considers the relationship between both domains on a continuum ranging from integration to segmentation in a way that on the side of integration both domains are interlinked, but mutually exclusive on the side of segmentation (Voydanoff, 2005). In this regard, the theory explains varying nature of borders between work and non-work domains i.e. physical, temporal, and psychological borders (Clark, 2000). Physical border relate to the actual space when work and non-work roles are performed. Such locations may be workplace or office versus home, or some designated area in home where they perform work roles (Pardhan, 2016). On the other hand, temporal border relates to the time distribution between work activities and personal activities (Clark, 2000). These are time based boundaries, where the subject could designate a time based boundary of suppose 6:00 in the evening to pick up their children from day care (Pardhan, 2016). Third and last psychological border represent perceptual boundary of subject in relation to the activities associated with work and non-work related roles (Ashforth et al, 2000). Pardhan (2016) exemplified it highlighting a situation where work related meeting in the evening could be perceived as a socialization activity with work friends.

Overall, both boundary and border theories argue that individual could maintain a better work-life balance if both work and non-work domains are managed separately, and individual could easily make transition from one role to the other, even if both work and non-work roles are integrated (Ashforth et al, 2000; Desrochers & Sargent, 2004). In this regard, permeability and flexibility are two important considerations defining role boundary (Zhang et al., 2020). Permeability reference to the ability of elements representing one domain to stem into other, whereas flexibility represents malleability of the borders between work and non-work domains (Saarenpaa, 2016). In this regard, Clark (2000) noted that boundaries characterized by inflexibility and

impermeable could be deemed as strong, while flexible and blended boundaries are weak allowing border crossing. Khateeb (2021) noted that people are generally border crossers, who like to negotiate and manage work and non-work roles with flexibility and permeability.

3.6 Conflict theory

Conflict theory posits a situation of role conflict between and work and non-work domains of life of individuals. Pardhan (2016) related the work life conflict to a situation where demands of work domain obstruct or create problems in meeting the demands of non-work roles. Khateeb (2020) deemed the conflict to be a fundamental aspect of work-family continuum. Zhang et al. (2020) explained that people are expected to discharge multiple role responsibilities in their daily routine. An individual could be indulged in the roles of an employee in the work domain, and a parent or spouse in the family domain simultaneously. Both of these roles require time and energy commitments, where an optimal distribution of these time and energy resources become difficult, giving rise to a role conflict. Different roles could require different time and energy commitments, making these roles incompatible with each other, creating a situation of inter-role conflict (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985; Sirgy & Lee, 2016). Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) explained that work-life role conflict could emerge in three ways. First is time based conflict, where time allocation between work and life roles becomes difficult and it becomes difficult for the subject to meaningfully engaged with on domain due to lower allocation of time to that domain. For example completing a presentation for work and participating in a family gathering in the same evening becomes difficult (Pardhan, 2016). Second is strain based conflict, where psychological or physical issues like stress, fatigue, anxiety, etc. created in one domain spillover to the other domain and restrict the ability of the subject to

meaningfully engage in that domain (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). For example, an individual could be less engaged in the family domain due to an upcoming important official meeting in the work domain (Pardhan, 2016). Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) argued that both time and strain based conflicts share a number of sources, despite being conceptually different. Lastly, behavior based conflict arises when behavior or skill learnt in one domain of life may be appropriate in that domain, but inappropriate for the other domain. For example, emotional sensitivity or expressiveness could be appropriate behaviors in the family domain, and may not be desirable in the work domain. Likewise, assertive behavior or work style may be indicative of success in the work environment, but could raise tensions, if deployed at home (Pardhan, 2016). Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) also explained that the amount of time dedicated to the work or job roles is one of the major issue contributing to the work-life conflict.

Apart from the aspects of the conflict, Gutek et al. (1991) highlighted direction of the conflict. First, work to family conflict, where work responsibilities make it difficult for the individuals to meaningfully engage in the family domain. Second, family to work conflict, where family issues make it difficult for the subject to exhibit good performance in the work domain. Pardhan (2016) indicated that mental and physical health related issues like hypertension, depression, and physical health issues stem from work to family conflict; whereas enhanced alcohol consumption could be motivated by family to work conflict. Such family to work direction of conflict could also result in negative work outcomes, attitudes, and performance (Kossek & Ozeki, 1999). Finally, irrespective of the direction of the conflict, work-family conflict causes negative work related outcomes like lower satisfaction and commitment, and higher absenteeism and turnover intention; and also adverse family related outcomes including poor family satisfaction and lower marital quality (Matthews et al., 1996).

Overall, contact center work is characterized by high time commitments and incompatible role demands, giving rise to role conflicts (Zhang et al., 2020).

Chapter 4

Research Methodology

The objective of this research is to understand dynamics of work-life balance of female employees of contact centre industry in Pakistan. This chapter outlines and justify the action plan to meet this objective. Research methodology represents a well thought out and organized plan, that guide the research process to ensure that inferences drawn from the research are relevant, reliable, valid, and generalizable to the extent of the scope of the study. Saunders et al. (2009) provided a research onion of research methodology, where each layer of the onion relates to an important aspect of research methodology. Following that sequence, this chapter starts with the research philosophy, which leads towards research approach, research strategy, time horizon, and data collection. This chapter also explains and justify choice of the data collection method, selection of respondents, and sampling procedures. The concerns relating the validity, reliability, reflexivity, and ethics are also addressed in this chapter. Lastly, it also explains the procedure of organization of data and analysis to draw inferences.

Creswell and Creswell (2017) explained that research approach must be relevant to nature of the research problem and context of the study. This study is conducted in contact centre industry of Pakistan, where existing on the work-life balance perceptions of women is scant. Existing scholarship only relates to the work environment of the contact centres and is devoid of the women experience with the environment. Further, Pakistani society is characterized with high patriarchal orientation, where females are expected to take care of all the household, even if they

are doing outside paid work. This makes work-life balance a more sparking issue for working women in Pakistan. Further, high work pressure, target oriented work, and cultural restrains related to disapproval of women to work in contact centre make it more relevant to study 'lived experience' of women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. Scant evidence and considerations of understanding lived experience of women working in the contact centre industry require collection of detailed qualitative data. Prior to discussion on the elements of research methodology, it would be beneficial to provide a description of the research settings.

4.1 Research Settings

Contact center industry has recently evolved in the country (Ahmed, 2022) and the industry is confined to the larger cities of Pakistan i.e. Islamabad, Karachi, and Lahore. Islamabad, being the capital city of Pakistan houses head offices of all information and communication technology firms. These firms also operate inbound call centres in Islamabad. Focus of Government of Pakistan is also increasing on the industry, and scope of IT enabled services and IT sector has recently been extended to include contact centre industry (Sarfraz, 2022). Islamabad and other large cities in Pakistan also have a higher women participation in formal workforce. Initiatives to promote and support women workforce are also more prominent in large cities like Islamabad (The News, 2022). All of this makes Islamabad a suitable city to locate suitable respondents to collect data from female contact centre employees for their 'lived experience' on work-life balance issues. The initial plan was to fly to Islamabad to collect data, but due to COVID-19 and related travel restrictions, I had to collect data through telephone interviews.

Islamabad is capital city of Pakistan with a population of 200 million people (Virk, 2022). Most of the population of the city is of working age (15-64 years) and the city

has the highest literacy rate (88%) in whole of the Pakistan (PBS, 2017). The city also has the highest Human Development Index (HDI = 0.875) in Pakistan (UNDP, 2017), and also is the costliest city in Pakistan (ET, 2011). The city has twenty universities, with a higher percentage of female students. The trend of female employment in the city is also higher compared to the other cities of Pakistan. Considering these credentials, Islamabad was deemed a suitable city with relatively higher trend of female education and employment.

4.2 Research Philosophy

Creswell and Creswell (2017) explained that philosophical orientation of the research is not explicitly described in research process and there is a need to relate philosophical assumptions to the research process as these assumptions have considerable influence on the research process. Research philosophy provides basic set of beliefs that guide the action of researcher throughout the research process (Guba, 1990), and shapes the world view that is employed in a research (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). Ontology, epistemology, and axiology provide foundation to the research philosophy; where ontology relates to the description of the nature of reality, highlighting the assumptions that we make to understand world around us (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; O'Gorman & MacIntosh, 2015). Ontology is considered a starting point of each research, which is followed by the epistemological stance, and then methodological choices (Grix, 2002). Ontology describes the nature of reality as being 'objective' or 'constructive'; the former equating social entities with objective entities with no influence of social actors, their actions, and perceptions; and later deeming social entities as construction of actions and perceptions of social actors (Bryman, 2016). Thus, under constructive paradigm, reality is presumed to be formed with interplay or social actors, their actions, and perception (Saunders et al., 2009), where

reality formation is an evolving process, subject to revision on accord of action and perceptions of social actors. Remenyi et al. (1998) explained the need to study the phenomenon in detail to understand the underlying reality and mechanism forming the reality. In this regard, a constructive ontological stance accepts that reality or knowledge are dependent on practices and perceptions of social actors, where such practices and perceptions are a functions of interaction of social actors with their social context and environment (Burnard et al., 2008). This research requires a thorough understanding of the perceptions and feelings of female employees of contact centre industry for their work-life balance, where such perceptions and feelings may be influenced by the social context or environmental factors. Therefore, a constructivist stance is deemed appropriate for this study as the meaning of work-life balance for women working in contact centre industry would be constructed by interplay of social and environmental factors. The focus of the research would be on subjective opinion of female employees of the contact centre industry to understand their version of reality on work-life balance.

Epistemology follows ontological stance. Epistemology is described as theory of knowledge (Grix, 2002), as it constitutes the methods, and ways of obtaining and validation of knowledge. Bryman (2016) argued that epistemological choices relate to question as to whether social phenomenon could be studied through ethos, methods, and procedures used in natural sciences or not. Epistemology is used to determine the knowledge that is acceptable in a particular knowledge domain (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Saunders et al., 2009). Objective ontological stance leads towards positivist epistemological choices, which rely more on scientific methods of enquiry to ensure that research process remains independent of the social actors and is free from perceptive biases (Saunders et al., 2009). Positivists consider social variables as

scientific variables to ensure objectivity in data collection and analysis, where opinion and perceptions of social actors and researcher are not given importance. On the other hand, constructive ontological stance leads towards interpretivist epistemological choices. Interpretivists argue that social variables are not scientific variables, and exhibit unsystematic and unpredictable patterns. This requires a high degree of involvement of researcher and interaction with the social actors. Bryman and Bell (2007) argued that social realities could only be understood by study their contextual underpinning in real life settings. This is particularly useful in scenarios, where there is limited background information or evidence in the literature. Thus, a constructivist employs an interactive and personalized method of data collection and analysis. This study aims at exploring perceptions and feelings of women employees at contact centre industry in Pakistan, where perceptions and feelings of the respondents cannot be treated as the scientific variable. The phenomenon under study is complex as it has contextual and environmental ramifications. Mertens (2019) argued regarding social variables as scientific variables would reduce complexity and richness of the phenomenon, whereas interpretivist epistemological choices could lead to provide a rich insight into a complex phenomenon. In this regard, Creswell and Creswell (2017) explained that social constructivists seek to understand the world around them, where individuals assign subjective meanings to their interactions and experiences with the world. These meanings are unique, subjective, and varied; providing researcher a rich description of the social phenomenon. Collection and analysis of such data requires the researcher to remain involved with the respondents and with the data collected. Researcher require detailed a rich description of feelings and perceptions of the respondents, leading him to choose qualitative study. Following these lines of reasoning, this research opts constructivist epistemological

choice of interpretivism, where a qualitative study would suit the purpose of the research.

Subsequently, axiology represents the values and ethical perspective of the research (Merten, 2014). Researchers studying social phenomenon with the lens of constructive paradigm need to be more careful in their research endeavours as these researchers are dealing with human beings as social actors, and not objects like in scientific enquiry. In this regard, Guba and Lincoln (2001) provided an ethical framework for constructivists highlighting the aspects of credibility to ensure accuracy of inferences, transferability to embed details to facilitate applicability of research to other contexts, dependability to highlight the process of emergence of concepts and understanding, confirmability to support conclusion with empirical data, and authenticity to express a fair and balanced view. The framework was further extended to include elements of reciprocity, rapport, and reflexivity (Trainor & Graue, 2013). Heron (1996) argued that individual values guide human actions, and values could influence the way in which a research is conducted, which in turn could affect credibility of a research. determines the credibility of your findings. Therefore, researcher should consider personal values and be able to articulate how these values might influence the research process (Saunders et al., 2009). For the purpose of this research, I have tried to mitigate negative influence of my values. I tried to enlist my values and biases that could have any impact on the data collection and analysis. I kept a written list of the possible values and biases to remain cautious of any negative influence on the values.

4.3 Research approach

Research approach describe the extent or scope of a research. The choice of the research approach is largely related to whether one has a clear theoretical premise at

the beginning of the research or not (Saunders et al., 2009). There are two research approaches to choose from: Deductive approach and inductive approach (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). First is deductive approach, which is used to test a theory. Under this approach, we have a clear theoretical premise to test. Data is collected through a standardized and structured instrument, from a larger sample to generalize the findings of the study whole population (Saunders et al., 2009). This approach is more objective and is quite suitable for scientific research design.

The other available approach is inductive research approach. This approach is used to explore the phenomenon, where little is known about the phenomenon. This approach provides more flexibility and allows collection to rich data from a small sample to understand a phenomenon. The approach allows integration of cultural, social, and environmental aspects in research process. Induction requires collection of qualitative data through an open format. The approach is used to develop theories or improve understanding on a phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2009).

Considering scant evidence on work-life balance of female employees in contact centre industry of Pakistan, and relevance of contextual and environmental factors; this study requires collection of qualitative rich data from the respondents. This implies that inductive approach will suit the purpose of the study, which is to understand perceptions and actions of working women in contact centre industry of Pakistan. Although findings of the study might not be generalizable, but would provide a detailed understanding of the phenomenon being studied.

4.4 Research strategy

Research strategy relates to the practical aspect of the research framework, which guides researcher on his quest to collect and analyse the data. Saunders et al. (2009) pointed out that no research strategy is superior or inferior to others, whereas certain

strategies may be more suited to inductive or deductive research approach. In this regard, Creswell and Creswell (2017) provided a simplistic approach to segregate research designs into quantitative, qualitative, and mixed method research designs; where quantitative research design could use experimental or non-experimental like survey research strategies; qualitative research design could choose from narrative research, phenomenology, ethnography, case study, and grounded theory; while mixed method design could use any of two or more strategies in accordance with the purpose of research. Research onion taxonomy of Saunders et al. (2009) also related to different research strategies including experiments, surveys, case study, grounded theory, ethnography, and grounded theory. This taxonomy of research is sequenced in accordance with the objective to subjective orientation of the research philosophy, where experiments are the most objective research strategy, resulting in a broader generalizability of the results; while archival research falls into the subjective domain, having least prospects of generalizability.

In order to explore into the feelings, experiences, and perceptions of the female employees working in the contact centre industry; I chose inductive approach, leading me towards qualitative research designs. Qualitative research strategies yield qualitative data that is rich in its description and could be used to tap into underlying feelings, experiences, and perceptions of individuals. Qualitative data is suitable for exploratory settings, where little is known about the phenomenon (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Saunders et al. (2009) also argued that social phenomenon could not be expressed and understood in numbers, deeming qualitative data more appropriate for studies trying to uncover social realities. In this regard, Blaxter et al. (2006) argued that qualitative data is not in line with social and behavioural tendencies of humankind, making qualitative data collection a valid choice for social scientists and behaviourists.

Although, there are generalizability issues with relying on qualitative data, collected from the few cases, a thoughtful process could enable the researchers to prevent from the representation bias.

Considering the objective of the study i.e. to tap into work-life balance experience of women working on contact industry of Pakistan, I opted to pursue a phenomenological research strategy. Moran (2002) described phenomenon as conscious experience of individuals relating to their social interaction to form their version of reality. In this context, Creswell and Creswell (2017) described phenomenology as an inquiry rooted on philosophy and psychology that aims at understanding 'lived experience' of a target group about a phenomenon, where such experience is described by the respondents from that target group. Spiegelberg (2012) noted that phenomenology has varied traditions and the practice may change from one phenomenologist to the other. However, most phenomenological designs could be categorized into descriptive or transcendental tradition of Edmund Husserl and interpretive or hermeneutic tradition of Martin Heidegger (Cohen & Omery, 1994). Husserl is considered father of the phenomenological tradition, who defined phenomenology as 'descriptive philosophy of essences of pure experiences' (Van Manen, 2016). Thus, the objective of Husserl's phenomenological design is to just describe the phenomenon as it is, without any preconception, further explanation, or formulation of any hypothesis (Husserl, 1970). Therefore, it is expected from researcher to shed all forms of prior knowledge, preconceptions, and experiences about the phenomenon being studied (Lopez & Willis, 2004). This ensures that no preconception or bias of the researcher creeps into the description of reality being experienced by the target group (Natanson, 1973). This relates to the Husserlian notions of transcendental subjectivity, where possible bias arising from researcher's preconceptions is

assessed constantly to neutralize embeddedness of pre-conceptions with social reality being experienced by the target group (Lopz & Wills, 2004). Moustakas (1994) proposed elements of epoché, bracketing, and reduction to neutralize preconception bias; where epoché requires the researcher to undergo a self-reflection process to note any preconceptions, biases, or knowledge on the phenomenon being studied. Such knowledge or preconception may arise from the personal experience of the researcher or from the literature reviewed. Bracketing relates to the deliberate attempt of researcher to put aside all presumptions to prevent these from mingling with the data collected (Van Manen, 2014). Moustakas (1994) explained that it might be difficult for researcher to practice epoché and bracketing in absolute form; however, continuous reflection, attention, and self-dialogue could mitigate the influence of preconceived thoughts on the research outcomes. Lastly, reduction relates to examination of participants' self-described experiences in a systematic manner to reduce self-conceptions and rely on the empirical data in the analysis phase. This helps in unveiling the true essence of the phenomenon being studied.

The second tradition of phenomenology was proposed by Heidegger, who was a student of Husserl. Interpretive or hermeneutic phenomenology is constructivist in its ontological orientation. Heidegger proposed that our understanding of the world is shaped by the way we interpret the reality, and it would be meaningful to bring an interpretive lens to the phenomenon being studied (Heidegger, 1962). Heidegger argued that phenomenology is bound to context under which it is being studied and rejected bracketing on grounds that object cannot be separated from subject's interpretation of the phenomenon (Groenewald, 2004). Thus, Heidegger's version of phenomenology relies on the interaction of interpretation derived by the researcher from the phenomenon being explained by the respondents, where both researcher

and participant may have a shared language, culture, experience, and context (Wojnar & Swanson, 2007). In this regard, Spiegelberg (1976) related that hermeneutics is useful to bring out hidden manifestation of the phenomenon that might be hidden in ordinary description of one's experiences. Therefore, it is important to go beyond the simple description of phenomenon to look it into a more interpretative paradigm to realize underlying meanings embedded in the real life practices. These underlying meanings are normally not apparent in the description of practices and experiences of the individuals, but could be unveiled through hermeneutic inquiry, which focuses on the essence of human experiences and not on the mere description of their conscious knowledge (Solomon, 1987). Thus, the main feature of Heidegger's (1962) phenomenology is that the relation of the individual to his lifeworld should be the focus of phenomenological inquiry. He used the term 'lifeworld' to express the idea that individuals' realities are invariably influenced by the world in which they live (Lopez & Wills, 2004). Another term being-in-the-world was also used by Heidegger to emphasize that human cannot abstract themselves from the world; therefore, it is not the pure content of human subjectivity that is the focus of a hermeneutic inquiry but rather, what the individual's narratives imply about what he or she experiences every day. Another important feature of interpretive phenomenology is the situated freedom, which means individuals' subjective experiences are inextricably linked with social, cultural, and political contexts. Interpretive phenomenology further assumes that preconceptions on the part of the researcher are valuable guides to inquiry and in fact, make the inquiry a meaningful undertaking (Lopez & Wills, 2004).

Interpretive from phenomenology seems more suitable to the study as social context of the country is important to relate to the 'lived experience' of women working in the

contact centre industry in Pakistan. Work and life aspects of women have cultural and societal contextualisation, and this is more relevant to the Pakistani settings where women are expected to manage household, and working women also have to perform household chores and care for elderly and children. In this context, respondents may not be articulating the extent of their work and home related responsibility, and it is responsibility of the researcher to lend an interpretive lens to unveil true meanings of the phenomenon under study. Despite utilization of interpretive phenomenology, I have tried to confirm to the notions of epoché and reduction, where the interpretive lens follows the empirical data to enrich the discussion and not the other way around. The continuously self-reflected and evaluated my beliefs and pre-conceptions during data collection and analysis phase to ensure that my beliefs and pre-conceptions are not guiding the process. I used literature review to provide more details to the description of reality and refrained from using my own experiences or knowledge of the phenomenon. This helped me to mitigate my influence on the research outcomes.

4.5 Sampling

Collection data from the whole population is not practical in the social science research, which leads to selection of sample to collect the data from (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Sample is a representative portion of the population, from which data is actually collected to make inferences. Saunders et al. (2009) explained that there are two main sampling procedures i.e. probability sampling and non-probability sampling. Probability sampling follows a systematic protocol to select a representative sample, and is mostly utilized in quantitative research designs (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). On the other hand, non-probability procedures are widely adopted in the qualitative research settings, where focus remains on the selection of 'information rich' respondents, who could provide detailed information and also are willing to participate

in the study. Within non-probability sampling procedures, I employed purposeful sampling protocol. Considering phenomenological research design, which focuses on the unveiling 'lived experience' of the target group i.e. women working in contact centre industry of Pakistan, it is important that selected respondents have personal experience of everyday phenomenon being studied (Moustakas, 1994). Therefore, selection of 'information rich' respondent was a priority in the research, and purposive sampling procedure could be used to select suitable respondents who meet the criterion of being 'information rich' (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). In this regard, Polkinghorne (2005) explained that purposive sampling is suitable for the qualitative research design as it allows the researcher to choose most suitable candidates, having rich experience of phenomenon being studied. Selection of such information rich candidates enables the researcher to obtain a relevant and detailed insight into feelings and experiences of the subjects being studied. Purposive sampling is useful in qualitative settings, but it relies on the judgmental bias of the researcher as to who meets his/her definition of 'information rich'. Further, purposive sampling procedure results in collection of detailed and abstract data, which require expertise to record and collect. Despite some issues, the procedure is widely adopted in social science inquiries collecting qualitative data.

Considering the selection of sample size, Patton (1990) argued that there is no rule for selection of an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Creswell and Creswell (2017) explained that decision of sample size in qualitative research lies with the saturation of the data, where no new candidate may be required if data collection has become saturated and no new information could be obtained by interviewing another candidate. A suitable sample size range was proposed by Leedy and Ormrod (2019) for phenomenological studies i.e. between five to twenty-five respondents. They also

defined the notions of information richness, which is characteristic of the respondents, from whom one can learn a great deal about the phenomenon being studied. Past doctoral studies employing phenomenological methodology mostly conform to this range. Thapa (2016) used a sample of six respondents in phenomenological study of teachers. Garcia (2015) recruited five female principals, while studying their work life balance under phenomenological settings. Rehman and Roomi (2012) utilized a sample of twenty female entrepreneurs from Pakistan to study their experience with work-life balance in Pakistan. Martinez (2018) obtained data from seven respondents, while studying work-life balance of female employees in public sector. Lastly, Zimmerman (2021) employed a sample size of twelve respondents in her doctoral dissertation studying work-life balance of millennial professionals. Following these notions, I planned to collect data from about twenty respondents, and collect more if no data saturation achieved after 20 interviews. Due to geographical and time constraints, I managed to collect data from eighteen women respondents, comprising my final sample size. It was noted that data saturation started to incur after about ten respondents. Due to geographical constraints, as I was not able to visit Pakistan in person to collect data due to COVID-19 travel restrictions, I kept on collection data to ensure that all relevant information and related details have been captured by my collected data and ended up with 18 respondents in my sample. Apart from that, I also interviewed two male managers to obtain insights pertaining to the male perspective on work-life balance of females employees of contact centre, pushing my final sample size to twenty.

4.6 Data collection

Phenomenological research requires qualitative data, where interviews are deemed a suitable option to collect the data (Moustakas, 1994; Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

Guest et al. (2020) also explained that interviews method of data collection could be used to obtain rich details on the personal accounts, perceptions, and experiences. Smith et al. (2009) also argued that phenomenological research design requires the input from the respondents, who are open to the sharing of the information, where such information could relate to the description and elaboration of the 'lived experience' of the respondents. Moustakas (1994) also necessitated collection of first hand, direct, and detailed information from the respondents to qualify for phenomenological inquiry.

Following these lines, I conducted semi-structured in-depth interviews with 18 women employees from the contact centre industry to answer the research questions under the framework of phenomenological research. I further conducted interviews of two male managers for a detailed understanding of work–life balance for women in the contact centre settings as many employees referred to the role of male managers. Since these interviews were arranged in the unusual scenario of Covid-19, I was utterly dependent on the point person from the contact centre for scheduling the interviews and on the availability of participants. All the participants were contacted through email and were provided a brief background, introduction, purpose, and scope of the research. After providing the information, an informed consent was also obtained from the respondents, where they agreed to share the relevant information with me. Obtaining informed consent is necessary from the respondents to ensure that the interview goes smoothly and no unwilling respondents signs up for the survey. Ethical hallmarks of the research also require informed consent, and collection of data without any coercion or deception (Saunders et al., 2009). Although, informed consent was partially obtained through the information sheet, although there have been concerns that information sheet have become long and complex over the time (Ennis

& Wykes, 2016). Respondents were also provided the option to skip interview questions, or leave the entire interview. They were also ensured confidentiality of the collected data and privacy of their information collected, which are also important aspect of research ethics (Saunders et al., 2009).

The interview required questions pertaining to personal information of the respondents, which is tricky as respondents may feel discomfort or may refrain from answering such questions. Culture of Pakistan is conservative, where males and females mostly remain separate and open interaction between opposite gender is discouraged. Therefore, most of female employees were not comfortable with video calling interviews, so I had to rely on voice only calls. It took me extra time to complete all interviews, but I had to respect employees' points of view. I started with a pilot interview which helped me with estimating the time required to complete the interview and to gauge whether the research goals and design were realistic. Yin (2009) explained that conducting a pilot study is a norm in survey research, where it enables the researcher to improve research instrument and data collection procedure (Saunders et al., 2009). Baker (1993) required to conduct a pilot study of at least 20% of the sample. Pilot study is a small scale version of the whole research, done with a view to consider issues in the process of complete data collection. The issues encountered were related to availability of the respondents, where some interviews took days to complete. Some questions were also improved, where long questions were broken down into the small questions and some vague questions were replaced with more clear questions.

After assurance that there was no issue pertaining to the question being asked, I completed the full run of the data collection from all 18 female respondents. It was noted that many respondents were not used to interviews, and their answers would

lead to other complex scenarios linked with cultural challenges of working with Chinese management and decision-making policies of male managers. Considering the involvement of the male managers and management in the interview responses, I decided to interview some male floor managers as well to understand their conception of work-life balance of women in contact centre industry of Pakistan. I prepared more questions for managers to better understand the actual situation of work–life balance in the organisation. I began interviewing the candidates in March 2020 and concluded all the interviews in November 2020. It was extremely challenging to match participants' time and availability due to Covid-19 and the five-hour time difference between the UK and Pakistan. I had to make sure, that settings were quiet to ensure audio recordings for all the interviews. I changed daily routines to match participants' availability and completed interviews with all the participants from home. I did not experience any problems related to technology during the interview process, except the first interview. There was some internet issue at participant's end as initially I tried to use WhatsApp. Due to the problem with the internet connection in Pakistan, and related distortions, I had to switch to voice network calls, which provided a clearer voice quality. As phenomenological study required me to record the interview completely, I altogether switched to network based calls to ensure clear voice recordings. It was a costly choice, but I saw no other way of completing the calls. The interview guide was prepared in both Urdu and English languages, as Urdu is national language of Pakistan. It was noted that Most participants were comfortable with Urdu as interview language. Although I asked whether they were comfortable with an interview in English or Urdu. Language is an important aspect in qualitative research, as respondents would be more expressive in their native language (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

I noted that about 80% of the respondents were not comfortable with interview recording. I assured them about confidentiality of the data collection and privacy of their personal information. I discussed the need for the audio recordings and provided them option of written assurance, that the data will remain confidential and information, private. After due deliberation, they agreed to the recording since I gave them detailed insights into the aim and purpose of the study. All interviews lasted between four to eight hours due to the situation mentioned above. All interviews started with a brief introduction from my side, as in most cases, respondents were not familiar with me. During the whole interview, I repeatedly asked respondents about their issues, concerns, or worries to earn their trust, which is considered an important element to solicit detailed and valid information from the respondents (Amankwaa, 2016). Since I interviewed female employees, I found it hard to interrupt with some questions due to cultural and social values. So, I just had to let the conversation flow, and the rare occasion of interruption was with a question, as I did not want to lose the free-flowing, dynamic mannerism of the conversation. In order to encourage the participants, I always tried to use open questions so participants could openly describe their experiences. In order to make participants comfortable during the interviews, I asked descriptive questions before moving on to more methodical ones. I also prompted them through probing questions in order to find out more about a particular experience or situation from time to time. Probing questions very often led to a richer data and better understanding of the subject matter (Chadwick, 2017).

Once participants understood, what the study was about to them, most of them did not need any additional guidelines to describe their experience. A small number of participants also got into storytelling mode about their non-work related experiences. In all such cases, the arranged questions were helpful to bring back their focus to

original study. In order to make participants comfortable with the study, I asked them about their educational experiences as most of them were highly educated and overqualified for contact centre jobs. The question around their educational background made employees comfortable, and most of them automatically started to talk about issues like role of management, working hours and career chances of women in Pakistan. Due to the time difference between the UK and Pakistan standard time, It was always challenging to complete a conversation on same day. In case of daybreak, they would want to go back to questions and views from the last session. Some of them wanted to counter-question me about my experience of interviewing them, and in some cases, they were only interested in knowing whether their work-life balance experience was unique or familiar.

In order to avoid self-bias in the data collection, I followed recommendations of Moustakas (1994), who recommended self-reflection and bracketing for awareness of preconceptions, and avoiding any influence of these preconceptions or knowledge on data collection process. For most of the data collection process, I refrained from speaking much, and remained at the listening end. The interview was semi-structured in nature, enabling me to track back to the objectives of the study. I practiced restraint to ensure that I do not lead the respondents in any direction. I just encouraged them to speak and share personal experiences. Such restrained enabled me to collect data without any visible bias on my part.

4.7 Data analysis

After collection of the qualitative data, this data is organized and analysed as per traditions of the qualitative data analysis. Creswell and Creswell (2017) explained that qualitative data collection yields voluminous unorganized data that could be in various shapes. Therefore, it is advisable to convert the data in a consistent shape, by

transcribing and translating the data in one language. Since, collected data in the study was in Urdu and English language audio recordings, the data was first transcribed and translated into English language for consistency. Halcomb and Davidson (2006) explained that verbatim transcription of the qualitative data is deemed essential in the qualitative research, and it is more relevant in phenomenological inquiry (Crowther et al., 2017). In order to protect privacy of respondents, and ensure anonymity, all identification information was expunged from the transcription. Such information was related to names, demographical information, and skills of the respondents that could be identified with a particular individual. The transcription was a lengthy and hectic process, requiring me to spend five to eight hours on each interview. After transcription of the interviews, the transcribed data was review to improve formatting and remove grammatical errors from the data. As most of the interviews were conducted in Urdu, I myself translated the data from Urdu to English as Urdu is my first language, so it was able to manage this feat. Translation of data from one language to another bears risk of alteration of meaning or context, so I ensured after listening and re-listening the interviews, that I am translating the data in its true form. I listened recording four to five times to ensure the right transcription.

After completion of the transcription, I followed proposed framework of Moustakas (1994) to analyse data and find answers to the research questions. The framework proposes a six-point process to data analysis in phenomenological study i.e. deployment of research epoche, reduction, imaginative variation, synthesis, saturation, and description. Firstly, epoche enabled me to self-reflect to become aware of my preconceptions of the phenomenon under study. I listened to the interview recordings and reviewed the transcribed data with an intent to start a anew. Further, I also made notes of my preconceptions and thoughts on the phenomenon

prior to data analysis to ensure that I am aware of my biases. After the self-reflection and intent to start anew, I started phenomenological reduction, which represents an ongoing and circular process, requiring examination and re-examination of data on multiple levels and different points in time (Yeh & Inam, 2007). This is similar to constant comparison method, where competing ideas in the data are identified and compared with each other to facilitate emergence of common themes (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). Phenomenological reduction was started by considering file of each respondent, where data in the file was sorted into meaning units. Moustakas (1994) referred this to as horizontalization. These meaning units are separated from the raw data and represent experience or feelings of the respondents on some particular aspect. All the irrelevant or repetitive data was excluded, and relevant data containing meaning units was transferred to the NVivo. Considering the large and complex dataset, manual analysis and coding of the data was difficult, so I opted to sought software support to facilitate data analysis for the study. NVivo is considered an effective tool to organize and analyse large and complex qualitative dataset (Jackson & Bazeley, 2019). The software supports qualitative data analysis through queries, which enable researcher to have rich insight into the data. This helps conversion of meanings units into codes, that are repetitive meanings units in the data. The coding is an iterative procedure that enable researcher to explore the data back and forth to identify meaning units that are present in description of many respondents. The data is constantly explored, reviewed, and compared to develop, refine, and revise emerging codes. Cross analysis of emerging codes also enables the researcher to find similarities and differences between the cases or respondents (Elliott & Timulak, 2005). After the codes are established, they were cross checked with their definitions to make sure that each code is used consistently, and data piled against each code

relates to the same meaning unit. Emergence of codes concludes phenomenological reduction. After the reduction, the codes are clustered to form themes, this step requires interpretive approach and requires imaginative variation. The emerging themes represent related codes, that are made of meaning units identified during horizontalization. These themes were gauged for their relevance to the research questions, and irrelevant themes were deleted. This step requires synthesis, where data is saturated around the emergent themes. This approach is similar to the thematic analysis that is widely used in qualitative data analysis. Braun and Clarke (2006) explained the procedure of thematic analysis, which is depicted in the following tables:

Table 4.1 Thematic analysis procedure

Steps	Description
Familiarizing with data	Transcribing data, reading and rereading the data, noting down initial ideas
Generating Initial Codes	Coding interesting features of the data systematically across the entire data set, collating data relevant to each code
Searching for themes	Collating codes into potential themes, gathering all data relevant to each potential theme
Reviewing themes	Checking if the themes work in relation to the coded extracts and entire data set, generating a thematic map
Defining and naming themes	Ongoing analysis for refining the specifics of each theme and the overall story that the analysis tells, generating clear definitions and names for each theme
Producing the report	The final opportunity for analysis. Selection of vivid, compelling extract examples, final analysis of selected extracts, relating back to original research questions and the literature review, producing a report of the analysis.

After the emergence of themes, rich quotes from the data supporting themes were used to describe the phenomenon and write a report. After development of themes, I

was able to generate a list of themes immediately after data analysis. In the next step I arranged them into two major categories: perceptions and challenges. I started with the challenges part since participants had taken much time to express challenges. I described every challenge one by one and paraphrased data from the participants on separate documents. As mentioned earlier I was able to recall almost every interview myself as well so it was easier for me to relate with most relevant quotes from the interviews. This helped me greatly, in the discussion sections as well as I was able to explain each theme. This further enabled me in creating a connection between my findings and the existing literature. These new topics have been mentioned in the revised theoretical framework as well, which emerged during the data collection. The analysis section was drafted and drafted and quotes from the thematic analysis were embedded in the description of the results to enrich the analysis. This is consistent with Smith et al. (2009), who also proposed to write analysis of qualitative data in an iterative process.

4.8 Methodological rigor

Qualitative research design relies on collection and analysis of qualitative data. Although the process of data collection and analysis is quite systematic, many see it an arbitrary process, raising question on the nature of qualitative inquiry, deeming it less rigorous (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). This is also related to the trustworthiness of the research process and its findings. Merriam and Tisdell (2016) explained that trustworthiness or rigor of qualitative research relates to the degree of confidence, researcher and other audience have on the outcome of research. Likewise, Lincoln and Guba (1985) explained that trustworthiness is assuring the audience that findings of the research are relevant and worth attention. I used a systematic approach of maintaining rigor during the study. This approach was proposed by Lincoln and Guba

(1985) and explained by Forero et al. (2018). This is a four dimensional criteria related to credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability.

The first aspect of credibility refers to the confidence on the truthfulness of the findings of the study. Ensuring credibility ensure that the results obtained from the study are credible, believable, and true (Forero et al., 2018). In order to ensure credibility of data collected and results I employed recommended strategies like having prolonged and varied engagement with respondents, where I collected data from each participant in multiple engagements spanning from two to four weeks. Further, I also conducted pilot study to ensure that the data collection procedure is consistent and hassle free. Lastly, I was also engaged in peer debriefing, where I consistently obtained feedback from my supervisor during the whole research process.

Second rigor criterion is dependability, which relates to the reliability of the findings, and consistency of results, if the study is repeated with same cohort of respondents in same settings (Forero et al., 2018). In order to facilitate replication of the study, I provided a rich description of the methods and procedures that were employed to collect and analyse the data. Further, an audit trail can also be established as I have all the recordings, transcriptions, analysis and coding schemes, and thematic trail. Such audit trail could lead to improve dependability of the results (Lincoln & Guba, 1985)

Third rigor criteria in the framework is confirmability, which is related to the replication of the study to confirm its findings. It relates to the extent to which results could be confirmed by other researches (Forero et al., 2018). The results of qualitative study may be distorted by personal biases of the respondents. In order to ensure that no personal bias of mine affects the research process, I kept reflexive journal to note the developments of the research, and records of any potential bias that could have

distorted the research outcomes. I also noted rationale for each decision I took, while conducting this research as recommended by Merriam and Tisdell (2016) to ensure better reflexivity.

The last aspect of rigor is transferability of the research, which relates to the generalizability of the research in other settings (Forero et al., 2018). In order to ensure transferability, I opted a systematic procedure of selecting and purposive sample. The selection of the sample was not controlled by me, neither I had any acquaintance with most of the respondents, making the sample selection an arbitrary process, leading towards generation of relevant and rich data. Further, saturation of the insight was also noted after conducting half of the interviews, making the results generalizable, at least to the similar contexts.

Table 4.2 provides summary of rigor criteria and strategies adopted to ensure rigor of the research.

Table 4.2 Summary rigor criteria employed in the study

Rigour criteria	Purpose	Original Strategies	Strategies applied in our study to achieve rigour
Credibility	To establish confidence that the results from the perspective of the participants are true, credible and believable.	Prolonged and varied engagement with each setting	Interviewers spent an average of 2–4 weeks to engage with participants.
		Interviewing process and techniques	Interview protocol tested at two induction meetings and using 1–2 pilot interviews.

Rigour criteria	Purpose	Original Strategies	Strategies applied in our study to achieve rigour
		Peer debriefing	I had regular debriefing sessions with my supervisor
Dependability	To ensure the findings of this qualitative inquiry are repeatable if the inquiry occurred within the same cohort of participants, coders and context.	Rich description of the study methods	I prepared detailed drafts of the study protocol throughout the study.
		Audit trail	I developed a detailed track record of the data collection process.
Confirmability	To extend the confidence that the results would be confirmed or corroborated by other researchers.	Reflexivity	I kept a reflexive journal
Transferability	To extend the degree to which the results can be generalised or transferred to other contexts or settings.	Purposeful sampling to form a nominated sample	I used purposive sampling techniques to form a nominated sample

4.9 Ethical considerations

This study collected data from the human subjects through interviewing, giving rise to the ethical concerns to ensure that no human or living being was harmed, while collecting the data or conducting this research. Creswell and Creswell (2017) explained that researcher need to protect participants of the study from any possible harm, guard against misconduct, promote integrity, and establish trust with the stakeholders. Researcher must respect rights, values, needs, and opinions of the respondents. The issues causing ethical considerations are already explained in various sections of the methodology, particularly in data collection; following is a brief description of ethical aspects that are considered in this research:

- Informed consent – I shared back ground and purpose of the research to the respondents, prior to collection of the data. Their formal consent was sought to provide data, after they had reviewed the background and purpose of the research. Participants were also given a chance to refuse participation in the data collection. Even after the collection of the data, participants were given a choice to withdraw from research, and had this option till the start of data analysis. Informed consent is an important formality, that must be adhered at start of the data collection.
- Confidentiality and privacy – Confidentiality of the data collected and privacy of respondents are a key priority in quality research (Creswell & Creswell, 2017), as qualitative data, particularly in the phenomenological research design, where respondents share their lived experience and personal feelings. I gave assurance to the respondents that data collected will remain confidential, whereas audio recordings will be destroyed by the end of the study. Further, privacy of the personal information of the respondents was also protected, and no personal information of the respondent was shared with anyone, and data is

used in the analysis in a generic manner, without any trace of identity revelation.

- Anonymity and data protection – The identities of the respondents were not revealed to anyone. The responses of the participants were transcribed in anonymous fashion, without any trace of personal information or identification mark. The collected data was stored in a password protected computer, and no one, other than the researcher has access to that data. All the audio recordings and transcription will be destroyed after the submission of this dissertation. All of this was explained in the consent form provided to the respondents. The consent form also confirmed that I do understand the eight principles of the Data Protection Act.
- Deception – It is important to gain trust of the respondents in the study. I tried to develop truthful and respectable relationship with the respondents, where no deception or lie was used to solicit any information from the respondents. I have tried to present the findings of my study with honesty and transparency as well. The Research Ethics Committee of UWS approved my research design, where I assumed that no wrongdoing will be done while conducting this research, and rights and interests of the respondents will be protected at any cost.
- Access to human participants - In order to recruit participants for the research, I used purposeful and snowball sampling. I approached the respondents through some common friends. The participants were explained that they were free to decide whether they want to be part of this study or not. As mentioned above, the participants were also free to withdraw from the research any time. I had no doubt that any of my gate keeper or I tried to influence the participants in terms

of their opinions while giving their answers. The voluntary character of the participants was emphasised in order to reduce any possible legal or ethical risks.

- Foreign participants - The research is mainly undertaken in the UK, but data was collected from the respondents of Pakistan. Data collection from participants in Pakistan complied with UK Data Protection laws. There was no additional ethical approval required in Pakistan, university, or UK.
- Direct contact with human participants - This study used phenomenological interviews for data collection. Participants for this study were recruited with the help of the management of the contact centre. Due to the Covid-19 situation, I was completely reliant on resources provided by the point person of a contact centre. The participant information sheet and consent form were sent to the participants at least 72 hours before each interview. The participants were fully explained about their rights to refuse to participate in the study. The data for the research was collected during the lockdown in Pakistan, giving rise to time management issues for participants. I made everybody aware that they can withdraw from the study anytime during or after data was collected. Most of the participants were becoming part of any research study for the first time. Thus I also ensured that they were not feeling any anxiety or risk of emotional distress. I had made it very clear to participants that they could stop or postpone interviews as per their comfort and wishes.

4.10 Reflexivity

Reflexivity has emerged as an important aspect of the qualitative research. Dodgson (2019) explained that qualitative research is always based on a context. It occurs between at least two people in a particular place, and on a specific time. The research

must elaborate all essential elements of space, to enable the reader to understand the context of the research. In context of qualitative research, researcher is considered a research instrument, influencing the context, settings, and outcome of the research. Considering this conceptualization of the researcher, it is important to describe researcher in a way that is relevant to the research. In this context, Schön (2017) explained that reflexivity relate to the extent to which researcher treats himself as an object of enquiry to embedded necessary details of his/her personality to disclaim his influence on research outcome, and related learning. Rolfe et al. (2001) described reflexivity as method of research, which embraces the subjectivity of researcher and exploit it. Gorelick (1991) also explained that researcher undergoes a transformative experience during the research process, where such transformation and learning is influenced by the research respondents, as they are influenced by the researcher. Therefore, it is imperative that researcher describes the transformation process to enrich the research context. Smith (2006) recommended confessional tales for this, where researcher needs to confess any possible influence of his personality on the research process.

Smith (1999) stressed on the need to reflexive research, as writing reflexively could increase self-awareness of researcher and promote a self-thought process to acknowledge important issues in the research. Jasper (2005) also argued that reflexive writing was central to the research process, and must be incorporated in the study as a viable source of data to improve trustworthiness and rigor of the research. In this regard, Berger (2015) argued that qualitative researchers should consciously consider their sensitivities and self-knowledge; with a view to understand their role as an instrument of knowledge creation; and monitor the possible influence of their preconceptions, experiences, beliefs, and biases on the research. This could enable

the researchers to maintain a balance between universal and personal considerations of research process. Smith (2006) also noted that reflexive writing has an ability to enhance credibility of the research, where documentation and acknowledgement of involvement of the self in the research process makes the process more transparent and visible. Smith (1999) highlighted that maintaining a reflexive journal could provide audit trail to make the research more reliable. Tracking all the progress and making reflection also provide new insight to the researcher, making the research more trustworthy.

During the research process, I have been regularly asking myself questions regarding bias, identity and the development of the study. My research supervisor has been regularly questioning me about validity of studies as well. Additionally, I have been regularly challenged by my supervisor in regards to development of a qualitative narrative framework. Thus it became essential to have an active reflexive process for justifying the credibility of my eventual findings. I practiced reflexivity during whole research process, where I employed tools of phenomenological epoché and reflexive journal writing. Phenomenological epoché improved my awareness on my preconceptions of work-life balance and also enabled me to re-evaluate my thoughts on work-life balance of females, as my thoughts were influenced by my gender and Pakistani origin. I explicitly described myself as a Pakistani male, with past experience and some friends in the contact centre industry. These connections and my past experience enabled me to approach my respondents and I was better able to make sense of the experiences of employees working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. Reflexivity also enabled me to tap into my preconceived ideas and biases embedded in my thought process. I started a reflexive journal to mark my progress during the research process, where I explained a rationalized each decision related to

data collection and analysis. I also noted my perceptions on the process of data collection and took notes in the reflexive journal after each interview. Likewise, the reflexive journal was updated during the data analysis and supported in thematic analysis to facilitate emergence of themes. Overall, reflexivity paradigm made me more aware of thought processes, facilitated me to embed more insight to research, and enabled me to improve my research outcomes in this study.

Chapter 5

Findings and Interpretations

Fifth chapter of the study provides discussion on the findings of the study and interprets these findings in the light of the literature review. I conducted phenomenological interviews of the female employees of contact centre from Pakistan. Responses of the managers were also sought to better contextualize and cross reference the findings obtained from the female employees. Thus, this chapter summarizes and discusses key findings and provides phenomenological interpretations of these findings, considering the context of Pakistan. Original names of the respondents have been replaced with the codes to ensure anonymity and privacy of the respondents.

I used thematic analytical procedure to organize the data and facilitate emergence of themes. The analytical procedure as explained by Braun and Clarke (2006) was employed in this phenomenological study. The emergent themes were organized considering the lived experiences of the respondents as to how they feel about their work, their life, and interaction of their work and life. The analysis in this part focuses on the personal experiences of the respondents i.e. women working in the contact centre of Pakistan. The analysis starts with a general description of certain aspects of contact centre industry and its work force, focusing on the themes of 'working in the contact centre industry' which is followed by the 'motives to start job in the contact centre', and then the 'skill requirements required in the industry'. After a general overview of industry, the analysis focuses on different aspects and characteristics of 'work' in the contact centre industry. After that work, 'life domain' is related in the lights of views of the respondents. After the life domain, themes pertaining to 'work life balance' and 'work life interaction' are discussed.

5.1 Working in a contact centre

Initially, it would be beneficial to relate to the expressions of the respondents on general outlook of the work in the contact centre industry and skill requirement of suitability of contact centre work for different cohorts of workforce. This initial description would facilitate the reader to have a better context of the industry, as per views of the respondents.

5.1.1 General outlook

The general orientation of women working in contact centre industry was not much pleasant. Most of the women described working in the contact centre as tough, difficult, or taxing. Almost all the respondents related to the demanding nature of the job and described the experience of working in the contact centre in likewise connotations. In this regard, respondents related to their workplace as 'electronic panopticon', 'jail like conditions', 'cruel place to work', 'bootcamp of stress and pressure', and 'exceedingly difficult environment'. On the other hand, respondents described their work as 'jumping out of fire into frying pan', 'battle for survival', 'running against fast blowing wind', 'hectic and tiring work schedules', and 'extremely challenging'. These connotations indicated that respondents have negative feelings about their work place and work, giving rise to a general negative outlook to the experience of working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. One of the respondent explained that contact centre work is not suitable for a long term career, and

"you should only work here on temporary basis and move on, once you have a better opportunity."

Another respondent related to the demanding nature of the work in the contact centre industry and explained that,

“in contact centre it is all about deadlines, urgent meetings, and prioritizing everything on your own life.”

Another respondent explained the woes of employees of contact centre and stated that

“factors like under-staffing, poor succession planning, excessive workloads and last-minute unpredicted tasks are the real worries behind woes of employees in contact centre.”

All of these notions relate to the tough and demanding nature of job at the contact centre industry of Pakistan. Not a single respondent appreciated working in the contact or related to the experience as pleasant. There were some opinions arguing that the job might be difficult, but it is, what it is. Like one respondent argued,

“This is what, it is, they need people to fill in early morning shifts. If you want it, take the role otherwise no one is forcing you to do the job.”

Another respondent tried to provide a balanced opinion and related to working in the contact centre as “a combination of good days and bad days”. The manager interviewed also provided a somewhat defensive view and explained that,

“customer use our service 24/7, so we need to be available 24/7 as well. Now everyone can extract meaning according to their understanding, but it is what it is.”

Interpretations

Considering the overall outlook on the notions on working in the contact centre industry, female employees of the contact centre industry related to it as tough and demanding job, where the focus in on the work, and not on the well-being of the employees. Some respondents dejected the idea of working in the contact centre for long periods of time and complained in the work routines and on nature of the work.

There were also few who argued that the job is difficult by default, and it is what it is. Contact centre industry has long been highlighted as an industry with tough work practices and strict environment (Guest, 2002; Taylor & Bain, 1999; Woodcock, 2016). Previous studies in Pakistan also highlight the same notions (Akhtar, 2019; Khalid et al., 2013). Such difficult nature of the job with high work demands and time requirements could create work-life balance issues for the employees of contact centre industry. This is particularly relevant to the female employees, who tend to face difficulties of tough work routine (Belt, 2002, King, 2020).

5.1.2 Suitability of contact centre job

Some respondents were of the opinion that contact centre job may not be suitable for everyone. Two consistent notions emerged in this regard. Firstly, many female respondents indicated that the job was more suitable for the young and unmarried individuals, who have more energy and time to keep up with the requirements of the job. Secondly, some female respondents deemed the job suitable for the males.

Considering the opinion of the respondents that the job was more suitable for the young and unmarried cohort of work force. Respondents argued that young people 'can adjust better to the hectic demands' of the job, and are 'prepared to work extra and different hours as they have less responsibilities'. One respondent provided a detailed explanation on this stating that

“when you are young, you have less things to worry and then it becomes easier to work in a place which has a strict schedule policy. Even at our workplace younger employees have greater motivation and are more productive. Probably they have higher energy to absorb the stress levels and cope better with productivity and absenteeism challenges.”

Another respondent also highlighted the relevance of the 'age group' of employees and stated that

“You will not see many young girls complaining about work life balance as they do not have many responsibilities, so they are happy to juggle around whatever they must juggle with. Once they get responsibilities, they seem to get excessively indulgent towards one aspect of life and fail to find harmony.”

One of the respondent even recommended that contact sector industry was a good experience for the young people, and encouraged 'young people to work in contact centre, even if it is for short duration' to gain exposure of a strict work routine. Same notions were also expressed by the female floor manager, who stated that

“I have lot of younger teammates who remind me of my young days where I had less commitments outside work, so I used to put all my energy towards job at hand.”

Thus, young people with lower responsibilities and more energy would be more suited to the demands of the job in the contact centre industry of Pakistan.

Being old and having family responsibilities go hand in hand in Pakistani culture, and this is more true for the females. Females get married, start a family, and entrusted with the household responsibilities in Pakistani culture. Many respondents argued that their work orientation had 'totally changed' after marriage into a 'battle for survival'.

Another respondent explained that,

“Once you are married and have a family, you are driven by your personal and family commitments and this is where you need flexible options.”

Working in contact centre becomes difficult after getting married for women, and even more so after having children, like one of the respondents expressed that,

“When I was younger and not married, I did enjoy better physical and psychological health even though I was working in contact centre.”

The same respondent also explained that,

“though I do not have children now, but my occupational commitment is relatively low as compare to younger employees of contact centre.”

Even younger-unmarried women working in contact centre industry also realize that sooner or later they will have to undergo the pressure and decide between their job and family. One of the younger employee provided a detailed explanation of the phenomenon in the following words:

“Though I have not got married yet, but lot of my colleagues have resigned due to non-availability and affordability of dependent care. This is mostly in form of childcare as they must face double pressure and burden from the employers and their family as well... Though I am not married but when I imagine myself with the problems faced by my colleagues, I also fail to check off lot of boxes”.

Then there was a specific issue of pregnancy and child birth. Many women undergo a lot of physical and emotional deviations and require special care during their pregnancy. Contact centre industry seems a less suitable workplace for such women.

Some respondents expressed this concern and explained that

“several women employees leave their job during maternity since most of the jobs in customer care demand zero flexibility.”

Likewise, the life of women changes after their child birth with increased responsibilities of taking caring of their baby. Therefore,

“lot of women never come back to contact centre after their maternity leaves ends and leave their demanding job to better take care of their child”.

Some of the respondents were of the opinion that the job was more suited to the males. One of the respondent explained that,

“many women are homemakers as well and they are forced to go for jobs and take up even careers that were considered only suitable for men such as working in contact centre which is extremely tough on mind and body.”

This feeling might stem from the general patriarchal structure of society in Pakistan, where men are expected to take up jobs, while women take up their home related responsibilities. One of the respondent pointed towards this by arguing that,

“the prime structure of work in our culture is primarily made to suite to the needs of men rather than women, so contact centre is not an exception as well.”

The same respondent explained this phenomenon for female managers working in the contact centre industry and highlighted that,

“The middle and senior management culture in contact centre is designed and developed to suit male employees. For example, we have night shifts as contact centre work 24/7 so it is almost impossible to have a female manager in night shift.”

Interpretations

It was noted that young individuals had lower responsibilities and had more energy and motivation to cope up with the workload and strict routine of the contact centre industry, whereas older employees might not be ‘happy’ in this regard. It was also expressed that contact centres prefer ‘hiring young’ people, who ‘know little about their work life concerns and requirements’. These notions indicated that respondents considered young individuals more suitable for the job.

With regard to the specific responsibilities of women in a patriarchal society, it was noted that each step of women life – getting married, undergo pregnancy, and taking

care of children – adds responsibilities and difficulties to the life of women working in the contact centre industry, and they have to decide between their family responsibilities and continuing their jobs, making contact centre job less suitable for women in Pakistan. It was also noted that working in the contact centre industry might be more challenging for the women, compared to men. This might be due to the work demands or due to general patriarchal structure of Pakistani society. Previous studies also relate to the efforts of women in a patriarchal societies, where women are expected to perform household responsibilities (Grünenfelder, 2013; Itrat et al., 2007) and job responsibilities are ranked after the household responsibilities (Omar et al., 2004). This makes job of women more difficult for them as they have to juggle along household and job related responsibilities at the same time.

Overall, women perceived contact centre job to be more challenging for older cohort, where marriage, pregnancy, and child care responsibilities could add more challenge to their work and life. Further, some women also deemed the job more suitable for the males. Thus, one respondent concluded that,

“There is a significant relationship between work life balance perception and the demographic variables like marital status, age, gender, etc”.

5.1.3 Motives to work in contact centre industry

Respondents were requested to relate to their motive to find and start a job with contact centre industry to better understand why women opt to pursue a ‘challenging’ job. Most repeated notions in this regard were related to the financial reasons, being unable to find other any other job, and provision of the pick and drop facility. Some respondents also expressed other motives like obtaining experience or doing something worthwhile for self-esteem.

Firstly, with regard to the financial reasons, female respondents related to the poor economic and employment conditions in Pakistan, and explained that it is important for them to provide financial support to their families, their husbands, or their educational endeavours. In this context, one of the respondent explained that,

“I need to support my husband as my salary goes towards paying rent otherwise, I would have resigned a long ago. I have continued to work here against my wishes, and I have paid a price in form of personal life.”

Another respondent explained that,

“Many of us are supporting our families, so it is critical to keep going”.

Some respondents were doing job to support their education, like one respondent highlighted that doing the job was requiring her to complete her education in more time, but supporting herself during the study was important for her. She stated that,

“This will take 4 years instead of 2 years but I must support myself here in terms of finances so I cannot leave this job...I belong to a middle-class family and there are numerous employees who also come from same background, we have same finance related problems.”

In this context, ‘stuck due to their financial reasons’ was a prominent theme, which was highlighted by many respondents.

Apart from the financial reasons, the second prominent theme was related to the inability of the respondents to find other job or convenience of finding a job in the contact centre industry. Respondents repeatedly made the point that highly qualified people were working in the contact centre, and that they were unable to find suitable jobs in their respective domains. One respondents indicated that

“highly qualified people are working in contact centre due to lack of job opportunities in their areas of specialties.”

Likewise, another respondent also noted that same and explained that,

“The contact centre is a strange place where you will see lot of highly educated individuals along with very modest stature candidates in term of education record. But there is one thing common between them and it is their failure to move on to desire roles or acquire jobs in their relevant fields.”

One respondent shared the personal experience in this regard, and explained that,

“I did try to get job in my own field, but Geology jobs are almost 100% Government sector. I did not have the enough links and references to get job in Government sector. I knew someone who was working in contact centre on basis of our regional language. Since I speak same language, which is Sindhi, so I got job in contact centre and as they say rest is history”.

Some respondents also indicated that they were unable to find any other job due to their modest education or some other reason, and they opted for this job. One of the respondent explained that,

“I did try to find jobs in my field for few months but then I lost the patience and took the first opportunity which came my way.”

Another respondent also highlighted the same notions of opting job in the contact sector industry as the last option and stated that,

“I am not very well educated so I did not have many options. I would only recommend you work in contact centre only If you have no other option and you are desperate to earn a living.”

Lastly, it was also noted that getting job in contact centre was easy or convenient. One respondent indicated towards the ease of getting a job in the contact centre industry by highlighting that,

“I was free after my exams for my bachelor’s degree and someone advised me to work for telecom sector as it is a booming industry in Pakistan.”

Another respondent indicated that,

“I knew someone in China Mobile, so I get hired here. Well it is incredibly challenging, but I have no other option.”

Lastly, some respondents were doing the job to pass some time. Like one respondent explained that,

“I am just waiting to get married and using this job as an excuse to kills the gap.”

Considering the overall scenario of inability of finding another job, it could be argued that females working in the contact centre industry do not adopt this job as a career choice, rather they opt for this job due to convience of finding a job or due to their inability of finding a relevant job in the market. One respondent provided a strong but relevant view in this regard, and stated that,

“I have no problem in saying that only those people work in contact centre who have almost got no option left elsewhere”.

The third most repeated theme in the motives to joining contact centre was related to the provision of pick and drop facility. In Pakistan, women carry a protected status and males in the family take the responsibility of picking and dropping them to their work or education place. Contact centres in Pakistan provide pick and drop facility to women, which is considered a plus point in the country. Thus, many women and their family members feel at ease, if pick and drop service is available from the employer. These notions were expressed by many respondents, like one respondent explained that,

“They were providing me with pick and drop facility which is a popular thing in our culture. It allows men in our families to get away from taking responsibilities

of their women.”

Another respondent deemed the job favourite for the family, as it is providing pick and drop facility. She explained that,

“women employees are provided with pick and drop facility which makes this job as favourite among parents and guardians.”

Although, some females expressed their distaste for the facility stating that they feel like a ‘parcel’; whereas others were positive for the facility as it was free of cost, saving transpiration cost and providing ease. One respondent highlighted the ease of having transport facility by stating that,

“Surely the job in contact centre sounds extremely attractive from outside as you get free pick and drop which is a big hassle in our country.”

This facility was also the reason for female retention in the contact centre as one respondent expressed that,

“the company has provided us with free transport which has helped me to stay here for 5 years.”

Despite the facility and its merits, many female employees complained about the travel time, where the transport facility took 2 to 4 hours extra in the travel time. Further due to this extra time, many female employees have to leave the home very early. One of the respondent exclaimed that,

“it has destroyed my personal life as I must leave home early around 4 am. The office is not far from my home, but we are picked according to assigned route, so I must bear that. Our actual shifts are 9 hours but normally we end up adding 1 hour each in start and end of the shift and with pick and drop.”

Another respondent noted that,

“the women in contact centre struggle with commute challenges. It is a free transport, but it adds almost 4 hours on top of 9-hour shift.”

There were complains that this extra time has ‘robbed (the respondent) of precious time for personal growth or family matters’, has forced the respondents to have ‘lesser sleeping hours’, has ‘exacerbated work-family tensions’, and is a ‘big price in form of poor work life balance’. Overall, the transport facility was a positive feature of working in the contact industry, but the travel time due on the standardized route was adding strain on the personal life of the respondents.

Apart from these three major themes, some respondents explained that they wanted to get experience from the contact centre job to move to a better position. One of the respondent explained that,

“Like many people in contact centre I wanted to use this ladder to move to different department related to my expertise but unfortunately it did not work out as per plans or wishes.”

Apart from this, few respondents also related to the esteem of self-aspect, where respondents provided that they were doing the job to do something or actualize their potential. But these were only few responses.

Interpretations

Women respondents related to three motives in relation to the working in contact centre industry. The first was related to financial reasons, where respondents were interested to support their studies or families. The second was convenience factor, or inability of respondents to find a job related to their credentials. The last was related to the provision of transportation, which provided ease to the females and their family, but was also causing an increased travel time for the females. These notions have been endorsed in the previous studies, where working women are disapproved in the

society (Grünenfelder, 2013; Kamal & Tariq, 1997), and mostly financial reasons could force the women to take up formal employment in such societies. Further, transportation is considered an important factor for women employment, as it facilitates women mobility and relieves the men in the family from pick and drop responsibilities (Noor & Isa, 2020). This indicates that women face employment limitations in male-dominant societies, where their economic pursuits are discouraged, and they have mobility-related issues. Thus, good pays and provision of transport encourage women to seek employment in the contact centre industry in Pakistan.

5.1.4 Skills required to work in contact centre

Respondents also related to the education or skill level that was required to work in the contact centre. It was noted that contact centre jobs did not require much of the qualifications or expertise from the employees of the contact centre industry. Despite the minimal skill requirements, contact centres still have many qualified employees. The low skill requirement of the job enables the contact centres to find abundant labour supply as one of the respondents explained that,

“since contact centre jobs are not skill-based jobs and there is an abundance of cheap labour thus it enables employers to replace the defective part and move on.”

The working employees of the contact centres are diverse in their educational background as related by another respondent, who stated that

“contact centres are a strange place where you will see a lot of highly educated individuals along with very modest stature candidates in terms of education records.”

This implies that educational or skill-based credentials are not required for the job. One of the respondents provided a detailed description of the skill requirements of the job and explained that,

“I used to feel bad that after spending so much time and energy and money, I am doing a job which anybody can do. You just need to know how to handle mouse and keyboard, basic knowledge of MS word, PowerPoint and Excel, and here you go. you have a job.”

Thus, the contact sector industry in never is short supply of the labour as one of the respondent sums up it nicely by stating that,

“I guess on the other hand working in contact centre does not require a specialised degree and thanks to high unemployment numbers, it is extremely easy to find replacement.”

Interpretations

It was noted that employees working in the contact centre industry have very low bargaining power, as they are easily replaceable. This might be the reason leading the contact centres to maintain workflow in a high pressure job environment. Contact centre industry functions on the handwork of the employees, who are not required to have any formal education or skills, apart from basic IT and computer skills. Previous studies have also noted that service sector jobs require minimal skills (Deka, 2020), and women are in such lower skill jobs (Senthana et al., 2020). Referring women to lower skill jobs like in contact centres also ensures that contact centres have adequate supply of labour force. This could be a potential reason, causing the contact centres to ignore well-being of their employees and prevent policies to ensure employee retention.

5.1.5 Competitive nature of job

It has been argued that contact centre industry is a competitive industry, and it is tough to work in the industry. First there is a considerable pressure to deal with external pressure and ensure sales. One of the respondents explained this stating

that,

“the contact centre is expected to support sales and marketing teams as competition is fierce. If contact centre fails to match the pace of sales and marketing teams, they are blamed for failure of the whole campaign.”

This highlights the role of contact centres in generating the sales and supporting sales staff. This competition is also reflected in the internal mechanism of the contact sector work, where managers believe that working round the clock could be a key to competitiveness. One of the respondents explained that,

“normally employers try to attract and keep best employees to remain competitive. But contact centre is completely opposite, where lot of young people are injected so they can cope with nonstop pressure.”

Another employee highlighted that,

“the environment in contact centre is very hostile, which I guess is linked with competition and perfection objective.”

The floor managers and employees of the contact centre industry also compete with each other to get maximum results. One experienced employee explained that,

“there is a cutthroat competition among our floor manager for getting top slot in monthly team rankings. Managers push us to perform at optimum levels and all the time.”

Interpretations

It was noted that contact sectors operates in a competitive industry, where employees and managers have to adopt competitiveness to succeed and progress. This might put extra strain on the employees of contact centre industry in Pakistan. Considering the general notions on the working in the contact centre industry, it could be noted that general outlook of the contact centre industry is deemed as tough or difficult, where

contact centre job is deemed more suitable to young and unmarried women, or to men. People working in the contact centre opted this job mostly for financial reason, or because they were unable to find a relevant job. Pick and drop service was also a reason for women to opt this job, despite the fact that opting the service increased travel time for women. No specific skill or education was deemed necessary to work in the contact centre. Lastly, contact centres operate in a competitive industry, where everyone is after the achievement of targets. There is indication such pressure in the contact centre job could lead the employees to suffer from stress and engage in counterproductive work behaviors (Bruursema et al., 2011; Dhanpat et al., 2018; Hooff & van Hooff, 2016). Such pressure and competitive nature of the job could contribute towards a general dissatisfaction with life and could make it difficult for employees to maintain a healthy work-life balance.

5.2 The work

The current study is focused on understanding work-life dynamics of women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. In this context, responses of women were obtained to relate to their lived experience of the work domain. Previous section provides background on the contact centre industry, whereas this section of analysis provides description women opinion and experience pertaining to work domain of their life. Different aspects of work were further segregated to provide a better description of experience of women employees in the contact centre industry of Pakistan.

The central themes identified pertaining the work experience of women employees were related to lack of flexibility, lower focus on wellbeing, higher workloads and odd working hours, discrimination and patriarchist culture, lower managerial and organizational support, strife competition, high level of monitoring, lower growth prospects, penalizing reward strategy, monotonous nature of work, profiling and

pressurizing, and lower work motivation and satisfaction. These themes along with their sub-themes are described in detail in this section of analysis.

5.2.1 Monotonous work

The work in the contact centre industry does not require much speciality. As described earlier, no specific skills or educational credentials are required to do the job. The work requires employees to repeat the same tasks over and over again, making the work tedious, monotonous, and tedious. One respondent described the work stating that,

“I am responsible for assignments of repetitive and monotonous nature.”

It was endorsed by another respondent stating,

“it is all about getting used to systems and knowledge and then it is piece of cake. We just need to repeat everything every day to customers. Same customers, same products.”

The repetitive routine tasks seem easy to perform as described by the respondent as ‘piece of cake’, but same repeat and monotonous work could be fatal to the motivation and innovative capabilities of the employees.

Many respondents expressed negative connotations with regard to the routine and monotonous nature of work. They expressed the situation as, being ‘caught in vicious cycle of work’, being treated ‘as robots’, ‘working in army or emergency services, where you must follow the roster’, ‘sitting in a cage’, and ‘stuck in a prison’. One respondent explained in nicely by stating that

“one time it feels like a jail as we have a fixed schedule for everything, like we are robots controlled by the employer.”

The fixed routine and schedule could be taxing for the employees, who then exclaim that,

“I feel like dragging myself every day to the work. It feels that I am in a prison with no way out.”

The work also deprive employees of their potential and creative abilities as noted by one respondent who argued that,

“this [routine work] has surely restricted my creative side and may have prevented me from realizing my full potential”.

Interpretations

It was noted that the work performed by the respondents in the contact centre industry is repetitive and monotonous in nature, which is easy to perform and does not require any specific technical skills; but such work is dull, boring, and may restrict people to use their creative side or actualize their true potential. The work of the contact centre had always been highlighted as such like Taylor and Bain (1999) pointed out it as an ‘assembly line in the head’, while Woodcock (2016) mentioned a factory like settings in this context. Loukidou et al. (2009) and Tsai (2016) highlighted that monotonous nature of work could lead to the boredom, and Woodcock (2016) mentioned higher turnover tendencies of contact center employees in this regard. Thus, nature of work at the contact center is uninteresting or unexciting, making it difficult for the employees to feel motivated about their work.

5.2.2 High workload and working hours

One of the most consistent theme that emerged from the interviews was description and ramifications of high workload and long working hours. With regard to the workload, one of the respondent complained that,

“I am not happy with my job as I think I am just working like a labour.”

The notions emerged under this theme were related to high pressure of work and higher workload, long working hours, extra work with no or little breaks, working on

holidays and not taking annual leaves, and taking work to home.

The work load and associated pressure in the contact centre industry is quite high.

This was nicely summed up by the line manager interviewed, who explained that,

“There is a famous quote used in telecom that says, customer use our service 24/7 so we need to be available 24/7 as well.”

Almost all the respondents talked about the excessive work load and high work pressure in the contact centre industry. The 24/7 philosophy is reflected in the work routine of the employees, one of whom exclaimed that,

“There is a constant pressure of being available 24/7. Managers demand instant connectivity all the time with no breaks and boundaries.”

Respondents also expressed that not only workload in the contact centre work is high, but they are required to do extra work or work on new projects, on top of their usual workload. One of the respondent explained this stating that,

“I struggle with high workload and [on top of that] I am given extra work or responsibility or am asked to work on another project.”

This was also repeated by another respondent stating that,

“every new challenge means more work, more late evenings.”

The work load seems an integral part of the work routines at the contact centre industry and there seem to be no break or exist from the work pressure. One respondent exclaimed in this connection that,

“the workload never goes down, neither the shifts are made any shorter, so one must cope up with all the workload challenges at the same time.”

The higher work load and constant pressure seemed very taxing and respondents seemed quite uneasy and vocal about the issue. Another employee explained that,

“the bar of nonstop work with zero margin of error is so high. It is especially higher in 24/7 work environment as employees must work nonstop to meet project demand.”

In this relation many respondents expressed notions like ‘no end to the job demands’, ‘ever increasing burden of excessive work’, and ‘working crazy hours with constant pressure’ to highlight plight of the female workers of contact centre industry. Even one of the respondent highlighted that many female employees do not want to get promotion to avoid more work and extra work hours. She explained that people in the contact centre industry do not want to progress or get promoted because, they

“are afraid of the workload and more hours attached with it [promotion].”

Few respondents also told that employees are encouraged to complete the work by working extra hours. She explained that,

“employees must end their shift on specific numbers and if they fail to achieve those with in 9 hours shift, they are encouraged to stay back and work two extras hours to achieve those KPIs.”

Some respondents also noted that complaints on the workload go awry on the management and people complain are suggested to resign from work. This suggestion could be made in an implied manner like on respondent explained that her friend,

“was told in hidden words that she can leave if she is not happy with the workload.”

In some cases the suggestion to resign could be expressed clearly, like another respondent explained that,

“this has become sort of a culture in our contact centre that people are politely asked to resign if they have problem with the workload.”

In relation to the theme, the second most repeated aspect of contact centre work is long working hours. Female employees complained a lot about the long working hours

and associated issues. Even line manager, who was interviewed, indicated that routine of long working hours stating that,

“even I end up working 50-65 hrs/week which is a lot of hours considering I only get paid for 40 hours. The customer advisors go through similar cycle, which is not ideal, but the nature of business keeps on challenging them to learn more even on their off days.”

Same notions were repeated by many respondents. One of them exclaimed that,

“my contract is 40 hours a week, but I end up doing 55 hours and if you add travel time it almost goes up to 75 hours a week which is just ridiculous amount of the work.”

Some respondents complained that they leave early in the morning and arrive late at home and in some instances,

“one cannot see sun for 6 months of winter.”

For women, transport hours also include in the time away from home, where many female respondents explained that they were spending 12 to 14 hours away from the home, including an average of two hours transport time. Most female employees explained that they leave from home early in the morning, get company transport, which leaves them at work about 45 minutes early. Then after work, transport picks up from work to leave them home late in the evening. One respondent explained that,

“though traditional 9-5 rigid hours can be stifling, but here in contact centre we will be more than happy to have those hours.”

One respondent explained the pressure and strain due to long work hours, and explained that,

“my work hours are not limited to 7 or 8 hours a day and I end up spending 12-16 hours at work.”

Some respondents also compared their working hours with their relatives and siblings to make the point that working hours were too long in the contact centre industry, and there is no break to counter negative impact of these long working hours. The notions of 'drained', 'overwhelmed', 'tired', 'worried', 'stressed', having 'poor mindset', and having 'anxiety' were expressed by the respondents in relation the long working hours. It was also explained by the respondents that long working hours are seen as a sign if hard work and growth in the contact centre industry. One of the respondent explained that,

“in contact centre people are encouraged to opt for voluntarily longer hours as this is considered as sign of hard work and going extra mile.”

In this connection, one respondent argued that,

“longer working hours are not winning formula as it is practised in contact centre.”

Another respondent explained that the managers also think longer work hours to be a winning formula. She told that,

“[Line Manger] works same, or I guess more hours than me and she thinks that this is the only way to get promoted so literally it was useless to talk to her.”

This highlights that long work hours have become a management philosophy in the contact centre industry and some respondents believed that long working hour philosophy is influenced by Chinese work culture. One of the respondents explained that, we often see our Chinese directors starting work from 6:00 am till 11:00 pm. This sends a clear message that quantity is especially important. Same approach is followed by our line managers as well who also strongly and blindly believe that long hours are key to getting ahead”. Thus, according to another respondent,

“the Chinese management has slowly injected long hours culture in us.”

Overall, it could be argued that long work hours was a regular feature of the work at the contact centre industry, where working long hours is seen as a sign of hard work and progress, whereas this long work hour culture was seemed to be influenced from the Chinese work philosophy and routines.

The next aspect of work load and work routine was related to the extra work, that was mostly unpaid, but required in the contact centre industry. Respondents noted the extra work as 'unregulated overtime', which was 'unpaid'. There was also an indication that work hours of the women employees were particularly long as one of the respondents explained that,

“the working days of women in contact centre are especially long, and longer than those of their male peers, as we must spend considerable time in other unpaid work as sessions before and after work.”

Another respondent explained that,

“we are expected to be available at odd hours, as well as potentially spend additional time at the office as needed or work on special days like Eid holidays or Pakistan Day etc.”

The workload also results for employees to work extra without any breaks. One respondent explained the extra working by stating that,

“sometimes, I give up my breaks to answer more calls in order to bring my targets down. This is very much appreciated by our team lead and line managers which is insane... It gets worse in the end of the month where these deadlines take better of me.”

The line manager interviewed had same opinion that employees need to work, even on their off days. She justified by stating that,

“the nature of business keeps on challenging them [employees] to learn more even on their off days.”

Apart from doing extra work during work days, employees in the contact centre industry are asked to work on the regular holidays and forgo their annual leaves. Employees worked on the special days like during Eid holidays and national days. Female employees expressed that having lower number of annual leave days are celebrated in the contact centre industry. One of the respondent exclaimed that,

“I have been working here for so long and there is not a single instance where I have taken complete 6 weeks of annual leave.”

Another respondent lamented work culture at the contact centre industry stating that,

“pushing people to work at their maximum levels all the time should not be celebrated. People should not be rewarded for having minimum annual leaves.”

Thus, it was noted that employees at contact centre industry are encouraged to work during the holidays and are also encouraged not to take their annual leaves.

In the last, few respondents also expressed that they have to take some work to their home. Employees have to remain connected to the work through phone or email in order to remain updated. One of the respondents explained this scenario by saying that,

“working in contact centre is all about having latest knowledge of the products so you can serve the customer with best possible information. This means that you very often must be attentive to emails after your work as well so you can keep yourself updated with latest information.”

Another employee also noted that contact centre work requires 24/7 attachment with the work. This was explained by highlighting that,

“now with phones and laptops it is like at work 24/7. I am always connected to my work ... Our employers encourage us to work from home even on our off days. Sometimes, people are given acknowledgments and awards for working from home which is foolish”

Interpretations

It could be argued that contact centre employees face high workload and also suffer from work pressure, and there is no solution to this issue in the contact centre work settings. Secondly, women employees at the contact centre were found to be working extra to make up for the workload and keep up with their job related responsibilities. Such extra work is mostly unpaid, but is appreciated by the management. Contact centre industry also requires its employees to remain in touch with the office, even after the work hours making it a 24/7 job. This again adds to the workload and long work hours dilemma. Previous studies have also highlighted workload and long work hours issue with reference to the contact centre industry (Deery & Kinnie, 2004; Simons & Buitendach, 2013). In this regard, Aldor-Noiman et al. (2009) explained the variable nature of work load at the contact centre industry, where workload remained higher during some days or certain times of a day, making it difficult for the contact centres to employ more workforce to manage workload. Therefore, existing workforce is forced to work extra to optimize costs. Such extra work creates issues for work-life balance and wellbeing of contact centre employees (Johnson & Lipscomb, 2006), and could cause a higher employee turnover (Chaudhary et al., 2023; Dhanpat et al., 2018).

Overall, work in the contact centre industry was characterized by female workers as bearing with high workload and long working hours with high work pressure. Employees also explained that they are encouraged to work extra hours, avoid taking

holidays, and remain intact with the work after work hours, which could lead towards a poor work-life balance.

5.2.3 Monitoring and quantitative targets

The work in the contact centre industry is highly monitored, where quantitative targets are required to be achieved by the employees. This requires the employees to be careful and ensure that all the targets are met within stipulated time period. Considering the level of monitoring, one female respondent explained that,

“even my greetings are monitored. I answer about 300 calls a day and around 7500 in a month... How much time I take to answer the call, and then how much time I take to answer call after that, all of this is monitored, and I am marked against it... If I do not answer a call within 15 seconds, team leader will be shouting my name as I have blown up the whole place. Since calls are monitored for recoding errors, so I can be even marked for a deeper breath or any impression which gets caught during the recording.”

Another employee explained that,

“the contact centre operations are governed on micromanagement basis where every move is caught and recorded. At work it feels that someone is looking at my shoulder all the times.”

There is a high focus on the compliance to the standard in the contact centre work. Many respondents expressed the notions of ‘zero margin of error’ for the work they perform. One of the employee provided that,

“we have zero tolerance towards sub-par work and people are forced to resign if they make same mistake thrice within 60 days”.

The quantification of the work and associated targets was also a highlighted feature of work in the contact centre industry. Most target assigned are quantitative in nature, and some respondents even argued that there is more focus on the quantity

compared to the quality of the job performed. One of the respondents argued that,

“the contact centre is all about numbers, and the focus is on quantity instead of quality.”

There is a stress on achievement of the quantitative targets as explained by one of the respondent stating that,

“our job is based around achieving our targets as we can obtain extra 25% of our monthly salary, if we achieve our targets.”

Thus, employees work hard and work extra to achieve their targets. One of the respondents related to this stating that,

“sometime, I give up my breaks to answer more calls in order to bring my targets down... It is such a hectic job and then one must give up breaks as well to manage the statistics of the day”.

Interpretations

Overall, it was noted that women employees in contact centre must cope up with high work targets, pressure, commitments, tight schedules, and the duties and responsibilities of life and home. Such high level of monitoring is practiced to ensure standardization and quality of service, but could cause elevation of pressure on employees (Russel, 2008). Such monitoring practice could also contribute to the feeling of work overload (Pico, 2006), and could be particularly more stressful for women employees, as women feel more stress compared to men (Domingo-Cabarrubias, 2012). Therefore, excessive monitoring with tough targets could cause an imbalance in work and life domains of women employees of contact centres in Pakistan.

5.2.4 Lack of flexibility

One of the most repeated theme emerged from the responses highlighted the lack of flexibility in contact centre work. Although the floor manager respondent argued that contact centre work is based on the adherence to the rules, and any form of 'flexibility should not break the law of adherence'; most respondents complained on the lack of flexibility. The sub themes emerged with regard to the lack flexibility are related to lack of relaxation at work, tendency to avoid leaves or off from work, policies and culture discouraging flexibility, scheduling issues, and inability to work part time or from home.

Firstly, women employees at contact centre industry complained on the strife nature of work with no margin of relaxation. Respondents in the contact centre industry related to their workplace as a place, which promotes 'nonstock work with zero margin of error'. Another respondent related to it with 'chaos on daily basis. The nature of work is continuous with no breaks or relaxations. One respondent compared a formal corporate sector job with contact centre job to note that,

"People need to understand that when you are working in the corporate sector, the routine is not that complex; you may go out for a walk, a coffee break or lunch break, early day off etc. However, in contact centre we must pay price for all such things, and they are marked as unusual activity."

Some respondents also argue that they sacrifice their official break to handle more calls, like one respondent explained that,

"Some time I give up my breaks to answer more calls in order to bring my targets down.

This is very much appreciated by our team lead and line managers which is insane."

This implies that lack of flexibility was being promoted by the managers. The respondents argued that work keeps them preoccupied and they can hardly think of anything else. One of the respondents highlighted that,

“I think my workplace is like 365 days of quarantine where I was not able to think or do anything other than work.”

These responses indicated that women employees feel unable to relax at the contact center. The next issue highlighted by the respondents was lower number of leaves from work. Some respondents explained that they prefer to come to the job, even if they are sick. Like one respondent argued that,

“So even I am sick and have a fever chances are I will not get a day off.”

Respondents also highlighted that people get limited numbers of annual leaves, and this behavior is celebrated in the contact century as one respondent explained that,

“The contact center is made up of machines and runs 24/7 with a regular schedule. We are encouraged not to take annual leaves rather people are celebrated for taking lesser number of annual leaves.”

It was highlighted by many respondents that contact center employees are unable to take off on national holidays, and also for other important life events like marriage, death of relatives, and dependent care. There had been indication that employees

“come to the shift on the back of news of death of their loved ones. They show up at work even if they had a traumatic event in their personal lives.”

Another respondent stressed that,

“it can be public holiday or emergency; one must show up to the work.”

The unsaid policy of no leave and forcing people to avoid leaves results in an inflexible work routine for employees, where they are to remain present at their workforce despite valid non-work related issues requiring off time from work.

It was also noted that call centers have policies that discourages flexibility. There is a bonus penalty for individual employees and her team, if she takes any off. One respondent explained that,

“if I decide to take a day off, It will not only impact my bonus but it will also hit team bonus as well.”

Respondents also complained about lack of support from the managers and HR. One of the respondents exclaimed that,

“my manager failed to help me with shorter days.”

Some respondents also complained on the policy to obtain a leave, where employees are required to book casual leaves well before time. One respondent explained the process by stating that,

“we need to apply for holiday 3 months before actual days, so I did book 2 weeks off for my marriage. I spoke to my manager few days before my marriage regarding extension of my leave. But he told me that 2 girls have already booked holidays in those days.

There is a rule in contact center that no more than 2 people can take off at same time.”

Another respondent also described that,

“For example, when my son is ill, I cannot get a day off as it we need to give 72 hours’ notice for casual leave otherwise our full bonus is deducted regardless of performance.”

There is even a policy to transfer or encash annual leaves, where employees are encouraged to sell their holidays to the employer. Thus, the bonus policy, leave approval policy, and leave encashment policy all suppress flexibility of the women employees, who could require these leaves to manage non-work aspect of their life.

Many respondents also noted that contact centers are run on the tight schedules, where each employee needs to follow the roaster. Failure to do so could result in reduction in the ‘monthly bonus’. Flexible work shifts were common demand of the respondents, who explained that contact center operations and schedules are fix and ‘leave little flexibility for employees’. Another respondent argued that there was

“a huge mismatch between working conditions and family needs.”

There was also an indication that even women with special needs, like during pregnancy are not facilitated for the work schedules. One respondent highlighted such issues and explained that she,

“used to suffer from mood swings (in pregnancy)... I used to get better in afternoon but there was no option available to start working after 11 am.”

Lastly, certain respondents also pointed out that contact center industry did not allowed flexible work options like working from home, working part time, or working for less hours. Respondents argued that many women wanted to ‘work part time’, whereas in the current work settings,

“the workload never goes down, neither the shifts are made any shorter, so one must cope with all the workload challenges at the same time.”

Although the line manager interviewed, provided input by arguing that company tries to protect data of their customers, which could have been misused outside the office premises.

Interpretations

It was noted that the bonus policy, leave approval policy, and leave encashment policy all suppress flexibility of the women employees, who could require these leaves to manage non-work aspect of their life. Work schedules at contact center industry also seem very rigid, with not facilitation for women employees, even for those who required some flexibility during pregnancy or for their studies. In this regard, Domingo-Cabarrubias (2012) highlighted difference between men and women, where women face different issues related to their health, pregnancy, family responsibilities, and safety. Previous research also highlights importance of work related flexibility for women (Fuller & Hirsh, 2019; Singley & Hynes, 2005). Work in contact center is

characterized by high workload, long working hours, and excessive monitoring, depriving employees any form of work flexibility. Considering the issues of women, lack of work flexibility could create work-life imbalance for women, who are also charged with the responsibility to manage household and take care of children.

Overall, work in the contact center industry is contextualized as lacking flexibility. The work is continuous, no leaves are allowed from the work, work culture and policies also deprive women of flexibility, scheduling is strife, and no flexible work options are available to women. This causes work-life balance issues for the women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan.

5.2.5 Lower managerial and organizational support

Respondents talk at length about the lack of or lower support from work agents including their managers, employer, human resource department, and from policies and culture.

Firstly, there was a particular focus on the lack of support from the managers or supervisors of employees. As indicated earlier that line managers compete with each other to work more. Thus, they are inclined to ask employees to work hard. Apart from the work aspect, many respondents related to the lack of support from their line manager, even during the time which might be important or critical for the employees.

One of the respondent blamed her manager for her failed marriage and stated that,

“he [manager] failed to realise my situation, so I blame my organisation for hiring such people to lead us...Many people know that my marriage failed, and my manager failed to help me with shorter days.”

Likewise, another respondent also related to the discussion with the line manager relating to her marriage, where the manager recommended her to quit the job and raise kids. She related that,

“I tried to have some soft discussions with my line manager about my marriage prospects and how I could manager with the new demands. He just smiled and told me to sit at home, enjoy marriage and raise kids.”

Likewise, another respondent related to her experience with the line manager during her pregnancy. She quoted that,

“in the start, I was reluctant to speak with my line manager. But than one cannot hide the changes which occur to one’ s body... I discussed all the possible scenarios with my line manager and all the possible outcomes, but my manager had extremely limited options to support me.”

There was also indication that line managers could allow certain level of flexibility or ease to the employees, but they do not facilitate their female employees in this regard.

One of the respondent explained it nicely by stating that,

“There is a clear lack of effort on our managers behalf...The operational model of contact centre allows duty floor managers to run the shift as they want. They can encourage or discourage employees’ efforts to balance their work and non-work lives for that day and the week. And this is where, the lack of intent becomes visible, and brings lot of disappointment.”

Likewise, another respondent also argued that,

“The attitude of line manager can have a critical role and a wider influence on outcomes for employer’s workload and balance. In the contact centre there is a clear gap and a missing link between management and comfort level of discussing work life balance.”

Apart from the managers, some employees also noted a lack of support from their employers. Respondents explained that,

“employers do not provide any formal support [in Pakistan].”

The lack of support from the employer is translated to the lack of support from the managers. One of the respondents argued that the lack of support options from employers stem from higher unemployment and lack of job options in the market. It was explained that,

“there is so much saturation and instability in job market, that employers get away without providing any privileges to employees. The role of support or lack of it from our employers is the real issue.”

Thus, contact centre work also does not have luxury of employer support in Pakistan. Like line managers and employers, Human resources were also not found to support contact centre employees in Pakistan. Respondents provided that,

“most of the policy making is managed by head of contact centre and human resources have little say in it.”

Lastly, few respondents also complained about the ‘unsupportive’ policies and workplace culture. All of this implies that female employees working in the contact centre industry are deprived of any support from the work agents. Interestingly, no mention of the co-workers was evident in the interviews. One reason might be lack of socialization opportunities in the contact centre as indicated by some respondents. It was mentioned by one respondent that,

“we rarely get time to bond with our co-workers and when we do get some time, we are so tired that we opt to stay quiet”.

Interpretations

It was noted that managerial support is not evident in the work environment of the contact centres in Pakistan. Managers pursue a competitive strategy to ensure that their performance remains good and since the performance is measured on the

quantitative criteria, managers do not consider to extent luxury of support to their employees. Further, it was highlighted no formal HR policy existed in the contact centres of Pakistan, and employees could not seek any support from the HR department or HR manager. Literature highlighted that managers in the contact centre industry use authoritarian approach to enforce targets (Pierre & Tremblay, 2011). They just monitor the progress and ensure conformance to the work standards (Neely et al., 2003). This study shows that women employees were not able to obtain any support from their managers, and managers did not extend any help to support women to better balance their work and life domains. Such lack of support seemed to leave the women employees helpless, without any support and assistance to manage their dual responsibilities, misbalancing their work and life domains.

Overall, a lack of support from every viable work agent and mechanism was evident in contact centre work environment in Pakistan, and women seemed unable to obtain any support from their managers to better manager their work-life balance.

5.2.6 Lower growth prospects

Contact centre female employees have either lower growth opportunities or they are not interested to get promoted, as promotion brings more responsibility and even higher work load.

Firstly, it was noted that many respondents related to lack of growth opportunities in the contact centre work. It was highlighted by many respondents that many qualified people were working in the contact centres for years without any promotion or growth over the years. One of the respondents indicated that,

“There are people and I am talking about highly qualified people who are stuck in customer advisor roles for more than 5 years.”

Apart from the promotion, there are also no opportunities of learning, job rotation, or job enrichment. Some employees indicated that there were no opportunities to move from one department to another. In this context, one respondent indicated that,

“the contact centre sector offers, limited climbing ladders to move to other department and chances of inhouse fame and recognition are non-existent.”

Pertaining to the lack of promotional opportunities, one respondent felt sorry on herself that, she had ‘failed to get promoted’. The same respondent also indicated that her manager is still there after seven years, which strengthens the point that there are not much growth and enrichment opportunities for females in the contact centre industry of Pakistan.

Many respondents also indicated that women do not seek growth in their career in the contact centre work. The reason is that growth or promotion in the contact centre industry brings more work and responsibility, where many female employees deem themselves unsuitable candidate for the promotion. One of the respondents explained this by stating that,

“There are lot of people in contact centre who do not want to progress to other roles within contact centre despite a pay raise. People are afraid of the workload and more hours which is attached with it.”

The line manager interviewed also explained that she was promoted in recognition of the extra work hours.

Interpretations

It was noted that the key to promotion in the contact centre industry is higher workload, whereas promotion also brings more responsibilities and higher workloads, for which many respondents would not be willing. Further, growth prospects in the contact centre seem bleak, where not much growth opportunities exist in the contact

centre work. The key to growth is more and more work, whereas growth and promotion in the contact centre is associated with even more work load and higher work hours. Therefore, many female employees opt not to get promotion in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. Deery and Kinnie (2004) labelled such jobs as 'dead-end', offering few career prospects. There is also an issue of glass ceiling for the women, where women are generally deprived of the growth opportunities. Scholarios and Taylor (2011) explained that women are disadvantaged in the contact centres due to their lower level of human capital and greater household responsibilities. Thus, women working at contact centre industry are deprived of growth, which could give rise to feelings of dissatisfaction with the work and life as well.

5.2.7 Penalizing reward strategy

Contact centre industry in Pakistan has a peculiar reward strategy. Firstly, it should be noted that the contact centre work pays a decent amount of money to its employees. Then there are individual level and team level conformance bonuses. Apart from that employees are also encouraged to sell their un-availed annual leaves for money.

Firstly, base compensation of the employees in the contact centre industry is considered decent and employees seemed satisfied with their salaries. One of the respondent exclaimed her happiness by stating that,

“people are happy with the compensation available.”

Another respondent specified the salary and explained that,

“I work at entry level and earn round Rs. 50,000, which is considered decent money for a women worker at entry level.”

This amount of salary is considered a good salary in Pakistan as most of the entry level jobs pay about half of this salary.

In addition to salary, one of the respondent explained that,

“our job is based around achieving our targets as we can achieve extra 25% of our monthly salary if we can achieve our targets...There is a quarterly and yearly award for people with least number of off days. This makes people come to work even if they are sick and tired of their routines.”

The conformance standards seem quite high in the contact centre industry, where employees can lose their bonus for logging in late or not meeting the quality or quantity standards. One of the respondent explained this noting that,

“our bonus is marked according to quality of our calls and how much time we take to answer calls...Would you believe that a single mistake can cost me my whole monthly bonus.”

It was noted that bonus was used in the contact centre industry to ensure employee attendance. Employees avoid taking days off work and cancel their holidays to ensure their bonus. Then, employer also encourage employees to encash their un-availed holidays. One of the employees explained this phenomenon stating that,

“un-availed holidays can be sold back to the employer and we are paid for them. In my case, I have been selling my holidays back to my employer since I want extra money around new year.”

Apart from the individual bonuses, contact centres also have a system of team bonuses. The team bonus is paid on adherence of whole team to the standards. This puts peer pressure on the employees to adhere to the standards and not take off. One of the respondent explained this stating that,

“there is a team adherence bonus which can only be achieved if everyone comes to work whole month.”

Another respondent explained that team ambers push you to be present at work, even if you are sick. She stated that,

“in contact centre it [absenteeism] is controlled through fear of losing bonus. Even our own team members will push you to continue working in case they find out that you are unwell because nobody wants to lose adherence team bonus.”

Apart from the taking off, little lates or mistakes could also cause erosion of the team bonus. It was explained by one respondent that,

“bonus is given on total adherence of the team so my late login could affect team bonus. At the end of the day, everyone works for money and working in contact centre is a difficult job. Why would you leave home at 3 am to reach office at 6 am and then loose bonus for that day, even if it is not your fault?”

Interpretations

It was noted that base compensation is quite attractive in the call centre industry. On top of the salary, employees are paid conformance bonus on achieving targets. Thus, contact centre industry uses conformance bonus to ensure that employees meet the targets, and also they remain present for the work. Employees in the contact centre industry go extra length to ear bonus and even sell their un-availed holidays to earn some money. This is dilemma for the working class of the developing country, where some extra cash could cause people to ignore their ease and wellbeing. Further, peer pressure is effectively used by the management of the contact centre industry to ensure availability of the staff.

Overall, contact centre industry uses a penalizing reward strategy, which is levered on the adherence bonuses and peer pressure. Employees are encouraged to adhere to the targets and standards to achieve the bonus. They are also encouraged to encash their annual leaves. Thus, financial rewards are used as a bait to ensure that employees remain present in the contact centre and also achieve the targets.

5.2.8 Profiling and pressurizing

Working in the contact centre is a hard job, where managers try to get things done by all means. Compensation and bonus is one tool in this regard, whereas profiling and pressurizing could be another.

It was noted that managers could profile the individuals to identify the people, who could be exploited to work more or work during holidays or odd shifts. This was clearly indicated by one respondent who was divorced. She explained that,

“over the years our line managers come to know us personally and they develop our profiles in their minds...like I am always forced to work on days like Eid or New year and excuse used against me goes like this. You do not have kids or husband, so you can accommodate someone else by covering a day for them. It is like an emotional harassment, where my circumstances are used against me.”

The profiling is not only used to force people into more or additional work, it is also used to label people with certain conditions as ‘unproductive’. One of ex-employee of the contact centre related to her experience during her pregnancy. She explained that,

“my line manager started to make me feel unproductive and useless. I do not know if it was intentionally or unintentionally, but it just kept on getting worse... I was made to feel so useless and rejected, that I opted to resign within 4 months of my pregnancy.”

Same notions were expressed by another employee stating that,

“there is a belief in contact centre that employees without caring or children responsibilities can contribute more towards goals of the organisation.”

Then there is a vicious circle of hard work, where in the start people would appreciate the extra hours and added financial benefits associated with the extra work. However, after sometime when they get tired and try to revert back to normal work hours, manager start thinking that such employees have become lazy or have lost interest in work, and become unproductive. There is a vicious circle of hard work in the contact

centre industry, where hard work leads the manager to assign you more work requiring hard efforts. This was indicated by some respondents like one respondents explained that,

“lot of new girls think that they are getting paid for the extra hours every day, so they are happy to stay extra. By the time they start to feel burnout, it becomes too late as by than their manager thinks that they have lost the interest”.

Another respondent also indicated the same stating that,

“once you get used to this sort of rush [hurrying to do extra work], your manager tries to make it part of your routine and then you are made accountable accordingly.”

Lastly, compensation and bleak prospects of employment elsewhere also empower managers to pressurize individuals into more work. The compensation at the contact is good and not available in ordinary entry level jobs with minimal skill level. According to one of the respondents,

“in contact centre, people are happy with the compensation available...The human resources team and management understand this and use this to their advantage.”

Same notions were repeated by another respondent who highlighted the notions of unavailability of the job in the external market. It was related like that,

“many girls are made to work extra hours as the managers know that with their skill level, it is highly unlikely that they will find another job.”

Further,

“there is abundance of cheap labour”

and any shortcoming in the labour force could be easily filled by hiring young and energetic people, who would work hard till they also start experiencing the stress and burnout.

Interpretations

Managers profile people in accordance with their work patterns. Once someone starts working extra, managers at contact centre expect extra work from that employee, and evaluate the performance accordingly. Further, managers at contact centre industry force employees to work more and work hard as they understand that many employees do not have any other viable option.

Overall, People in the industry seem trapped in the vicious circle of hard work, where hard work in the start leads towards expectations of more hard work in the future. It was nicely summed up by one respondent stating that,

“employers exploit our needs or personal commitments to raise bar of their own operational excellence”.

5.2.9 Employee wellbeing

During the interviews, many respondents talked about employee wellbeing and its related aspects in the contact centre industry. Out of the wellbeing theme, three subthemes emerged i.e. psychological issues, behavioural issues, and physical issues. This section of the analysis relates to the experience of women employees of the contact centre industry pertaining to these three aspects of their well-being.

5.2.9.1 Psychological issues

Respondents talked much about the psychological issues that they were facing due to workload and high pressure work environment. It was noted that female employees at contact centre industry were facing high stress, many were experiencing burnt out, and had negative self-image.

First of all, respondents largely talked about the pressure and stress relating to the work. Respondents connoted to the working in the contact centre industry as ‘working in prison’, being ‘constantly under pressure’, and ‘stress follows you’. One of the respondent explicitly stated that,

“if you are someone who cannot handle stress than I would not recommend you this job.”

Another respondent explained that,

“every single moment at our workplace is micromanaged. This keeps me stressed out around the clock.”

Another respondent argued that,

“Stress is a real thing and even a bigger thing in contact centre.”

It was also argued that excessive work and long working hours were causing stress to the people working in the contact centre industry. Some respondents also saw stress as a management strategy to ensure that everyone works hard. One of the respondents argued that,

“these methods [stress] are used as managerial strategy to get maximum out of us or keep us motivated... We are emotionally abused to perform at our optimum levels all the time.”

There was also indication that constant stress has resulted in the depression for the employees of contact centre. One of the respondents argued that,

“I think too much work stress over a long-term period on consistent basis becomes chronic stress...I just feel that I always have too much to do at work. I am always tired and have no energy...Overall, I have become more depressed.”

There was also indication of the work related burnout, where employees argued that they feel drained all the time. One of the respondent summarized the situation by stating that,

“everyone seems tired, depleted or exhausted.”

Another respondent argued that the nature of work causes burnout to the employees. She explained that,

“no work is easy, but a work should not leave employee anxious, drained, or uninspired.”

It was also argued by some respondents that everyone in the contact centre industry was suffering from the burnout. One respondent raised the point that,

“the employees in contact suffer from burnout without realising it.”

Another blamed the work environment and stated that,

“long hours, zero margin of error, tight deadlines, and ever-increasing demands leave me feeling worried, drained, and overwhelmed every day”

Thus, the work related reasons cause employees to experience burnout as nicely summed up by one respondent, who stated that,

“the routine took all the happiness out of my life and it is reflected in my health as well. I feel burnout and overworked all the time.”

Even managers working in the contact centre industry have some realization of the issues.

The line manager interviewed accepted that,

“unfortunately, issues like burnout are not given any importance in our work culture”.

Lastly, some of the respondents also highlighted a distortion of self-image or self-identity as a result of working in the contact centre. One of the respondent explained that,

“I have started to develop negative psychological identities around my job and my own reflection of myself. This made me feel undervalued or underachiever and slowly but surely, I developed a kind of hatred towards my role as an employee.”

Another employee exclaimed that,

“I feel I have been a failure all my life.”

Another employee explained this feeling in detail by stating that,

“I think I have given up on so many things in my life, my ambitions, my goals, I do not dream any more of becoming something different.”

Interpretations

Considering the responses of the female employees, stress seems an evident feature of the work environment in the contact centre industry of Pakistan, and it has a potential to cause depression for the female employees working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. Such notions have also been endorsed by previous studies, where call centre work was provoking stress among the employees (Khalid et al., 2013; Lin et al., 2010; Visser & Rothman, 2008), which could lead to spill over of the stress to other domains of life, or could cause employee turnover (Modau et al., 2018; Van Rensburg et al., 2013). Over the time, employees working in the contact centre industry could, “feel powerless and displays of low morale and frustration”. Overall, employees working in the contact centre industry exhibit psychological issues relating to stress, depression, burnout, and self-worth

5.2.9.2 Behavioural Issues

Apart from the psychological issues, some respondents also related to the behavioural issue as a consequence to the work routine. They argued that they remain angry and frustrated, and also feel withdrawn from the world around them.

Firstly, pertaining to the anger, respondents explained that they have started feeling angry with everything. One of the respondents argued that,

“I seem to have problem with everything whether it is management, workload, travelling, literally everything. There seems to be a hidden anger inside me for not getting I deserve, or I am capable of.”

Another respondent acknowledged having ‘temperamental issues due to excess workload’. Another respondent explained the issue in detail and provided that,

“I am always very tired and angry... my parents are always making jokes of me that I cannot stand anyone. My younger brother thinks I have become this character from games ‘angry bird’. I do not have patience for anything anymore. I literally start shouting for very minor occurrences.”

One of the respondent also quoted having ‘mood swings’ in this regard.

There was also some indication that people working in the call centre industry become withdrawn over the time. This could cause people to behave in antisocial manner. One of the respondent explained this behaviour stating that,

“I generally stay quiet in team meetings and prefer not to take part in any group work or presentation. I always liked attention and limelight, which pushed me to become a better player as well. Look at me now, my outlook is more of a retired coach than a retired player. All these things really make me angry and sick”.

Interpretations

It was noted that call centre work could affect behaviour and emotions of employee in a considerable manner. Overall, contact centre work has been indicated to cause behavioural issues including being angry all the time and exhibit anti-social behaviour. In this regard, Groth and Grandey (2012) explained that call centre employees have to deal with angry and frustrated customers, which could lead towards emotional exhaustion and tendency to become aggressive (Grandey et al., 2004; Goussinsky, 2012). Such aggression could spill over to other life domains of the life and distort affairs in other life domains.

5.2.9.3 Physical issues

Apart from psychological and behavioural issues, many respondents indicated physical consequences of the contact centre job. Contact centre job is a repetitive nature of work, where one has to sit on the chair and communicate with the clients

over the phone or computer. Many respondents highlighted that they were experiencing mental as well as physical health problems due to their work. It was also highlighted by the employees that the health consequences materialize over the time.

Like one of the respondents indicated that,

“over the time that my health has suffered dramatically”.

Another employee related that,

“one thing which employees realise only leaving the company is the potential long-term negative effects on their health.”

Likewise, another employee raised the concern that,

“here is an alarmingly high percentage of colleagues who feel that work is the causing them health problems... people tend to stick to their roles for long time without realising its long term effects on their mental and physical health.”.

Contact centre work requires the workers to sit on a chair during long working hours and answer the phone calls one after another, with no or minimal breaks. This could cause posture issues for the employees, resulting in muscle stiffness or back pains.

One of the employee explained the issue in detail by stating that,

“After sitting in same posture for 10 hours or more, once I finally decide to get up, I feel like my body will break into pieces. Along with that, I cannot take off my head set, even there are no calls in que. Sitting in one posture makes my muscles stiff. I have worked here for only one year, but my neck and back muscles are already affected, and it will get worse over the time.”

Another employee also highlighted the issue of ‘body ache’ due to ‘insane work schedule’. These notions imply that employees at the contact centre are under real risk of having physical issues relating to muscle stiffness and posture related pains.

Subsequently, some respondents also highlighted issues pertaining to high blood pressure and anxiety due to the work routine at the contact centre industry. Notions like 'anxiety has taken central stage', and 'high blood pressure' were highlighted in relation to the health issues by some respondents, indicating that employees at contact centre industry could suffer from these health related issues, where these issues might be consequence of work stress and related routines.

Apart from the blood pressure, there were some concerns pertaining to the sleep of the respondents, where respondents expressed a decline in the quality of sleep or insomnia. One of the respondent indicated that, "demand of work has greatly affected quality of my sleep", while another expressed that,

"I have also noticed that lack of good sleep in these days also impacts my memory".

There were some indications that long work hours were causing the employees to cut their sleep, whereas some had voiced that they were suffering from insomnia. It was noted that sleep issue was the most prominent issue highlighted under health issues. Contact centre work requires the worker to wear head gear all the time, and talk a lot to, sometime disgruntled, customers. One of the employees raised this issue that,

"working in contact centre can cause hearing issues in the long term, since you must use head gear almost 10 hours a day."

Another respondent also highlighted that they cannot take off head gear and relax, even if there are no calls in the que. Although, the hearing issues was not much highlighted, the work in the contact centre could cause the hearing issues to some employees in the long run.

Lastly, some respondents highlighted issues pertaining to digestion and obesity. One of the respondents highlighted that,

"recently, lack of sleep has influenced my digestive system in a negative manner."

Other have highlighted that due to lack of physical activity, they were gaining weight and becoming obese. One of the respondents in this regard explained that,

“I have also put-on a lot of weight as I do not have any time for exercise...I have also developed love for unhealthy diet and sometimes I do binge eating as well.”

One of the respondents also related to ‘stress eating’ in this connection. Thus, eating disorder related issues could raise health concerns for the employees working the contact centre industry of Pakistan.

Interpretations

Many respondents raised concerns on the health related issues and explained that they were suffering due to their work in contact centre industry. They further highlighted sleep issues, posture related pains and muscle stiffness, blood pressure and anxiety, and eating disorders in relation to their work in the contact centre. Previously, research noted sleep related issues among employees in the contact centre industry (Marinache, 2016; Raja & Bhain, 2016; Rawat et al., 2016; Suri et al., 2007). Likewise, another stream of studies highlighted posture and muscle pain related issues of contact centre workers (Amit & Song, 2021; Constancio et al., 2012; Toomingas & Gavhed, 2008). Thus, call center work could cause physical issues to the employees, which could lead to hamper the ability of such employees to function effectively in other life domains.

5.2.10 Women – work mismatch

It was also noted that women have specific physical and social needs or responsibilities, which hinder their ability to keep up with workload and long work hours requirements. The issues that were found in this regard were related to maternity, where women might require certain level of relaxation; family related responsibilities, dragging women towards household chores; hormonal issues,

making women uneasy at certain time of month; and communication gap with the male managers, as in Pakistani society females feel discomfort discussing their issues with males.

First and foremost issue creating difficulty for women to manage contact centre work is relating to their maternity and related relaxations during pregnancy. Women planning to have kids are not considered a good fit for the contact centre work and are not hired. One of the respondent shared her experience with the job interview where she was asked if she was “expecting any career interruption after joining work”. These questions are indirectly related to assess whether the women candidate is planning to get married or have a baby in near future. Another respondent explained that,

“recently one of my reference was not hired as she said in her interview that she is planning to have a kid.”

This would require call centre to allow her maternity leave, which the management cannot afford. It was also noted that women are made to feel ‘unproductive and useless’, after they get pregnant. One of respondent had to resign after being pregnant for the unfair treatment. Another respondent also related to her experience during the pregnancy, where she suffered from morning sickness and had to take extra breaks due to increase urination. She had to take unscheduled breaks, and her team bonus was compromised because of her. Such issues deem women a poor fit for the contact centre jobs, as there is no additional support available to the women undergoing pregnancy or maternity issues.

The second issues was related to the marriage and household responsibilities. First, women are expected to get married in Pakistani society at the earliest possible time and it was noted that many women employee resign after their marriage, as they are unable to keep up with the job after the marriage. This is well known in the contact

centre as one of the respondent explained her experience with discussing of marriage prospects to the manager, who

“just smiled and told [her] to sit at home, enjoy marriage, and raise kids.”

Thus, these notions that a women have to get married, and after marriage women have to take-up household responsibilities and undergo pregnancy. Considering the no leave policy of the contact centre industry, women become a poor fit for the job. Apart from getting marriage, women run the household in a typical Pakistani family. As the line manager explained that,

“our culture does not bound them [males employees] to certain responsibilities as compared to women.”

So, women face difficulty in managing two full time responsibilities.

Third is hormonal issue, where women experience discomfort and sometimes pain during their menstrual period. In Pakistani culture, women avoid such topics. Further, there is no relaxation for women undergoing their hormonal period. Few respondents highlighted that the job becomes more challenging during the ‘periods’. One of the respondent explained in detail that,

“there are numerous occasions where we as a woman must face embarrassment on the topic of ‘period’. I remember one of employees resigned as she was questioned on her unusual prolong breaks on period. Imagine being asked by a male manager whether your periods pains are real? There are many line managers who would jokingly comment about thinking twice before hiring a female employee in contact centre due to ‘their’ special needs.”

Thus, women may have special physical needs, which are not accommodated in usual sphere of contact centre operations.

Lastly, women employees in the contact centre may feel discomfort while sharing and communicating their issues with male managers. One of the respondents in this regard explained that,

“A large number of female employees will prefer not to discuss their problems with male managers. You can call it as cultural thing and there are not many women in leading roles in contact centre... it is also quite common to see women being unable to express physical and mental issues to their [male] line managers. It is even a bigger case, especially when it comes to gynaecological conditions and you have a male manager.”

This is well known phenomenon in Pakistan culture. Even the female line manager also understood this and explained this phenomenon in detail. She stated that,

“I guess the female employees find it easier to engage with female managers... I might be able to discuss their personal issues, maternity issues and all such issues which are important to them. In our society we do not expect male bosses to interfere with matrimonial issues etc...I can share my experiences with them as regard to marriage and then birth related challenges which could make them comfortable.”

Despite the ease of women to engage with women manger, most of the managers in the contact centre industry are men. This creates a dilemma for the female employees, who avoid discussion of their issues with the manager and seek related support. Presence of male manager could create problems for the female employees, making the job less lucrative for the females in conservative society of Pakistan.

Interpretations

Overall, it could be argued that women may need special consideration due to their special physical and social needs. They might get married, become pregnant, and undergo maternity time. These different phases of women life require different kind of

support for women. In this regard, Staritz and Reis (2013) noted that contact centers lack policies relating to maternity leave and child support, making it difficult for married women, pregnant women, and mothers to manage their job with household and caregiving responsibilities. Thus, ordinary contact center jobs become difficult for women with household and children-related responsibilities. All of this could cause contact center employers to deem women unsuitable for the job, requiring long work hours and no leave from work.

5.2.11 Patriarchal culture

Pakistan is a male dominant society with strong patriarchal underpinnings. Respondents highlighted that women have to abide by the societal considerations of male dominance along with pressures from family and society. Further, women are also expected to perform household responsibilities on top of their job. This makes it difficult for the women to manage both roles: job and household.

Firstly, male dominance is a central theme of a patriarchal culture. Women are considered a subservient group in Pakistani society. Women also have a protected status in the society. Considering this status, women employees are provided transport services by the contact center. Despite this, most women work under male managers. It was noted by one respondent that,

“female teams are considered tougher to handle and therefore mostly we are allocated male managers.”

Males are deemed a directional force in the society, and also in the contact center industry. Thus, there are lower numbers of female managers in the contact center industry, while the workplace is mostly dominated by the male managers. Thus, male dominance is pervasive not only in the contact center industry, but in the overall society of Pakistan to a larger extent.

One of the most important aspect of a patriarchal society is that males in the family – father or husband takes the central role and makes all the decisions for females. Females need to seek approval of the males, who levy certain restrictions on working women. Like one of the respondents explained that,

“I cannot work in evening shifts as I am a woman and I have safety and security issue... acceptance of status must firstly be given by my family members as they should not question my evening shifts.”

Thus, women need to seek approval from the family to join an odd work shift. Another respondent explained that,

“in many families, women do not have an opinion in anything and same mindset is carried at workplace as well.”

Therefore, women might not be included in the decision making in family and at workplace as well, barring women to progress, fell empowered, and make their own decisions. In traditional cultures like Pakistan, women are allowed to work after assurance that the work environment is safe and constrained. One of the respondent explained this in detail stating that,

“our parents would want us to work, but in a bubble, where nobody can see us or touch us. It does not matter whether work conditions are like a jail. Then once you get married, same mindset is adopted by your husband, who would want you to work in similar jail like conditions.”

Thus, an influence of males remain on the women working in the contact centre industry. These women cannot start job without permission of family head, and also can not resign without the approval. This makes work secondary to the women, and many women would leave the work after marriage as their husbands would not like them to work anymore.

Apart from the family pressure, women also face pressure from the society. Society judges women on patriarchal strands, where non-conformance to the societal norms could damage reputation of woman and her family in the society. One of the respondent explained that,

“Leaving home at 3 am/4am for early morning shifts has made me infamous in my street. People think I am doing a strange sort of job and therefore I must leave so early... I have no doubt that if men leave that early for work, society will celebrate him for his hard work or sacrifices made for his family... our society still looks at women through a male lens”.

Another respondent also told the same story,

“she [contact centre employee] must show up at work 5:00 am in the morning. She might be supporting her husband, but will the society or her neighbours would understand that?”

Thus, working women face unnecessary pressure from the society due to their work, where the odd shift of contact centre makes the pressure more severe for women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan.

Lastly, women are expected to perform household roles. This stigma is always associated with the women, and people at work expect peculiar things from the women. Like one of the respondent highlighted that,

“early morning shifts we have in contact centre are only reserved for female employees. This is based on the stereotype that women get up early anyway to take care of their house chores”.

Then there is an issue that people think that working women are using the job as an excuse to avoid household work. This was explained by one respondent, who related that,

“she [her aunt] thinks that I am using this [job] to run away from responsibilities of a women, who had to stay at home and do house chores... this is exactly how our society looks at working women.”

The household roles of the women are that much fixated in the mind of people that, “employees in contact centre are more likely to subconsciously associate male managers with career progress and women managers with family and work life balance issues”.

Thus, work side of the women is greatly influenced by the notions that women have family issues, and their job is always a second priority for them.

Interpretations

Overall, patriarchy is very much alive in countries like Pakistan (Hadi, 2017), where working women have to face pressure from family and from society. Moreover, they are always stigmatized to carry the burden of household responsibilities (Tabassum, 2016), which could influence their outlook towards work, and also their image in the eyes of the management. Therefore, women in Pakistan would always prioritize their house hold responsibilities over the work (Omar et al., 2004) to fulfil their social role. The patriarchal nature of the society, itself hinders the ability of the women to maintain a work-life balance. Women are expected to discharge their household responsibilities, over and above their work related responsibilities, leaving little personal time at their disposal. Thus, it is very difficult in a patriarchal society to maintain work-life balance .

5.2.12 Discrimination

Discrimination is a regular phenomenon all around the world, where women are discriminated against men. Same is the case in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. Respondents complained that women are considered weak and inefficient,

whereas married or pregnant women are considered even more inefficient in the work settings of contact centre industry. Respondents also noted that women are less paid, have lower growth opportunities, and have lower privileges and facilities compared to their male counterparts.

Considering the notions of women are weak and inefficient. Many respondents noted that women are considered inefficient. One of the respondent explained these notions in detail by saying that,

“it is an age-old convention that women are less capable and inefficient in working as compared to men and contact centres seem to be a prime example of this... [where] working women are made to feel that they must do better all the times than their male colleagues.”

Such labelling of women as incapable and inefficient makes them push harder to prove their worth, causing stress and other work related issues. Women are also considered weaker gender. One respondent explained that she tried to explained his issues to his supervisors, but

“he [manager] thinks women are weaker gender and that is why they seem to label everything to stress and depression”.

Another respondents reaffirmed the point by highlighting that,

“men are considered strong and are free to take lot of decision.”

Thus, women are discriminated against men and are considered less capable and efficient. They are labelled as weak and are pushed harder to compete with men.

In addition to being women, being married or being pregnant is also penalized in the contact centre industry. Married or pregnant women are considered more inefficient.

One respondent explained that,

“as a married woman I am a prime victim of gender bias at workplace.”

One of the respondent related to her experience of discussing with manager about her marriage, who encouraged her to resign and raise kids, instead of doing a job.

Another respondent highlighted

“unfair treatment at work once you get married or pregnant.”

Another respondent related to the experience of being pregnant and explained that,

“there are real challenges around pregnancy and working with male managers, especially if he is not married... My line manager started to make me feel unproductive and useless. I do not know if it was intentionally or unintentionally, but it just kept on getting worse.”

Thus, getting married or being pregnant is considered unproductive in the contact centre industry, as both of these events divert attention of women from work to family related responsibilities.

Some respondents also highlighted that their male colleagues were being paid more and also are promoted more often. It was highlighted by one respondent that, all promotions within contact centre seem to go to male colleagues. Another respondent provided a detailed description of the issues and stated that,

“I am paid less as compared to my male colleagues. I am scheduled on such campaigns where there are less chances of bonus and it is same for my female colleagues as well”.

This indicates that women are systematically allocated to less productive or low earning tasks, whereas males get all the bonus related tasks. This was explained by the line manager, who argued that,

“employees in contact centre are more likely to subconsciously associate male managers with career progress and women managers with family”.

Thus, male may get more promotions, while women are left out to deal with their family.

Lastly, few respondents also explained that men at contact centre work get more privileges and facilities. Like one of the respondents related that,

“people [males] have been given laptops to work from home. I am sure reason will be like that male employees can take better of laptops at home. Whereas women might spill water on them or our kids at home might do somethings with the laptop”.

This implies that males may be trusted more to take care of technical equipment.

Apart from that, another respondent noted that,

“there is a male cricket team in contact centre, and they are given off time from time to time to represent the company”.

There was not female team for any sports, neither they were given any time off for any sports. The only privilege obtained by women is free transport facility, they should not ask for anything more.

Interpretations

Overall, it was found that women were discriminated against men, where they are deemed unproductive and ineffective. In this regard, Banerjee et al. (2009) noted presence of gender discrimination in the contact centre industry. Further, gender discrimination is a regular issue in normal work settings (Esteve-Volart, 2004; Pudnery & Shields, 2000; Russen et al., 2021). Further, women were also found to receive lower compensation and are less likely to be promoted. Lastly, males in the contact centre industry obtain more privileges and facilities compared to women. Thus, ordinary women face discriminating in the contact centre industry of Pakistan.

5.2.13 Lower work motivation and job satisfaction

Last theme pertaining to work in the contact centre industry was lower levels of work motivation and job satisfaction. Pertaining to the motivation it was highlighted by one of the respondents, who noted that

“motivation starts to diminish with passage of time”.

Another employee explained that,

“employees feel leftover and motivation and satisfaction levels drop”.

Thus, lack of motivation is an evident factor in working women of contact centre industry of Pakistan.

Apart from the motivation, respondents also expressed discontent with their jobs. The notions of happiness was repeated often. Like one of the respondents indicated that,

“if you hate what you do, you are not going to be happy”.

Same notions of disinterest were expressed by another respondent, who told that,

“I feel like dragging myself every day to the work. There is not a single day or even an hour when I am happy at work.”

Another employee concluded that,

“current approach followed by managers is killing employee morale and satisfaction levels.”

Interpretation

Overall, a lower level of work motivation and job satisfaction was evident in the jobs of contact centre industry. Considering the strife nature of the job, lack of support, lower flexibility, higher monitoring, and dissimulation; women working in the contact center industry feel a lot of pressure, which ultimately leads to the higher burden and lower work satisfaction (Dhanpat et al., 2018; Hooff & van Hooff, 2016; Zielińska, 2019).

Therefore, it has been noted that turnover intention of contact centre workers are quite high (Van Dyk et al., 2013).

5.3 The life

After the work domain, women employees of the contact centre industry also related to various aspects of their life. The most repeated aspect of their life was either family

or things related to their family, whereas other aspects like time for self, entertainment or leisure activities, sports or exercise, hobbies and interests, health, education, friends, and social events were also highlighted by some respondents. With regard to the domain of family, some aspects highlighted were performing household chores, giving time to family, expanding the family or pregnancy, and getting married. Following discussion relates to abovementioned 'life' aspects of women employees of contact centre of Pakistan.

5.3.1 The family

Women interviewed related to their lived experiences in context of their family. It was noted that scope of family for women in Pakistani society is very broad, where family include kids, husband, parents, in-laws, and older dependants. In social settings of Pakistan, family have broad connotations, particularly for the women. Pakistani society is based on the notions of joint family system, where after marriage, family of husband is deemed family of the wife. This was also indicated by the respondents. One of the respondents indicated that,

“I am not only responsible for primary care of my children, but also extended family of my husband.”

Thus, women are seen as a caregiver to all of the family members including their children, husbands, and elderly in the family as indicated by one respondent, who stated that

“women are considered as the sole caretakers of husband, children and older dependents.”

This makes life of women a quest, where they need to prove themselves

“as great daughters, perfect wives, with children as top priority.”

This puts extra strain on the working women. Considering the life domain, respondents talked a lot about their family and related aspects. Three aspects were highlighted by the respondents in this regard i.e. performing household chores and caregiving responsibilities, giving time to children and family, and after marriage life and extending family by giving birth to child.

First family aspect for women working in the contact centre industry was related to their responsibilities as 'family manager' or 'caregiver', and this is all in addition to their jobs. One of the respondents explained that,

“women in Pakistan are still viewed as the family manager and are expected to return to the home at a certain time, and need to engage themselves in cooking, cleaning, and taking care of family affairs.”

Another respondent explained the duality of the roles and iterated that,

“mostly, in Pakistan, women must perform dual roles in the family one is [as house manager] as cook, house cleaner, the dish and clothes washer; and second is [as caregiver] caring for the child and husband.”

All the house chores like cooking, cleaning, and cloths are deemed responsibility of the women. Considering the caregiving, women in Pakistan are supposed to take care of all family members including their children, husband, extended family of husband side, and elderly at home. One of the respondent included caregiving in the domestic responsibilities of women stating that,

“women are still primarily responsible for domestic responsibilities such as elder and dependent care and childcare as well. Caring for their children, husband and his parents and the extended family are traditional obligations which are deeply embedded in society and the culture on a larger scale”.

Even the unmarried women are also expected to take part in the household chores.

One of the unmarried respondent added that,

“I am not married yet, but I am supposed to take care of my parents and do lot of house chores.”

These household responsibilities along with the job become difficult for the women to manage. One of the respondent clearly explained this by stating that,

“working women in our part of the world are often confronted with tasks of juggling between children, home, in-laws, parents and their social circle.”

Samee notions were provided by another respondent, who related to the situation of other married women in the contact centre industry and noted that,

“many women colleagues around me must juggle between their family and children and end up completely ignoring their own health.”

Second aspect related to the family was spending time with the family. Respondents related it to a ‘struggle’, where women in the contact centre industry

“struggle to find time for myself and for my family”.

There was also an indication that respondents were unable to spend time with their family during festivals or holidays. One of the respondent indicated that,

“it is the special days like Eid or Ramadan where I miss them [parents], or they miss me”.

Another respondent also indicated that,

“Eid or Independence Day holidays are the few days where everyone is at home and one would like to spend time with them [family]”.

Apart from these special days, women working in the contact centre industry feel guilty of not giving time to their family, particularly their kids and husband. One of the respondents explained that,

“imagine how difficult it is for married worker as she cannot send her kids to school or send husband to work as she is leaving for work earlier than them”.

A struggle was evident to allocate time to the family members as well. Like it was explained that,

“I can go home and do house chores or play with kids. As a result, my husband gets extremely limited attention from me. Also, I rarely get time to speak with my in-laws, which has created an uneasy atmosphere at home.”

This indicates that women constantly are in a struggle to allocate time to their family members, where giving more time to kids could reduce time allocation to the husband, in-laws, or parents. Spending time with kids was found to be most important or emotional aspect of this theme. In this regard, One of struggling mother exclaimed that,

“I feel like I have missed his [son] childhood memories. I leave home early so all his morning routines are done by my mother-in-law. I reach home around 18:00 hours, and then mostly he is asleep. I feel a guilt that I have failed to do my job as a mother...I only want enough time to spend with my kid and my husband.”

Another divorcee working mother also highlighted the same and explained that,

“my son is 8 years old and goes to the school, but I am unable to give him the time he deserves...I am missing out my time with my son. He does not have a father, so I need to play a dual role.”

Third and last element of family aspect was related to the married life. In Pakistan, women are expected to get married as early as possible. After marriage, not only household responsibilities of women increase, but also they face an expectation to become mother as early as possible. Both of these notions are endorsed by the respondents. One respondent highlighted that,

“marriage is inevitable, and it is followed by motherhood.”

Getting married and giving birth could have severe implications for both work and life domains of working women in contact center industry of Pakistan. One of the respondent indicated that,

“my husband is putting extra pressure on me to expand our family, which further adds to my frustrations ...I would have to give up my job to give birth to another kid. But my husband wants me to continue working, so this means I would have to sacrifice more...it leads to unfair treatment at work once you get married or pregnant”.

Thus, marriage or getting pregnant are not favoured options in contact centre work environment. Managing both work and life after marriage or childbirth becomes quite difficult, and one respondent indicated that,

“I had to resign after my daughter was born as I was unable to manage work and home at same time.”

There were indication of a discouraging behaviour of the employer after women employees get married or undergo child birth. In this context, one respondent highlighted that,

“employers also see this link and make it hard for employees to settle in after major life changing events like marriage or birth of children”.

Interpretations

It was noted that working women in Pakistan are also expected to manage the household and take care for their family, in addition to their job related responsibilities, making it difficult for them to manage both at the same time. In this regard, Itrat et al. (2007) and Noor et al. (2021) explained implications of joint family system, where women are expected to take care of the whole family. In the society, men take up financial responsibilities, while women are charged with household management and

care giving responsibilities (Tabassum, 2016). Therefore, economic or financial role of women in Pakistani society becomes secondary in the favour of their household role (Omar et al., 2004). In this context, women who opt to do a job have to juggle between family and job related responsibilities, making it difficult for them to balance their work and life domains.

Further, family aspect of the life domain of women working in the contact centre has an element of 'spending time with family', where spending time with the kids had emotional connotations. In this regard, Siddiqui (2005) explained that in addition to the job roles, women have to perform household chores, which takes a toll on their leisure time, that could be spent with their family. Yerkes et al. (2020) also highlighted multiplicity of the roles of women, making them sacrifice their leisure time. This implies that family domain of working women in countries like Pakistan is divided into two spheres; one related to family chores, and other spending leisure time with the family. James et al. (2016) also noted that involvement in the multiple roles could distort the quality of time allocated to family and community.

Lastly, findings highlight that life domain of women has aspects of marriage and child birth, which are life changing events, and make work-life paradigm more difficult for the women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan. These aspect also relate to the family domain women, where changes in the family aspect change the whole life of the women. Staritz and Reis (2013) highlighted that contact center do not support women during their pregnancy, child birth, and child care tenures. Therefore, women working in the contact center industry could face more responsibilities and pressure during and after these life changing events.

5.3.2 The self

Apart from the family aspect of the life domain, the other most prominent aspect was themed as the self-aspect of life. This aspect had elements of time for self, entertainment or leisure activities, sports or exercise or caring for self-health, education, and hobbies or interest element. Following discussion relates to these elements in detail.

Firstly, many respondents related to their inability to find time for themselves. Respondents indicated notions like, 'I am left with no time for myself', 'difficult to relax in my own time', and 'do not know what is going on in my personal life?'. Many respondents seemed to be dissatisfied with the unavailability of the self-time, which according to them could cause issues with personal and psychological well-being. One of the respondents explained that,

"I struggle to find time for myself and for my family...This results in neglect of my personal life and could lead to health and mental issues."

Respondents blamed work routine and lack of support from the work in this connection. One respondents elaborated that,

"I am too preoccupied with my work and preparation of work to consider personal time and leisure activities."

Likewise, another respondent highlighted the role of the employer in this regard stating that,

"People are made to resign for asking for parental leave and time off for dependants... There is little space for self-care here."

Within this personal time element, one respondent also argued that she was unable to perform her personal chores at home. She explained that,

"I am working fifty hours a week in a job that barely enables me to wash my clothes myself."

After the self-time element, respondents indicated a need for the entertainment or leisure activities in their life domain. The notions of 'picnic', 'sabbatical', 'holiday planning', 'going to cinema' came up in this connection. Respondents complained on being preoccupied and having short of time to consider any entertainment or leisure time activities. In this regard, one of the respondents highlighted that,

"I am too preoccupied with my work and preparation to work to consider personal time and leisure activities".

Likewise, another respondent related to the difficulty of planning some entertainment or leisure activity. She stated that,

"I would like to have time to go to cinema once or twice in a month but even planning such outing seem to be a herculean task."

Another respondent talked about picnic, while relating to the leisure time activities. She highlighted that,

"some people would want to bond with their family members or go to picnic".

Lastly, another respondent noted that women working in the contact centre industry require some leisure activity after a hectic work day. She made her case by arguing that,

"many may be able to unwind after a hectic workday simply by reading, practicing yoga, or taking a bath or shower and doing things that they would like to do".

Apart from the entertainment and sports activities, respondents in the contact centre industry also indicated towards sports, exercise, and their health. One of the respondent was wary on the discrimination that males were provided sports opportunities, but not the females. She explained that,

"There is a male cricket team in contact centre, and they are given off time from time to time to represent the company. Why is not there a female team?"

Another respondent indicated that she,

“used to be a good table tennis player and had won a gold medal in national games for my district as well”.

Apart from the sports, some women respondents also indicated about exercise. One of the respondent explained about her inability to have time for exercises stating that,

“I cannot exercise anymore because I have no time and it makes me feel guilty specifically stress and lack of exercise”.

Another respondent related to the ‘practicing yoga’ to deal with her stress. Further, there was also indication that some respondents considered exercising in gym is a part and parcel. Respondents also pledged to ‘go for a walk’, ‘focus on health and exercise routines. Likewise, there was an indication that women respondents ignore their health. Therefore one respondent suggested,

“if they [employer] are not worried about my health and well-being than why should I put my personal life and health on risk”.

Next was the element of education, which was related to by the young and unmarried respondents, who were pursuing their education along with their job. One respondent indicated that she did her MBA in the evening classes to keep up with job and education. Likewise, another respondent highlighted that she was unable to do some coding course due to job timings. Another respondent related to this and explained that,

“I do struggle to keep up with the pace and requirements of my study. Therefore, I have opted for part time ACCA instead of full-time classes”.

Lastly, few respondents also related to the hobbies and interests, and lack of time for these. It was indicated that,

“every women employee would like time for ... pursuing their hobbies like music.”

Another respondent indicated that work,

“also took away any possibility of engaging in hobbies and enjoy what life had to offer?”

It was stressed that the contact centre work provided women,

“little or no space for their own self to pursue their personal interests.”

Another respondent also related to her dream ‘ to become a fashion designer’.

Interpretations

There is an indication that women working in the contact centre industry are unable to find personal time for relaxation and for doing self-chores. This is consistent with the notions provided by previous studies. Siddiqui (2005) and Pundery an Shields (2000) noted that women are deprived of leisure time due to family and work related responsibilities. Miller and Brown (2005) also noted that leisure time remains at the last priority of women, who first allocate time to their work and family related responsibilities, and adjust their leisure time accordingly.

There was an indication that women in the contact centre industry of Pakistan consider leisure or entertainment activities as a viable aspect of their life domain. Further, sports, exercise, focusing on health were deemed important elements of the life domain of the women working in the contact industry of Pakistan. Furthermore, education was also viable element of life domain, but it may be related more to the young and unmarried women. Lastly, hobbies and interests were also deemed important element of self-aspect of the life domain. However, deprivation of the leisure time and social norms restrict ability of women to meaningfully involve in these activities. For example, Lit et al. (2015) noted that women in Pakistan are less likely to exercise and involve in physical activities due to social norms and household responsibilities. Likewise, James et al. (2016) noted that work patterns in the contact centre industry could distort quality and quantity of leisure activities of the employees.

Thus, women working in the contact centre industry seemed deprived of self or leisure time to manage their personal or leisure activities.

5.3.3 Social circle

Lastly, Very few respondents related to the social aspect of their life domain. There were few indications of social relationships apart from the family and fewer on the social interactions apart from the essential ones like during some events i.e. marriage, deaths, etc. One of the respondent related to her lack of social life by stating that,

“I think I have not made any new friends since I have started working...Thinking about it, I see my laptop or phone more often for work than for my friends for sure. My bedroom is ... like a hub of technology which keeps me connected with work instead of friends.”

The other indications of friends was mostly in terms of ‘having no friends’, ‘juggling with family and friends’, or lack of understanding from friends, who thought that ‘my [respondent’s] complaints [about work] are vague.

Interpretations

Overall, social aspect of the life domain seem to be underrepresented in the life of women employees of contact centre industry. In Pakistani society, women have less friends and more family related obligations. Much of the life of women is concentrated on their family, whereas they seem to lack time for self and for their friends and other social activities. Previous studies also highlight the same where social life of women in Pakistan was deemed confined to the a small group, mostly from their own family (Safdar & Ghani, 2018). It was also highlighted by Masood (2018) that women face mobility restrictions in Pakistan, which restrict their ability to maintain social interactions. The relocation process after marriage further distorts the ability of women to build and maintain social relationships (Habiba et al., 2016), as after marriage

women shift at husband's place, making it difficult for them to connect and socialize with pre-marriage contacts. With reference to the contact centre workers as well, James et al. (2016) and Patel (2006) noted a deterioration of social life of contact centre employees over the time. Thus, social life seemed a least priority for women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan.

5.4 Work-Life interaction

Much of the work and life domains of female employees of contact centre industry of Pakistan highlight that work domain is characterized by high workloads, lack of flexibility, monotonous nature of job, long working hours, lower growth and managerial support, less focus on employee wellbeing, and discrimination against women. On the other hand, the life domain represented family, self, and social circle. Interestingly, family had higher relevance to the life domain, where women were expected to manage the household and take care of the family members. The self-domain contained work for self, education, entertainment and leisure, and hobbies and interest; whereas social circle domain was underrepresented in the responses. The respondents related to a struggle to keep up with the demands of work and life domains. Firstly, respondents recognized there was no border or boundary between work and life domain, after that they related to the notions of work-life conflict and indication of a negative spill over, mostly from work domain to the life domain. This part of the analysis relates to the work life interaction in this regard, where themes are organized in accordance with the available theories on work-life balance. Firstly, revelations relating to the border theory are discussed, and after that relevance of the conflict theory is discussed with the help of data, and lastly, evidence pertaining to the spill over theory is elaborated.

5.4.1 Boundary and border between work- life domains

Boundary theory propagates a clear distinction between work and life domains to avoid inter-domain conflicts. Considering the responses of the respondents, it was noted that female employees working in the contact centre industry were unable to establish any form of boundary or border. There were visible indications that respondents were unable to 'draw line between work and life'. One of the respondent explained her effort to create temporal boundaries divided in time and explained,

"I tried dividing work life in to equal 12 hours shift, with 12 hours going to professional life, and 12 hours to personal life. But I found that there is no magic formula to unlock this."

Another respondent also related to this by stating that,

"I am working on separating work pressures and education pressures in order to cope with them in a better manner."

One respondent elaborated that, "the nature of job requires employees to be updated all the time; the better updated you are, you will do better on the monthly bonus. This tendency forces employees in contact centre to avoid engaging in the home life. Many employees increasingly feel that they must be constantly available to work in order to demonstrate their devotion in front of line manager". Thus, women employees at the contact centre industry seemed unable to setup viable boundaries between work and life domains.

Information technology integration with the work and life has also made it more difficult create the boundaries between work and life domains. Many respondents indicated the need to remain digitally available, even from their homes. It was highlighted by one respondent that,

"Employees working in contact centre are always connected with their work at home 24/7 via mobile phones and laptops".

Employees also indicated that contact centres have provided employees mobile phones and other digital devices to ensure their digital availability. One of the respondents related to this by stating that,

“one must carry out the work from home as well. The company has provided phone connections along with free Wi-Fi devices to the employees, and in return they expect employees to remain available 24/7”.

Another respondent related to the need to remain updated with the new information and packages and explained that,

“working in contact centre is all about having latest knowledge of the products so you can serve the customer with best possible information. This means that you very often must be attentive to emails after your work hours”.

Thus, the technology causes employees to remain connected to their work. All of this urge to connect to the work from home was explained in detail by one respondent, who noted that,

“I am always short of time for myself ... I see my laptop or phone more often than my friends. My bedroom is not a place for relaxation and fun, it is like a hub of technology, which keeps me connected to the work instead of friends... We need to establish work boundaries, as it feels that we are always at work. I know technology does help staff stay up to date on everything, but it makes our life miserable as well. In a 24/7, always-on era, I am always tempted to check what is happening at work. There must be some way to stop this constant work temptation”.

Interpretations

Overall female employees working in the contact centre industry were unable to establish temporal or physical boundaries between work and life domains, where work

domain was found to intervening in the life domain. Moreover, technological integration has made it more difficult for the employees to remain separated from work, while at home. Despite a visible effort from some respondents, the boundary creation mechanism could not support any viable work-life balance. One of the reason explained in this regard was 24/7 culture, where employees were expected to remain available 24/7. Modern work practices have evolved (Kamp et al., 2011) and information technology integration into work routines has made it difficult to establish temporal or physical boundaries between work and non-work life (Field & Chan, 2018). Segers et al. (2008) specifically highlighted the nature of contact centre work to deem it boundary less by default. Thus, modern IT interventions, evolving work routines and practices, and 24/7 culture in the contact centre industry makes it difficult for the employees to establish boundaries between their work and life domains.

5.4.2 Conflict between work-life domains

Women working in the contact centre industry mostly related to the notions of conflict between work and life domains. In this regard, Greenhaus and Beutell (1985) explained that conflict could be time based, strain based, or skill based. Since, call center job is low on skill requirements, no skill based conflict was noted in the scenario. However, time and strain based conflicts were evident from the responses of the employees. Further, Zhang et al. (2020) related to a role based conflict, where different roles may require different time and energy resources to be effectively performed. Presence of a role based conflict was also noted in the contact center industry of Pakistan. It is pertinent to note that Pakistan represents a traditionalist society, which has a patriarchic culture, where women are expected to engage in household roles related to household management and also discharge caregiving responsibilities to children, husband, and elderly. This requires women to allocate time

and energy in performing these roles. Further, life domain of women changes after they get married or after they become mother, where the change is marked by additional set of responsibilities. Thus, women have different perspective on work-life balance. This study considers such specificities, where this section relates to all three types of conflicts – time based, strain based, and role based; that were found present in contact center scenario being investigated in this study.

Firstly, time based or temporal conflict arises due to a conflict of time allocation between two domains. Considering women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan, it was noted that most had household and care giving responsibilities, which one respondent related to as a 'juggle with kids, elderly parents, and other activities'. Employees were found to sacrifice their family time due to their job. Notions pertaining to 'missing on my family engagements', 'missing out time with my son', 'struggle to find time for myself and my family', 'working crazy hours', and 'burden of excessive work', were highlighted to relate to the conflict of time allocation between work and life domain, where work domain was highlighted a requiring more time resources, leaving less time for the life domain. One of the respondent highlighted the dilemma by stating that, "the last three years have been a real struggle as I was struggling to find a balance between nonstop work and my health. I was upset that I was unable to give myself any time". Another respondent exclaimed that,

"I only want enough time to spend with my kid and my husband".

Same was repeated by another respondent,

"I am always short of time for myself so how come I would find a time left over to spend with your loved ones".

Even the supervisor interviewed had difficulty managing her time as she related that,

“sometime, I struggle to give time to my son as well. My husband also complains, and shows his disapproval and dissatisfaction over my mid days shifts, where I end up spending most part of the day at work”.

In this context, it was highlighted,

“that the real conflict between work and home revolves around identity and how employees manage time”.

In this regard, one of the respondent provided details on the conflict. She highlighted that,

“I end up spending 12-16 hours at work. It leaves me with limited energy and time, either I can go home and do house chores or play with kids. As a result, my husband also gets extremely limited attention from me. I rarely get time to speak with my in-laws as well which has built an uneasy atmosphere at home”.

This indicates that work domain drains most of the available time from the women employees working in the contact center industry, and they have limited time to deal with the responsibilities related to the home aspect of the life domain. One of the respondent puts the blame on the society, where long working hours are considered a sign of hard work. She expressed that,

“as a society we think that long working hours are sign of prosperity, which is wrong in so many ways. It has adverse effects on family and social relationships and definitely leads to an increase in the conflict... The extra working hours at work on daily basis jeopardizes my work life balance and, in some cases, destroys my personal and social relationships. I am hardly left with any time to pursue personal interests. The daily travel timer has also robbed me of precious time that I could have constructively spent for my personal growth or family matters”.

The second most prominent theme emerged from the respondents was related to the role based conflict. Women in Pakistan are expected to perform household management and caregiving roles, even if they are doing some formal job. In this way they are tangled with both work responsibilities and home responsibilities, giving rise to work-family conflict. In this regard, notions related to 'demands of multiple roles'; 'juggle with kids, elderly parents, and other activities'; 'family pressure along with work demands'; 'sandwiched between professional and personal challenges'; and 'tug of war between the professional and their personal life and professional life'. The role conflict for women working in the contact center industry could be explained in three situations. First, if the employee is unmarried, having no husband and child care responsibilities. Such respondents face role conflict, while considering to perform personal chores. One of the unmarried respondent highlighted that,

"I am working fifty hours a week in a job that barely enables me to wash my clothes myself."

Two other unmarried respondents related to a conflict between their role as employee and as student. One of these explained that,

"I am not married and my family lives in a different city, so my real challenge is to cope with this dual battle with work and study...I struggle to keep up with the pace and requirements of my study. My teachers think that I am only working to enjoy perks of working for a multinational company, which are hardly any. On the other side, my managers think that I do not put enough effort on my shift as my priority is my study"

On second level, married women have to perform household management and care giving roles. Such married women are expected to perform household responsibilities and take care of their husband and in-laws. One of such respondent highlighted that,

“I do not have kids now, but I am already struggling to balance different roles...You are judged on your ability to provide pleasures to your family, and let me add in laws as well. So, I must ensure that my in-laws are happy with me at any cost, even if it means that I do not get any time for myself.”

On third level, the toll of conflict is heavy on the mothers, who have to take care of their children in any way. One of the respondents explained this in societal context, where

“we expect women to stay at home and raise kids. Then there are ever increasing economic expectations as well. Taking care of families and kids is considered as a complete feminine activity and then they should balance it with work as well”.

This dual role become very much difficult for the women. One of the respondents indicate this scenario,

“particularly, mothers are less satisfied with their work-life balance or quality of life in contact center. If you imagine that along with this tough job, they still must go back and complete bulk of the housework and childcare, it is a scary picture”.

Therefore, there was indication that women tend to resign from the work after child birth. One of the ex-employee iterated that,

“I had to resign after my daughter was born, as I was unable to manage work and home at same time”.

This was further explained by another respondent, who stated that,

“several women employees leave their job during maternity, since most of the jobs in customer care demand zero flexibility. After maternity break as well, women employees tend to resign, as they prefer to stay at home”.

One respondent explained this phenomenon in its full manifestation by stating that,

“I feel greater pressure now as not only, I am responsible for primary care of my children, but also extended family of my husband... The caring responsibilities cause heavy stress on working women when it is combined with their professional duties.”

The third aspect of the work-life conflict identified was strain based conflict, which causes strain from one domain to spill over to the other domain. Here again, it was noted that contact center work is taxing. Thus, stress or other related feelings or behaviors could spill over from work domain to the life domain. There were indications that strain of the work was influencing life of the women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan. One of the respondent noted that,

“the whole work environment leaves me psychologically drained even after work. I feel aftershocks even at home”.

It was again highlighted by another respondent stating that,

“burden and responsibilities of work are slowly but surely taking toll on my life”.

Respondents also indicated that work domain was causing the unease in the life domain. One of the respondent indicated that,

“increased workload always takes a lot out of me and I struggle to have any sort of relaxation time. Along with less time to unwind during these periods, I also struggle to maintain healthy sleeping habits which further adds up to trauma of busy shifts”.

This implies that stress of high work load in the work domain could creep into the life domain to cause distortions. This was also highlighted by another respondent, who explained that

“my parents are always making jokes of me that I cannot stand anyone. My younger brother think I have become this character from games ‘angry bird’... And frankly and secretly I do agree with them. I do not have patience for anything anymore. I literally start shouting for very minor occurrences. And all of this is because of my work

routine.”

Interpretations

It was noted that work-life conflict exists in the contact center industry of Pakistan, where women employees are unable to allocate proper time to the life domain, due to high time allocation requirements from the work domain. In this regard, Menaria (2016) accepted that high work load and long work hours make it difficult for women in the contact center industry to effectively deal with their family responsibilities. Hechanova (2013) also highlighted that employees working in the contact centre industry were unable to allocate appropriate time to their life domains. Many other studies also highlighted that full time employees in the contact centre industry experience higher level of work-life conflicts, compared to their part-time counterparts (Bohle et al., 2011; Chambel et al., 2017; Russel et al., 2009). Thus, work in the contact centre industry in Pakistan gives rise to a work-life conflict, where high work demands and time requirements leave contact centre employee were fewer hours to cater to their family responsibilities and personal needs.

There was also indication of the strain based conflict between the work and life domain of women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan. Numerous studies have highlighted that call center work is difficult and exhaustive (Baker et al., 2003; O’Brady & Doellgast, 2021; Simons & Buitendach, 2013), and such wok could give rise to the feelings of frustration among the employees (Zito et al., 2018). Considering the roe based conflict, it was noted that married women also feel more role conflict between work and their other roles. The role conflict is also quite evident in this regard, where the conflict is higher for females, and even higher for the females with child care responsibilities. Previously, Joseph (2015) noted that married women an women with kids could experience a greater work-life conflict. Likewise, Asuncion

(2008) noted that such role based conflict could force married women to quit their jobs, while Domingo-Cabarrubias (2012) noted that women employed in contact centre industry had a greater work-life conflict. Overall, this study highlights a work-family-life conflict for women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan, where the conflict was temporal, role based, and strain based in nature.

5.4.3 Spill over between work-life domains

Lastly, there was also an indication of the affective spill over, mostly from work to the life domain. Spill over theory argues that behaviours, emotions, and experiences could spill over from one domain to the other. In this regard, one of the respondent provided a strong stance indicating that,

“I have been working here for 8 years now and it has literally destroyed my personal life.”

The same respondent iterated that,

“it is also important not to allow your work life to spill over into your personal life and this is where I have suffered a lot.”

Edward and Rothbard (2000) noted that spill over could be either instrumental or affective; where instrumental spill over relates to the spill over of skills or behavior learnt in one domain to the other; while affective spill over is related to the spill over of moods and attitudes from one domain to the other. Considering the responses of the women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan, there were indications of the affective spill over, but not instrumental spill over. Following discussion relates to the spill over aspect of work life domains for women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan.

Considering the excess workload and tiresome environment of the contact centres, q negative experience seem to be spilled over from the work domain to the life domain.

In this regard, respondents related to the notions of 'aftershocks' and 'spill over' to relate to this. One of the respondent highlighted the dilemma stating that,

"the dual stress or burden follows you wherever you are, work or at home."

Another respondent also related to the stress spill over, stating that,

"Like me, many of colleagues end up with spillover of work domain into other aspects of life, which results in increased level of stress."

It has also been indicated that contact center work is stressful and hectic work, and such stress is likely to spill over to the life domain of the employees working in such stressful environment. One respondent highlighted this scenario by stating that,

"there is a one common sight in contact center, where you find every one stressed and pre-occupied. Lot of employees take this stress and work issues back to home and then bring them back to work"

Same notions were elaborated by another respondent who argued that,

"the whole work environment leaves me psychologically drained even after work as I feel aftershocks, even at home...This constant pressure has created an oppressive, exploitative and stressful situation at workplace which follows us back to our homes."

Interpretations

There was also some evidence of a negative spill over from work to life domain was evident in responses of the women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. Literature and analysis of this study explained that contact centre job is stressful and burdensome (Deery et al., 2010, Pico, 2006). The stress could be aggravated by dealing with the frustrated and abusive clients (Maos, 2014; Poddar & Madupalli, 2012). In this regard, Zito et al. (2018) explained that strain experienced in the work domain, while working in a contact centre could spill over to the family and other aspects of life. Thus, workers working in the contact centre industry could bring the

frustrations and stress of work to their family and life.

5.5 Discussion

Contact center industry has witnessed a tremendous growth around the globe and also in Pakistan. In Pakistan, the industry has got much growth potential, which could contribute towards the economic development of the country (Siddiqui, 2023). Despite the huge economic potential of the industry, the general perception of the employees working in the contact center industry is not much positive. The industry is work intensive and runs 24/7, where workload and related stress is quite high. This indicates that dynamics of the industry have not improved over the time as previously Taylor and Bain (1999) have related to the nature of the industry in international context. Subsequently, many researchers have highlighted notions related to high work pressure and strife work environment (Woodcock, 2016; Zielińska, 2019), and situation is no different in Pakistan (Akhtar, 2019; Khalid et al., 2013). There were also indications that call center jobs were more suitable for males and for younger individuals. There is a long debate on the suitability of call center jobs for the females, yet majority of employees in the call center work are females. Belt (2002) characterized call centers as 'female ghettos', where women were exposed to tough work routines and lower career progression options. These notions were also endorsed by other researchers stressing that women employees in the contact center industry face tough work routine and work related exploitations (Hunt & Rasmussen, 2010; King, 2020).

Despite the rough work environment and related routines, women get employment in the call center industry due to its lower skill related requirements of the job and transport facility provided by the call centers. Studies have noted that service sector with lower skill requirement jobs like in call centers have been considered feminine

jobs (Deka, 2020). Further, Senthana et al. (2020) noted that women are get referred to the lower-skill and lower wage job segment, as job is not considered an important aspect of their life. Further, free and reliable transport was found to be a very attractive point for the female employees in the contact center industry. Pakistani is a traditional patriarchic country, where there are many constraints related to female mobility (Farooq, 2020; Khan, 2021; Malik et al., 2020; Starkey et al., 2021). Previous work on the availability of group female transport endorses the value of the transport to improve mobility of women along with other educational and employment related outcomes (Broker, 2021; Cheema et al., 2019). Noor and Isa (2020) also noted that women have rely on their male relatives for their mobility. This context, transport facility is a very lucrative option, which frees the males from an added responsibility to pick and drop the women in the family. This makes contact center a lucrative job for the females as they are provided a group transport services, which although consumes more time of women in pick and drop, but is considered reliable, safe, and no cost option. This section discusses the findings of the study related to the lived experience of women employees of contact center industry, where they relate to the work in the contact center, life of a women working in a contact center, and work life balance of such women.

5.5.1 The work domain of women working in contact center industry of Pakistan

The work domain of women working in the contact center industry was characterized by multiple factors highlighting difficult nature of the work. The themes identified with regard to the work domain were monotonous work, high workload and long working hours, high monitoring and target based work, lack of flexibility, low support from the managers and organization, lower prospects of growth, penalizing reward strategy,

profiling and pressuring, lower focus on employee wellbeing, and lower motivation and satisfaction. All of these aspects are quite negative and seem to hinder the prospects of work-life balance of women employees working in contact center industry of Pakistan.

Firstly, work in the call center industry is highly standardized and monotonous in nature. In this regard, Woodcock (2016) connoted to call centers with the factory settings, where work is performed under a standardized manner. Female employees are expected to follow a standard protocol, while greeting and communicating with the customers. The work is boring and there is no breaks between the calls. Taylor and Bain (1999) related to this as an 'assembly line in the head'. Loukidou et al. (2009) noted that monotonous nature of work could lead towards boredom, whereas boredom is characterized as an unpleasant emotional state of employees (Tsai, 2016), which have been found to have association with negative work behaviors like the job dissatisfaction and turnover intention of employees (Kass et al., 2001; Wihler et al. 2022), absenteeism (Hanna et al., 2005; Kass et al., 2001; Shackleton, 1981; Teng et al., 2016), stress and depression (LePera, 2011; van Hooff & van Hooff, 2016), counterproductive work behavior (Bruursema et al., 2011), and lack of general life satisfaction (Seçkin, 2018; Waterschoot et al., 2021). Previously, Modau et al. (2018) stressed that call center work and environment is based on monotonous work, which is repetitive and unchallenging in nature. This could lead the employees to feel boredom, and boost negative behaviors among the employees.

One of the most distinguishing feature of call center industry is high work load and long working hours. Aldor-Noiman et al. (2009) highlighted that workload in the contact call centers is variable in nature, where the load is high during peak time and also during weekends. This implies that contact center cannot manage the high

workload by employing more staff, and existing staff is used to manage workload during peak time and days to ensure cost efficiencies. Previous literature on the call center work has endorsed the notions of high work load and work pressure in the contact center industry (Deery & Kinnie, 2004; Simons & Buitendach, 2013). Dhanpat et al. (2018) explained that high workload and associated pressure forces employees to work long and odd hours to meet their target in the contact center industry. Such increased workload could cause job stress, burnout, and ultimately provoke employee turnover (Chaudhary et al., 2023; Dhanpat et al., 2018; Simons & Buitendach, 2013). Long working hours in the contact center industry also add to the workload of the employees. In this regard, Johnson and Lipscomb (2006) indicated that long work hours take a toll on the mental and physical wellbeing of the employee. Long working hours have always been a cause of conflict between employees and employers, since the industrial revolution (Hunnicut, 1984). Such long working hour is still in practice in Pakistan (Abbas et al., 2015; Ahmad & Javed, 2015), and one of the important factor contributing to the difficulties of work-life balance (Dhanpat et al., 2018). Much of the issues pertaining to the work-life balance were described by the respondents of this study in the light of workload and long working hours. Such work practices of long working hours and work overload hinder the ability of women to effectively function in the life/ family domain, giving rise to a work-family conflict.

Another pressure related to the work domain of the respondents was related to the monitoring practices in the contact center industry. Employees at the contact center industry are assigned with quantitative targets, and their performance along with the quality of calls is regularly monitored. Neely et al. (2003) explained that managers at call center have sole responsibility of monitoring their agents to ensure quality service. Budhwar et al. (2006) explained the dynamics of monitoring in the contact center

industry, where time spent on each conversation is noted, calls are recorded and conversation is monitored. Such excessive monitoring could cause stress among the employees and could contribute to their fatigue and workload perceptions (Taylor & Bain, 2005; Pico, 2006). Russel (2008) also highlighted tight managerial oversight and intense target orientation in the contact center industry, making the company more competitive, but causing stress to the employees. Domingo-Cabarrubias (2012) argued that women feel more stress and pressure compared to men, due to their engagements in the family domain. Thus, excess monitoring cause unease to the women working in the contact center industry, brining stress to their lives.

One of the most repeated theme, highlighted by the women employees of the contact sector industry was lack of flexibility in relation to their job at the contact center. They highlighted that they suffer from the continuous work, where there is no break and no leave. Further, schedule and policies at their workplace was discouraging flexibility. In this regard, Domingo-Cabarrubias (2012) explained that although both male and female employees are exposed to the same strife work environment, women experience things differently due to their health issues, pregnancy and lactation related issues, safety concerns in nightshift work, and family related responsibilities. Thus, women employees might need more flexibility to manage their issues and responsibilities. Chung and Lippe (2020) highlighted that organizations around the globe are shifting towards flexible mode of working, where employee have control over where and when they work. Singley and Hynes (2005) highlighted that flexible work is more important for the women due to their family related responsibilities. In this regard, Chung and Horst (2018) noted that flexible mode of work allows women to maintain their work hours after childbirth. Likewise, Fuller and Hirsh (2019) also found that flexible working enables women to retain their job in the times of high family

related demands. Although, there are indications that women may use flexible work options to allocate more time to their family, causing a family-work conflict (Hilbrecht et al., 2008). Despite these nations, flexible work options could enable women employees to better manage their life domain affairs, and remain more content with their work domain. Work flexibility has been found to have an association with lower work pressures (Russell et al., 2007). In this regard, Valcour (2007) highlighted that control over work hours was associated with improved work life balance in call center industry environment. Clark (2009) also noted that operational flexibility was associated with better work life balance. Contact center industry requires a full dedication from the employees, where employees are required to complete their shift, and even forgo their annual leaves to obtain favor of manager. This are severe consequences for the nonstop work for professional and personal life of women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan. Non-flexible work might be the main restraining factor to improve work-life balance of women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan as most of the women are expected to take up household and caring responsibilities.

Next important restraining factor obstructing work life balance of women in contact center industry of Pakistan is lower managerial and organizational support. Women in the contact center industry indicated that most of the supervisors were male, who do not understand their issues and struggles. Further, work in the contact center industry was designed in a competitive fashion, where no employee is granted any support or favor. In this regard, Neely et al. (2003) noted that managers serve as a monitoring agent in the call center, focusing on achievement of targets. Managers discourage holidays and provide no support for personal and family circumstances of the workers of contact center industry. Pierre and Tremblay (2011) found that supervisors in call

centre organisations use authoritative measures to monitor and keep records of agents' calls and, as a result, agents experience high levels of uncertainty and discomfort which decrease their levels of job satisfaction. Thus, lack of managerial and organizational support is also a key restraining factor that hinders ability of women working in the contact center industry to achieve work life balance.

Another important job related factor was lack of growth opportunities for women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan. This indicates that employees disagree that they receive opportunities to grow within the organisation (Modau et al., 2018). A lack of growth opportunities (career advancement) has been found to have a negative influence on an individual's attitude towards the organisation, which in turn influences their intention to leave (Van Dyk et al., 2013). Such jobs are characterized as 'dead-end' and offer few career prospects (Deery and Kinnie, 2004).

Employee well-being was the next aspect of the women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan. Research revealed that 20% of call centre employees experience a medium level of stress and 40% of call centre employees experience a less severe level of stress (Khalid et al., 2013). Furthermore, the research showed that these levels of stress can be caused by targets as well, which makes the job more stressful besides dealing with hostile customers. Stress can lead to health issues, but can also increase the intention to quit (Lin et al., 2010; Arshadi & Damiri, 2013). Call centre employees deal with a variety of customers and because of dissatisfied customers that weatherise to be solved, a conversation with a customer might change rapidly in a negative way (Groth & Grandey, 2012). Dissatisfied customers sometimes show verbal aggressive behaviour towards call centre employees. Research has shown that call centre employees experience

approximately ten aggressive conversations with customers a day (Grandey et al., 2004). Verbal aggression is positively related to emotional exhaustion, which is seen as one of the most critical dimensions of job burnout (Grandey et al., 2004; Goussinsky, 2012). Van Rensburg et al. (2013) indicated high stress levels, high employee turnover and emotional burnout as factors associated with call centers. Call center work places a high burden on employees (Pillay et al., 2014). Visser and Rothman (2008) report that the call centre agent role is regarded to be one of the most stressful jobs in the present-day global economy. The call centre work environment has been associated with reduced employee well-being due to the nature of the work which has been linked to increased occupational stress, disengagement, burnout, absenteeism, and employee turnover (Modau et al., 2018). Such stress could spill over to the life domain and could cause the worker to become dysfunctional in the family domain.

A theme related to the women-work mismatch also came to the surface, where physical and social consideration could create certain issues in the work domain of women employees working in the call center industry. Firstly, women have to undergo maternity and hormonal issues that are different than men, making it difficult for them to manage their work. Staritz and Reis (2013) acknowledged that call centers exhibit lack of child care support and maternity leaves for the parents, making it harder for the women to continue job in the industry. Likewise, Rowe et al. (2011) also explained that call center work could be suited to the part time work routine, making it feasible for the women to opt a job after maternity. Apart from the maternity, pregnancy time could also be challenging for the working women (Greenberg et al., 2009; Salihu et al., 2012), where work load and related pressure of call center work hinders women's ability to have a good outlook for the work. The second aspect of this mismatch is that

women in Pakistani society are expected to get married at the earliest. This tendency of getting married early have been found to reduce employment prospects of women (Assaad et al., 2017). Thus, social and physical consideration restrict the ability of women to manage work domain as expected in the contact center industry of Pakistan.

Lastly, themes pertaining to the discrimination and patriarchic culture also came up. Like other Asian economies, Pakistan has a conservative society with strong patriarchal roots (Hadi, 2017; Weiss, 1990). In this regard, Tabassum (2016) argued that women in Pakistan are only deemed suitable for household roles, and not for the employment roles. Further, women are considered weak gender, and are not considered suitable for the managerial positions in patriarchal societies (Abalkhail, 2017; Jamali et al., 2005). Agnihotri and Srivastava (2017) also noted a lower number of managerial positions for women in the call centres of India. This adds to the woes of the women employees, as male supervisors in the call centres are unable to understand their situation. Respondents also related that women had lower growth and earning opportunities in the call centres of Pakistan. Gender discrimination on growth and compensation has always been a cause of concern in work settings (Esteve-Volart, 2004; Ginther & Hayes, 2003; Pudnery & Shields, 2000; Russen et al., 2021). Banerjee et al. (2009) found evidence that women could face discrimination during employment process of call centres in patriarchal settings. Overall, women were found to face patriarchy and discrimination in call centre jobs in Pakistan.

5.5.2 The life domain of women working in contact center industry of Pakistan

It was observed that the life domain of the women could be segregated into three major aspects i.e. family aspect representing husband, children, extended family of

the husband, and parents; self-aspect representing time for self, entertainment and leisure, sports and exercise, education, and hobbies and interest; and social aspect representing social relations. The dominating theme in the responses of the women working in the contact center industry was their family aspect, where they highlighted their role as a 'manager of household' or 'caregiver'.

Pakistani society expect women to manage household and fulfill their role as a caregiver to children and older dependents. Itrat et al. (2007) highlighted that the culture of Pakistan is organized around a joint family system, where people prefer to live in a large family. Within this family setup, women have limited economic role and expected to uphold honor of the family as home maker and caregiver. On the other hand, only male members of the family are charged with the responsibility of earning and livelihood and provide financial support to the family (Tabassum, 2016). This leaves women with a restriction to stay at home to uphold family honour and manage household chores (Grünenfelder, 2013). Kamal and Tariq (1997) also argued that women in Pakistani society are disapproved for their economic pursuits, and are socially obligated to perform household chores. Therefore, paid work comes after the household responsibilities of the women in Pakistan (Omar et al., 2004). The household responsibilities of the women are not confined to their immediate family members like husband or children, but also extended family from husband or parent side (Noor et al., 2021). At home, women are expected to cook and serve food, do cleaning and laundry, help men and children to ready for work and school, and deal with relatives and other family guests. Women working in the call centre of the country were found to be working for supporting their families, and it was also noted that they were expected to perform household chores in addition to their work related responsibilities, leaving them to have little time for themselves and relaxation. The

social role expectation from the women in Pakistani society creates difficulty for them to manage work and family at the same time, and many women prefer to quit their job after getting married or having a baby to care for. This implies that household responsibilities overshadow career aspirations of women in Pakistan, and they have to choose their family over their job in most instances. Women wanting to do the job have to juggle between work and family responsibilities, both of which require considerable energy and time to manage.

The second aspect of the life domain of the women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan was 'self-aspect', which was related to the women doing something for themselves like having self-time, pursuing entertainment and leisure activities, participating in sports or exercise, improving their education, and having hobbies. Although, these aspects were related to the women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan as viable part of life; most of the women highlighted that they were unable to dedicate time or energy to their self-aspect of their life domain. The extent of time for self or leisure time for different activities have been consistently found to be inadequate in previous studies conducted on the working women. In this regard, Siddiqui (2005) noted that paid work does not liberate women from the household chores, but instead makes them to squeeze their leisure time. Likewise, Pundery and Shields (2000) explained that women in the role of mother and wife need to lend a hand in domestic chores, even if they are involved in the paid work; which leaves them with the less free time for leisure and related activities. This has been the situation from quite some time, where Green et al. (1990) noted that women along with their jobs are involved in caregiving responsibilities of dependents including their children, husbands, and elderly and both caregiving responsibilities and household work along with the job leave them with almost no time for their own self and leisure

activities. Recently, Yerkes et al. (2020) supported these notions highlighting that countries with conservative societies, lower paternity leaves, limited child care options, and lower political voice for women. In this context, women are occupied with multiple roles with higher workload, causing a deterioration in the quality and quantity of their leisure time (Chatzitheochari & Arber, 2012; Haller et al., 2013). It has also been found that women are adjusting in their nature, and their sense of responsibility prompts them to adjust their leisure activities in accordance with their household demands (Miller & Brown, 2005). It is also noted that women are more likely to include their children in their leisure activities, than men (Chatzitheochari & Arber, 2012; Craig & Mullan, 2013), making their leisure time and activities less enjoyable (Miller & Brown, 2005). With reference to the call centre work, James et al. (2016) highlighted that work patterns in the call centres, particularly night shifts take a toll on the leisure time of the employees. They also highlighted that it distorts the quality of time spent with the family and community. (James et al., 2016). With regard to the exercise, Toomingas et al. (2012) highlighted that women spend more time in the sitting postures in the call centers, and recommended more physical activity and exercise to fend off consequent health issues. Despite such requirements, Lit et al. (2015) noted that Pakistani women are less likely to exercise due to social norms and their work - home related engagements. Overall, it could be argued that women working in the contact sector industry are no different than any other working women, where they prioritize their household and work. This leaves them with lower time for leisure activities, and even in that limited time they allow their children and family to be a part of their leisure space.

Lastly, social circle aspect was also deemed important part of the self-domain by some respondents. Here again, negative responses were expressed by the

respondents highlighting their inability to maintain a healthy social life. It was highlighted that women working in the contact center and keeping up with the family responsibility did not have much time for their social life, other than the family life. Pakistan, being a conservative patriarchal society, limits mobility of women (Masood, 2018), confining the social life of women to a small group, mostly from the family (Safdar & Ghani, 2018). Habiba et al. (2016) also highlighted that women in Pakistan undergo a resocialization process after marriage, where the process is controlled and directed by her in-laws. This coupled with job and household responsibility makes the personal social circle of women almost non-existent. Work nature in the call center industry could make development and maintenance of social circle more difficult. James et al. (2016) explained that call center workers, particularly those working in the night shifts, have lower levels of social integration, leaving them with less friends and unsatisfied social relationships. Patel (2006) also highlighted that call center employees experience a diminished social life over the time, as they are unable to keep in touch with their friends and also family. Poster (2007) also noted the same. Pal and Buzzanell (2008) also concluded that call center workers acknowledge disruption of their social and cultural life due to their work routine. Putting this all together, women in Pakistan has limited social circle and social mobility, which is further confined after their marriage. If we combine this with the tough work routine at the call center and household responsibilities, they do not have any time for their social circles. Therefore, much of the respondents did not highlighted their social circle, and kept highlighting their family aspect as the most prominent facet of the life domain.

5.5.3 Work-life balance of women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan

Women working in the contact center industry seemed to juggle work and life roles within time limits of a day, where they try to cope up with the high work load and long working hours at work, and struggle to keep up with their household responsibilities, leaving them almost no time for leisure, rest, and socialization. Considering the theocratical premises on the work life balance, it was observed that women working in the contact center industry were unable to segregate their work and life domains from each other, where work domain seemed to be overshadow the life domain due to 24/7 culture. Modern work routines and integration of information technologies with work has created more challenges in this regard, where employees at home are expected to remain in touch with the work. In this regard, Deery et al. (2010) noted that product range, services, pricing, and discounts rapidly change at contact centre industry, and employees have to read, absorb, revise, and update information constantly to remain updated and ensure consistent customer services. This requires the employees to remain in touch with the work, even after the routine working hours. Segers et al. (2008) also argued that call centre work is boundary less by default. Kamp et al. (2011) argued that dynamics of the work settings have changed and a new form of boundary less work setting have emerged. Ciolfi and Lockley (2018) highlighted the role of information technology, which has ability to connect people in remote locations. ICT has value, but it has intensified the work beyond the confines of the work place and working hours, rendering the modern work boundaryless. Field and Chan (2018) also noted that teleworkers use ICT and are able to attain rapid boundary transition, blurring the work-home boundary, making work-life interface boundary less. Modern ICT technology, competition in contact centre industry, and requirement of rapid flow of information have deemed the modern work settings boundary less and call centre work, having high ICT integration is no expectation in this regard.

A relatively more prominent theme pertaining to the work life-balance of working women in the contact center industry highlighted notions of a conflict between 'work' and 'life' domains' The conflict was mostly temporal in nature with some indications of a strain based conflict. There also indication of a role based conflict, where women employees were unable manage their household roles in an effective manner. Firstly, temporal conflict was most highlighted conflict by women working in the contact center industry in Pakistan. It was noted that women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan had high work demands, requiring them to sacrifice household and self-time. The remorse for not having proper family time was higher for married women, and even higher for women with kids. Menaria (2016) highlighted the nature of the job in the contact centres, making it difficult for women to allocate time to the family issues. Hechanova (2013) also noted the same work-family temporal conflict in the call centre work, where employees working in the call centre industry were unable to spare time for their family and social relations. In this regard, studies have also documented that full time call centre employee experience higher work-life conflicts compared to the part time employees (Bohle et al., 2011; Chambel et al., 2017; Russel et al., 2009), making time flexibility an important element in work-life balance considerations. This is more server for the working women, due to their home related responsibilities. Second most prominent conflict highlighted was a role based conflict, where it was noted that women are expected to perform different roles during their life time. Unmarried women employees were found unable to perform self-chores and meet educational expectations, married women related to difficulty of performing household roles related to management of household and managing chores of their in-laws, whereas women with children need to perform a caregiving role to their children as well. This makes it a work-family conflict in nature, where work hinders the ability of women to

manage and take care of their families. Asuncion (2008) argued that such role conflict makes married women quit their job at the contact call centres, as women may not be able to keep up with the demands of family and work roles after marriage. Joseph (2015) also highlighted different nature of work-life conflict for different worker cohorts, explaining that women with children could experience a greater work-life conflict, leading them to have a lower level of work-life related satisfaction. Another study conducted by Domingo-Cabarrubias (2012) also found that women employees at call centres complained on the conflicts between work and other non-work domains like family, domestic, and social responsibilities. Thus, a role based conflict could be quite evident for women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan, where women spend a large part of their work day on the job in the contact centre, and remaining in their homes, fulfilling household responsibilities. Lastly, some strain based conflict was also noted in the responses of the women employees of contact center, where the strain of work was causing issues in the life domain of the respondents. In this regard, numerous studies have highlighted call center work as laborious and exhaustive (Baker et al., 2003; Kavitha, 2017; O'Brady & Doellgast, 2021; Simons & Buitendach, 2013), which could cause emotional dissonance and frustration among call centre employees (Zito et al., 2018).

Lastly, notions of affective spillover from the work domain to the life domain were also noted. It was highlighted by the respondents that working at the contact center was a tough and stressful job, and negative emotions experienced at the workplace were being spillover to their life domain. Employees working in the contact center industry were found to have been burdened and stressed, even in the life domain. Deery et al. (2010) related to call centre job as stressful, where the strain of the job could increase during the promotional campaigns. Pico (2006) also argued that excessive monitoring

along with a pressure to achieve performance target provokes stress and feelings of dissatisfaction among contact centre workers. Apart from these issues, there are issues pertaining to dealing of aggressive and abusive clients in the call centres (Maos, 2014; Poddar & Madupalli, 2012). The strain and exhaustion caused by the job could has negative implications for the quality of life (Deery et al., 2002; O'Brady & Doellgast, 2021). Likewise, Zito et al. (2018) also argued that emotional strain of call centre employees could spill over to their life outcomes. Simons and Buitendach (2013) also related that call centre workers are exposed to higher work pressures, intense workloads, and mental and physical exhaustion. Such environment makes it difficult for the worker to maintain a healthy social and family life. Thus, emotions, strains, and issues experienced at the job could spill over to the life domain of the women employees working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan.

5.5.4 Factors affecting work-life balance of women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan

This study provided a phenomenological enquiry into the work-life balance of women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan. Various facets of work and life of these women were identified and explained with reference to their lived experience. This section of discussion relates to the key factors that could have positive or negative impact on the work-life balance of women working in the contact industry of Pakistan. These factors include workload and working hours, flexibility, managerial and organizational support, discrimination and patriarchy, and household responsibilities.

First important factor that affects work-life balance of the women working in the contact center industry was related to the work load and working hours. It was noted that women working in the contact center industry were experiencing high work load

and long working hours. Such nature of the work was the main reason of creation of temporal and role based work-life conflicts. Strain conflicts and work stress also emerged from the high work load. In this regard, Michel et al. (2011) argued that work characteristics including work load and working hours have ability to explain work-life conflict. Subsequently, Chambel et al. (2017) also explained that work demands like work load and time pressure contribute negatively to the work-life balance of employees in the contact center industry. They further explained that employees have limited resources of time, energy, attention, and emotions, and employing more resources at work could lead to a work-life conflict, considering time based, role based, and strain based conflicts.

The second factors related to the work life balance of women working in the contact center industry in Pakistan was flexibility. Responses of this study indicated that women workers in the call center were deprived of any flexibility or flexible options related to the shift or work and work burden. Bohle et al. (2011) found that flexible work options were related to work-life conflict in the call center industry. Hechanova (2013) also highlighted the issue of work schedules in the contact center industry as a major source of work-life conflict. Further, Chambel et al. (2017) found that part time work in the contact center industry could be useful to mitigate work-life conflict in the contact center industry. All of this implies that flexibility in the scheduling and work burden could be instrumental to mitigate temporal and role based conflicts of women working in the contact center industry of Pakistan as working less hours could enable the women employees to attend to their household responsibilities and spend time with their family.

Next important factors related to the work life balance was managerial and organizational support. Here again, it was found that women employees working in

the contact center industry of Pakistan had lower support from their managers or organization. Michel et al. (2011) deemed social support at work place (from organization, supervisor, and coworkers) as one of the most important predictor of work-life conflict. Chambel et al. (2017) also found that supervisory support had negative implications for work-life conflict, especially with reference to time based conflict and train based conflicts. In this regard, Bohle et al. (2011) explained that schedule control and work related flexibilities could be sought from a supportive supervisor in the call center industry. Likewise, organizational support is instrumental to alter worker related policies. Despite its importance, it was found that most of the supervisors on the women contact center employees were male managers. It was further argued that male managers could not understand the issues of female employees. Moore et al. (2005) highlighted that women employees feel more comfortable and experience more job autonomy under the supervision of a female manager. Lastly, Hechanova (2013) found that supervisor support moderated the impact of work-life conflict on the turnover intention of employees in the call center industry. Overall, women employed in the contact center industry could better cater to their work-life balance needs under the supervision of a female manager as female managers are more understanding and communal in nature (Eagly & Wood, 2012) and may be better suited to provide and negotiate support for women employees working in the contact center industry of Pakistan.

There were also indications of discrimination and profiling of the women, where women getting married or having children were profiled to label them as inefficient and weak. This implies that women employees need to prove their competence in the work settings every day, as their gender is stigmatized to have lower achievements. Tabassum and Nayak (2021) explained women stereotypes, where women are

considered timid, weak, and emotionally unstable. Such discriminative attitude puts more pressure on the working women, forcing them to strive hard to prove their worth and fend off stereotypes. Such extra effort could lead the women straight to the work-life conflict.

Lastly, family related responsibilities were also deemed an important predictor of work life balance of women. In patriarchal societies, like Pakistan, women are considered home makers and are charged with a primary responsibility of manage household and take care of elderly and children (Masnsoor & Abid, 2020). In this regard, Tas et al. (2021) quoted UN Women to report that women spend 11 hours a day on the household chores and caregiving activities, compared to only one hour for men. In this study, it has been noted that working at contact center industry was difficult, and managing the whole household in addition to that makes things more difficult. Women working in the contact center industry seem to juggle between work and family roles, giving rise to a role based conflict. Such role based conflict is embedded in the societal norms, where women have to take care of the household (Eagly & Sczesny, 2019). This household role is fixed for the women, even if they decide to opt for a formal employment. Thus, working women have to bear the burden of responsibility of dual roles, one related to formal job and other to household unpaid work (Gordon & Kauppinen, 2019). Patel (2020) related to the struggle of women working in the call center and explained the nature and extent of the work-life conflict of women, who struggle to keep up with both job and household roles. Thus, it could be argued that household roles cause work-life conflict among women working in the contact sector industry of Pakistan.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

This chapter addresses the conclusions of the study. It commences by revisiting the research questions and to what extent these have been answered based on the findings of the study. This is followed by a critique of the study's limitations. This is followed by contributions of this study to the theory of work-life balance and practice in the contact centre industry of Pakistan are highlighted. Finally, implications for the practice and directions for the future research are stated in the end of this chapter.

6.1 Revisiting the research questions

This study posed three research questions: the first question asked, How women working in contact centre industry of Pakistan describe their work-life balance experience? For answering this research question, this study found that the work domain for the working women was characterized by high work load, long working hours, lower flexibility, lack of managerial and organization support, lower job growth, and discriminated and patriarchist work settings. Such work demands had negative consequences for employee work behaviours and wellbeing. Life domain of women working in the contact centre industry was dominated with the family life, requiring them to take care of household chores and family members. A lack of free family time, personal time, and leisure time was evident in the responses of women working in the contact centre industry. Overall, no physical or temporal boundary existed between work and life domains of the respondents and notions of a work-life conflict was quite evident, where women had to manage household responsibilities and bear with long working hours and high workloads. The conflict was temporal, role, and strain based in nature, making it difficult for the women to manage work, family, and life aspects

together.

The second research question asked, which factors restrain or support attainment of work-life balance of women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan? This study found that these factors were related to work load, such as working hours, work related flexibility, managerial and organizational support, profiling and discrimination, and household responsibilities in a patriarchal society. These factors were related to both work and family domains, as in Pakistan, social role expectations require working women to take up household and caregiving responsibilities, forcing them to juggle with work and household responsibilities at the same time. This spared them with little or no time at their disposal, depriving them with personal and family leisure time. The findings indicate that women working in the contact centre industry experience a work-family-life conflict, where their life mostly revolves around their work and family responsibilities, and they cannot have quality time with their own self, family, and friends.

The third research question of the study asked, how contact centres in Pakistan can provide support to their women employees to enable them to attain a better work-life balance? In section 5.5.1, while discussing the findings, this study clearly highlighted a lack of flexibility and support for women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. This implies that embedding more flexibility into work domain and also breaking the shackles of societal norm of patriarchist society could improve work-family-life balance of women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. The goal here should be mitigation of temporal, role-based, and strain-based conflicts by enabling women to manage their work-family routines by introducing flexibility in contact centre industry and providing appropriate managerial and organizational support. Thus, women working in the contact centre could be facilitated by improving

work flexibility and managerial support in the organizational settings of contact centre industry of Pakistan.

6.2 Limitations of study

Despite the contributions and value of the findings, the study has certain limitations. The study has two major limitations: first, the data was collected from respondents during the COVID-19 pandemic, which restricted the ability to travel to Pakistan and collect data face to face. The situation also restricted the ability to follow up to clarify things and collect more data. Most of the contact centre employees were working from home and were not easily available for interview and the follow-up. Second, data for this study was collected from contact centres of only one telecommunication company. Although, the selected company is one of the largest cellular companies in Pakistan, such limitation on the scope and breath of data collect limits the generalizability of the findings at industry level.

Considering the first limitation, COVID-19 disrupted lives of people around the globe. Travel restrictions were imposed, people were encouraged or forced to stay at home, and face to face interactions were minimized. Under such circumstances, I was unable to travel to Pakistan, visit workplace of respondents, and collect data through face to face interviews. I collected data through online interviews, where I ensured that respondents remained at ease, and they were given option to get interviewed in more than one sittings. I also conducted follow up interviews with respondents, when required. Moises (2020) also recommended adaptation of online mode of data collection during COVID-19. Likewise, Jones and Abdelfattah (2020) also deemed online interviews optimal during the pandemic. Despite unfavourable circumstances, unease, and interactional difficulties; I was able to collect relevant data from respondents and complete my study. However, the data collection took twice of the

expected time due to abovementioned circumstances. The second limitation is that most of the referrals I obtained were from contact centres of one of the largest cellular companies, which could limit the scope of the study. However, reviewing the literature, I observed that work settings described the respondents were typical description of a call centre work environment (Ahmed & Javaid, 2015; Akhtar, 2019; Belt, 2002; Guest, 2002). This assured me on the reliability and validity of the data and led me to the assertion that the data collected could be useful for the contact centres of Pakistan. Both of these limitations could be taken up in subsequent studies to further validate findings of this study. Despite these limitations, this study has increased the understanding on the nature of work-family-life conflict for working women in patriarchal societies like Pakistan, and have paved the path of future research into this line of enquiry.

6.3 Contributions to work-life balance practice

This study highlights work-family-life conflict among women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. Women working in the contact centre industry spend whole of their day on their paid job, after that they are expected to discharge household responsibilities, and are deprived of any family or personal leisure time. The practice pertaining to work-life balance calls for maintaining a balance between work and life domains of life. Such calls ignore the fact that working women in the conservative and patriarchal societies have a compulsory family role to manage. The study notes that women face difficulty in managing work, family, and life domain. We aim to contribute to the practice on work life balance by proposing a broader conceptualization on work-family-life balance. Based on the findings, following are some actionable recommendations in this regard:

- The domain of family should be treated separate from the domain of life in conservative societies like Pakistan. Sharabi and Harpaz (2011) and Sharabi (2017) explained that women have high centrality for family among other life domains, including work. Hesse-Biber and Carter (2005) also highlighted that work-family conflict is more prominent for women, even in the western economies. This implies that women would always be involved in their home related responsibilities. Separation of family from life domain would highlight family as a distant and important domain, which would enable managers and practitioners to understand the duality of responsibilities being dealt by the working women in the conservative economies like Pakistan. This would enable the managers to consider the family burdens of working women, while supporting them at the workplace and providing them flexibility in their work routines.
- This study found that the work-life issues of working women in a patriarchist society need to be recognised and dealt by incorporating more flexibility in their work routines and duty roasters. Drew and Murtagh (2005) argued that women prefer to avail a flexible work routine for family and quality of life reasons. Singley and Hynes (2005) also explained that flexible work enable women to better manage their family, and it became more important for women after childbirth to retain their jobs and maintain their work hours (Chung & Horst, 2018; Fuller & Hursh, 2018). Working women could be facilitated to deal with high workload and long working hours through flexibility policies. Flexible options pertaining to management of their work schedule could boost morale and quality of life of working women (Papalexandris & Kramar, 1997; Subramaniam et al., 2013) and encourage more women to participate in the

economic activity. Workhours swap policy, occasional work from home, and mandatory breaks could be used to facilitate working women in Pakistan.

- Previous research has argued that work related flexibility leads women employees to dedicate more time to family domain, leading towards a family-work conflict (Hilbrecht et al., 2008, 2013; Singley & Hynes, 2005). Van der Lippe et al. (2018) also explained that women feel responsible for childcare and housework, leading them to dedicate more time of these activities. Therefore, some previous research argues that work flexibility could only reduce work related burden and increase family burden, leaving no net result on overall work burden of working women. A socialization and leisure at work policy could be used to provide necessary personal time to the working women, where Fritz and Sonnentag (2005) argued that leisure activities could leads to recovery from work and family responsibilities, whereas Newman et al. (2014) highlighted that leisure could detach people from their responsibilities, reduce stress, and enable people to replenish themselves with the necessary resources to start anew on their responsibilities. Therefore, organizations could provide opportunities to their women employees to dedicate some time to their personal life.
- There is need to realize that women undergo various phases in their lives. Life of women changes after getting married, during their pregnancy, and after having children. Such phases re-endorse importance of family for the working women (Cousins & Tang, 2004). Some respondents highlighted their intention to quit after these life changing events, as such events could make it more difficult for women to manage work and family domains. Bernardi et al. (2017) also highlighted that mothers are more likely to reduce working hours and quit

their job temporarily, than fathers; leading to the assertion that married women, particularly mothers have a preference of family domain over their work domain (Snir et al., 2009). This requires special considerations in order to accommodate their needs and embed flexibility in their work-family-life routine. In consideration of the special requirements of the women, an appropriate representation of female managers should be appointed at workplace with women employees. This study also showed that lower proportion of female managers, whereas women respondents highlighted that male managers were unable to understand their work-family-life needs. Appointment of an appropriate proportion of female manager would also reduce discrimination and profiling of women employees.

- Certain policies of contact centre industry seemed exploitative, where managers in contact centre industry discourage leaves, off days, maternity leaves, and other forms of flexible options. There is a need to strengthen employment regulations in the countries like Pakistan to enforce rights of working women in Pakistan, who are a deprived of their justified flexibility options.

6.4 Contributions to work-life balance theory

This research indicates that women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan are exposed to intense and inflexible working routines of the contact centre industry. In addition to that social roles expectations also require these women to play house roles of caregiving and household management, which is also deemed a full time unpaid work in patriarchal society of Pakistan. Thus, working women in Pakistani society have dual work responsibilities – paid work and unpaid work at home, that leave them with limited time to have personal and leisure time making it a work-family-

life conflict, where contact centre work consumes much of the time of the women employees, and all remaining time goes to the management of house hold. Respondents in this study even expressed their discontent on their time allocation to the family domain, and personal or leisure time aspect had the least attention from the respondents. The contributions to the work-life balance theory stem from these findings, where it is proposed that work-life balance of women working in a patriarchal society in general, and women working in contact centre industry of Pakistan in particular should be considered in a social role perspective as proposed by Eagly (1987).

6.4.1 A social role perspective on work-life balance

Literature on the social role theory explains a gendered perspective on the social roles, and this perspective could be used to enrich revelations of this study. Social role theory argues that social roles evolve from societal and environmental factors, where males and females are assigned different roles on the basis of their physical appearance, strengths, and social norms (Eagly & Woods, 2012). The theory further explains that gender roles emerge as a result of socialization and social reinforcement, where society and family treats girls in a particular manner and reward appropriate 'girl' behaviour from the start of their life. With time, certain roles become associated with a particular gender (Martin, 2012). Thus, women are expected to do unpaid household work and take care of children and family members (Lippa, 2010). My findings are consistent with these notions where working women, despite having paid work related responsibilities, were performing unpaid house work, which is a full time job. The social role expectation from women not only brings extra responsibilities for women, but also extends their work domain to include family related responsibilities. This requires extra time commitment and physical effort on the part of

the women, where a women must dedicate more than half of her active day on a paid job at her workplace, and remaining half on an unpaid job in the household. In this regard, Thomposn (1991) explained that women consider household work as essential part of their life, and they do not have any option to quit household work (Parreñas, 2015). These notions were explicitly expressed in this study, where women working in contact centre industry felt guilt for not giving much time to their family. This accounts that work-life balance should be considered in relation to social roles of the respondents, where such roles could cause intensification of load in one domain or the other like social role expectations from the males overstress their economic role (Moazam & Shekhani, 2018), while females are charged with home responsibilities (Tabassum, 2016). Such roles expectations from women could intensify in a male dominant and patriarchist culture of Pakistan, where people live in a joint family system (Itrat et al., 2007). In this context social role perspective clarifies the work-family struggles of women in patriarchist culture. Findings of this study provide an insight into social role aspect and its implications into the theory of work-family balance. Findings of this study opens a new perspective into the work-life balance debate, where societal roles should be taken into account in work life balance considerations.

The work-based conflict model only accounts for two domains, where work routines and responsibilities could create issues in the life domain, or vice versa. This study documents that societal expectations or socially imposed roles in patriarchal societies could create and temporal and role conflict between these two domains. In this context, Leslie and Manchester (2011) argued that work-family is not a women issues, rather a social issue. Previously, Bruke and McKeen (1994) noted that working women are more stressed compared to men, and this stress stem from their actual or

expected societal role. Likewise, Linhen and Walsh (2000) explained that socially defined roles of women explain their role in the household, implying that the role identity of women is influenced by societal values and norms. Such role impositions exacerbate role conflict for women, between work role and family role.

Figure 6.1 Work-Family Conflict – Role of Social Expectations

Thus, in patriarchist societies like Pakistan, work-family conflict for women is exacerbated by the externally defined social roles, and not due to intrinsic factors related to the work or family. Figure 6.1 highlight this revelation representing the nature of conflict between work and family domains in countries like Pakistan.

6.4.2 A work-family-life perspective

Findings highlight a role based and temporal conflict being experienced by women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan as they were full time indulged in two roles: paid work role and non-paid household role. Both of these roles require

significant time and energy commitments that impact on family and personal commitments and personal activities. This redefines the nature of conflict for women working in contact centre industry of Pakistan. Conventional notions on the work-life balance/conflict mostly relate to two domains of employee life i.e. work domain and life domain, where initially life domain was only conceptualized as family domain (Keeny et al., 2013) devoid of any social, personal, or leisure time or activities. Modern conceptualization of life argues that there is much more to the life than only family (Pichler, 2009). The findings of this study indicated that women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan consider personal and leisure activities separate from their family responsibilities. Even within the family domain, one aspect could be related to the household responsibility and other family leisure time. Thus, considering a multiple identity perspective (Coulmas, 2019; Thoits, 1983), it could be argued that people could have different identifies in different domains of their life.

Working women in patriarchal societies like Pakistan juggles with multiple roles and multiple identities. They do paid work in the work domain, and unpaid work in the family domain. This extends their work domain to incorporate both work and family domains. The fact that such women have little time and energy for their life domain highlights this domain as neglected domain, where women are deprived of time and energy to spend leisure time with their own

Figure 6.2 Work Family Conflict for Women in Patriarchal Societies – An Extended Model

self and their family; participate in sports, exercise, or healthy activities; engage with their hobbies and interest; and interact with their social circle. Thus, this study highlights that women in patriarchal societies like Pakistan have at least three domains of life i.e. work, family, and life domain, where they do both paid and unpaid work in work and family domains, which extends scope of the work domain. On the other hand, life domain of such women mostly remains neglected, giving rise to a feeling of deprivation and dissatisfaction. Therefore, work-life debate in the patriarchal societies needs to be redefined to account for family domain and life domain separately. Figure 6.2 provides extended model for work-family-life conflict in patriarchal societies like Pakistan. The model recognizes a conflict between work and family domains of the working women's life, where work related issues like high workload, long working hours, lower flexibility, lack of support, lower job growth, discrimination and patriarchist environment could cause temporal, role, and strain based conflict between work domain and family domain. The family domain of the model is also recognized as separate domain from life domain, where family domain relates to the management of household and care of other family members. The model also recognize the influence of social expectations on the work-family conflict, being experienced by working women. Lastly, the model also recognizes life domain as a separate domain, separate from the family domain. The life domain was related to leisure time, social circle, and other discretionary activities.

6.5 Implications for practice

Considering the revelations of the study, following are implications for the practice on work-life balance of working women in patriarchal societies like Pakistan:

- Managers supervising women employees need to understand that women are strongly attached with their family, and have social obligation to discharge

household responsibilities. This could enable them to understand their situation and extend necessary support to them to enable them to function effectively in both work and family domains.

- Organizations, employing women, need to realize differences between male and female employees, where female employees undergo different phases in their lives. Their life could drastically change after marriage and after child birth as well. In order to provide necessary support to women during such phases, such organizations could appoint more female managers or could train their male managers to extend necessary support to their female employees to navigate through the changes in their lives.
- Organizations, employing women, should also note that life domain of most working women is neglected due to their work and family responsibilities. Thus, organizations and managers could provide certain facilities to enable women employees to socialize with each other, participate in sports, do exercise, pursue some hobby, bring children at work to spend time with them, and enjoy some recreational activities. This would not only enable working women to appreciate their employer, but also enjoy the good moments in their life.
- Work intensive organization like contact centres should consider incorporating element of flexibility in their work routines. Policies like mandatory break after two hour work, higher-lower workload in different weeks, workload swapping with co-workers, part time work and work from home during pregnancy and after childbirth, four-day work week , and the like could be used to infuse flexibility in work routine of work intensive organizations.

6.6 Implications for policy

Based on the findings of this study, following are implications for the policy makers to facilitate working women in patriarchal societies like Pakistan. Policy makers could facilitate working women at two levels:

First at policy or legislative level, policy makers could develop policies and pass necessary legislation to provide ease to working women in different phases of their lives. As indicated in the analysis, women undergo various phases during their life. They get married, bear children, give birth, and raise children. This implies that they might require different type of support and flexibility during different phases of their life. Most countries have a maternal/ paternal leave policy but after that policies and legislation does not offer any support to allow work flexibility to raise children. Policy makers could develop policies and push for legislation, allowing women to opt for part time work, flexible shifts, or work from home. Such policies could encourage women to take part in economic activities and contribute positively towards economic development of the country.

Second at the implementation level, policy makers could pass necessary orders to collect data on working women. In Pakistan, public institutions like worker welfare boards, labour & human resource departments, women development department, and others could be instructed to implement policies related to women welfare and work flexibility. Previous studies have found that social welfare policies have weak implementation in Pakistan (Ali & Knox, 2008; Butt & Asad, 2016). Policy makers could push for the policy implementation related to maternity leave, equal opportunity, women empowerment, workplace safety, and other labour related laws and policies. A strong implementation of the women worker welfare policies could prevent women from work exploitation, profiling, and discrimination. Likewise, flexibility related policies could also create a breathing room for working women in Pakistan.

6.7 Future research

Future research in the domain of work-life balance of working women could consider the limitations of this research. More specifically, future research could use face to face mode of interviews, and also could collect data from contact centres of more than one companies to further validate findings of this study. Further, such study could also be conducted in other geographical regions of South Asia like India and Bangladesh to find implications. Following are some other suggestions for the future research:

- This study highlights a three domain frame work of work-family-life balance. This is a promising avenue and future research could be directed to understand the notions pertaining to family and life domains of women working in the contact centre industry of Pakistan. Understanding both of these domains is important as both of these domains account for a significant part of their awake time. Such researches could focus on development and proposition of ways through which household responsibility could be managed in better manner to spare some time for other domains of life. Within this context, links of social role theory for work-family-life domains could be explored to expand theocratical premises and nature of work-family-life .
- Lives of women take many courses over the time, where events like marriage and child birth significantly alter their life, sometimes forcing them to leave their paid jobs. This study has highlighted that married women and mothers face more difficulty in managing their work-family-life balance. Subsequent studies could consider the work-life balance of women before and after these events to find particular implications for married women and working mothers.

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